

iMPACT HTA

The logo for iMPACT HTA features the word 'iMPACT' in a bold, black, sans-serif font, with a lowercase 'i'. The letter 'C' is replaced by a circular graphic consisting of several concentric rings in various colors (yellow, green, blue, purple, pink) that create a rainbow-like effect. To the right of this graphic, the letters 'HTA' are written in the same bold, black, sans-serif font.

D12.2 - An exposé of lessons learned and policy recommendations

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Abbreviations

AIFA	Italian Drug Agency
AGENAS	Regional Health Agency (Italy)
BIA	Budget Impact Analyses
BSC	Best Supportive Care
CADTH	Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health
CEA	Cost-Effectiveness Analysis
COVID	Coronavirus Disease
CPI	Consumer Price Index
cTTO	Composite Time Trade Off
csDMARD	Conventional Synthetic Disease-Modifying Anti-Rheumatic Drugs
d-CEIs	Decrementally Cost-Effective Interventions
DCEs	Discrete Choice Experiments
DICE	Discretely Integrated Condition-Event
DRG	Diagnosis-Related Group
DSA	Deterministic Sensitivity Analysis
DSU	Decision Support Unit
EC	European Commission
EMA	European Medicines Agency
EU HCSCD	European Healthcare and Social Cost Database
EU	European Union
EUnetHTA	European Network for Health Technology Assessment
EUR	Euro
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
HAS	Haute Autorité de santé
HB HTA	Hospital-Based HTA
HIV	Human Immunodeficiency Virus
HRQoL	Health-Related Quality of Life
HSUV	Health State Utility Value
HTA	Health Technology Assessment
i-CEIs	Incrementally Cost-Effective Interventions
ICER	Incremental Cost Effectiveness Ratio
ICUR	Incremental Cost-Utility Ratio

MAH	Marketing Authorisation Holder
MCDA	Multi Criteria Decision Analysis
NICE	National Institute for Health and Care Excellence
NRS	Non-Randomised Study
OA	Osteoarthritis
OBMEA	Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreement(s)
OMP	Orphan Medicinal Product
OR	Odds Ratios
PER	Political Economy Report
PRISMA-P	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Protocols
PRO	Patient-Reported Outcome
PROM	Patient-Reported Outcome Measure
PSA	Probabilistic Sensitivity Analysis
QALY	Quality-Adjusted Life Year
QoL	Quality of Life
RA	Rheumatoid Arthritis
RCT	Randomised Controlled Trial
RDT	Rare Disease Treatment
ROR	Ratio of Odds Ratios
SMA	Spinal Muscular Atrophy
SMC	Scottish Medicines Consortium
SVJs	social value judgments
TKR	Total Knee Replacement
T2D	Type 2 Diabetes
VBA	Visual Basic for Applications
WP	Work Package
WS	Workstream
WTP	Willingness To Pay

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The IMPACT HTA objectives

Although health and social care policy remains the responsibility of EU Member States, there is an increasing perception that there is an opportunity to improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the use of health technologies to support sustainable health systems by implementing cross-country collaboration in a range of activities, including Health Technology Assessment (HTA). Recent years have also seen significant changes: data on costs and health outcomes are now available from an increasing range of sources underscoring the need for better data integration and evidence synthesis, as well as the strengthening of data generation processes for economic evaluations and the improvement in methodological quality. Based on these developments, the overall objectives of IMPACT HTA are:

- To contribute to the understanding of variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, the rationale and criteria for decision-making across different settings as well as the factors and preferences that shape HTA recommendations;
- To develop and disseminate innovative methodologies, toolkits, frameworks, processes and software aiming to aid decision-making and improve efficiency in resource allocation in a number of areas including: extrapolation from RCT data; the development of a common and comparable dataset on health and social care costs across EU countries; quality of life measurement with emphasis on patient preference elicitation; a value assessment of medical technologies framework, including multi-criteria decision analysis; and guidance on how non-randomised studies can inform health economic evaluations; and
- To develop and disseminate tools facilitating EU-wide collaboration across Member State governments, HTA agencies, health care professionals, patients and the broader stakeholder community.

Key Outputs and Associated Impacts

On the submission of the original proposal in 2017, IMPACT-HTA had the ambition to deliver on each of the 10 distinct research areas it proposed. From an over-arching perspective and based on the results achieved four years later, IMPACT HTA has contributed to the creation and implementation of new methods, tools, guidance and processes in several distinct areas of economic evaluation and performance measurement, where there was urgent need for these. The 10 work packages (WPs) of

IMPACT HTA were derived from the above objectives and their achievements and expected impact are briefly outlined below.

- 1. Development and application of a tool to combine and use Randomised Clinical Trials (RCT) and observational/registry data in economic evaluation:** HTA staff will now be able to undertake quick, robust cost-effectiveness evaluations using local data. The Discretely Integrated Condition-Event (DICE) simulation model and all the open-source materials that support it are freely available for download at <https://dice.impact-hta.eu/>. DICE models are easily modified for local adaptation and this flexibility enables sharing models across agencies and from one appraisal to the next in a given therapeutic area.
- 2. Development of a costing methodology and a database of unit costs in health and social care.** The first European common database of health & social care unit costs in nine countries is now available. The European Healthcare and Social Cost Database (EU HCSCD) is easily accessible and can be used to feed into health-economic evaluations carried out by transferring economic evaluation analyses and models across countries. It not only saves researchers' time in searching costs, but also allows cross-country comparisons and provides an understanding of the variation in costs within and across countries. The database is publicly available on the IMPACT HTA website (<https://www.easp.es/Impact-Hta/>).
- 3. Health preferences of different sub-population groups using EQ-5D.** HTA institutions need to take into consideration the differences between patient health state preferences and the general population preferences as the choice of value set might lead to different decisions in the context of HTA. For national contexts where patient preferences are favoured, it is feasible to combine patient preferences and national general population-based value sets. Patient preferences which show the dimensions of health-related quality of life (HRQoL) that patients consider important can be used for treatment decisions in clinical settings and in organising health care processes. Value sets derived from the generic youth-specific EQ-5D-Y can be used in economic evaluations, particularly cost utility analyses, of paediatric treatments in the countries in which they were developed (Germany, Slovenia and Spain).
- 4. Methodological guidance on the analysis and interpretation of non-randomised studies to inform health economic evaluations.** The lack of randomised data continues to be a challenge in HTA because of the substantial scope for uncertainty about the effectiveness of new health technologies, including potentially exaggerated treatment effects. IMPACT HTA has developed a set of evidence-based recommendations for the use of non-randomised studies to estimate treatment effects in HTA, including the need to justify the use for a non-randomised study, to prospectively plan such studies. Such studies should consider possible biases and how to

address them and should transparently report the methods used. HTA systems need to be strengthened to allow effective appraisal of non-randomised evidence.

- 5. Methodological tools using multi-criteria value methods for HTA decision-making, including the creation of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework.** Recognising that the relative value of a health care technology spans across a multi-dimensional domain going beyond the classical concept of “economic efficiency” as measured by incremental cost effectiveness ratios (ICERs), two distinct contributions are made in developing and testing the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework: first, a model of the parameters associated with HTA coverage recommendations has been developed and tested empirically, encompassing product- and country-specific variables, regulatory variables, critical clinical and economic evidence parameters, the role of evidence uncertainties and the importance of social value judgements. Second, informed by primary and secondary evidence, the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework captures the value concerns of decision-makers and other stakeholder groups within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers and the broader stakeholder community.
- 6. Analysis of economic evaluation methods for hospital-based assessment.** Implementation of HTA recommendations can be challenging and the anticipated improvement in outcome might not be achieved. Hospital performance is multi-faceted and multiple hospital contextual factors can affect the ways in which health technologies are adopted. With a focus on medical devices, two toolkits were developed: the first assesses the overall hospital performance; and the second provides a methodology to assess how contextual factors affect the full implementation of a technology. The toolkits are supported by a decision model, which identifies the technologies with the same efficacy and safety but which are more subject to clinical variation and assesses different interventions with the goal of improving the performance and efficiency of healthcare delivery.
- 7. Expanding economic analysis for HTA: Methods for measuring the fiscal impact of new healthcare interventions.** Alongside the cost of a medical intervention, the fiscal impact of productivity losses provides an additional dimension characterizing the value for money of the intervention. This approach is based on the concept that an individual contributes to society and this contribution should be considered when assessing a new technology and that governments should invest in new medical technologies to increase the population’s health and thereby enhance productivity. There is a strong recommendation that fiscal impact should not be used to inform rationing policies or perform cross-group comparisons among different socio-

economic categories as it can lead to discrimination against the elderly and low-income subgroups.

- 8. Appraisal of Orphan Medicinal Products (OMPs) and associated guidance.** A new appraisal framework for OMPs, or more generally rare disease treatments (RDTs) has been created that ensures a fair, lenient, flexible and consistent appraisal, beyond clinical and cost effectiveness in an effort to overcome the associated challenges, notably the small number of patients (which can make clinical trials challenging) and the high cost of the technology. The framework is supported by recommendations and guidance for the appropriate use of Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) and Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreements (OBMEA) with RDTs. The Appraisal Framework can be used by individual health systems in the EU (which currently use different processes described in country vignettes <https://www.impact-hta.eu/country-vignettes>) and beyond, or for collaborative HTA initiatives and proposes ways of collaborating, such as an international repository for OBMEA plans and reports.
- 9. From HTA results to guidance implementation: behavioural considerations in the adoption of decrementally cost-effective technologies.** Decremental cost-effective interventions imply cost-savings at the price of a reduction in efficacy compared to usual care. Some of these interventions have been found to be highly effective but are much less studied compared to interventions implying both higher costs and efficacy gains. A Discrete Choice Experiment was designed to investigate under which conditions policymakers (or participants acting as such) might be willing to adopt decremental cost-effective interventions. A 'decision-tree' based on the results of the Discrete Choice Experiment is delivered together with a *Political Economy Report* that addresses the broader economic, ethical and political aspects associated with the assessment and adoption of decremental cost-effective interventions. These outputs provide policymakers with guidance on whether and under what circumstances to adopt potentially decremental cost-effective interventions.

INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognised that health technology assessment has a critical role to play in supporting access to effective treatment and that the methodology must adapt as the science of medicine expands and new treatment approaches become available. In Europe, there is also recognition that there is an opportunity for cross-country collaboration that can improve the effectiveness and efficiency of the use of health technologies. IMPACT HTA draws on the current knowledge and looks to the evolution of HTA to adapt to changing circumstances with the following overall objectives:

- To contribute to the understanding of variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, the rationale and criteria for decision-making across different settings as well as the factors and preferences that shape HTA recommendations;
- To develop and disseminate innovative methodologies, toolkits, frameworks, processes and software aiming to aid decision-making and improve efficiency in resource allocation in a number of areas including: extrapolation from RCT data; the development of a common and comparable dataset on health and social care costs across EU countries; quality of life measurement with emphasis on patient preference elicitation; a value assessment of medical technologies framework, including multi-criteria decision analysis; and guidance on how non-randomised studies can inform health economic evaluations; and
- To develop and disseminate tools facilitating EU-wide collaboration across Member State governments, HTA agencies, health care professionals, patients and the broader stakeholder community.

These objectives are addressed through the 10 work packages (WPs) of IMPACT HTA (Figure 1):

- The use of randomised controlled trial (RCT) and observational/registry data in economic evaluation;
- The development of a costing methodology and the creation of a core dataset of health care costs for facilitating cross border comparisons in economic evaluation;
- The role of social costs in economic evaluations and the creation of a core dataset of social care costs;
- Capturing health preferences across different patient diagnoses using the EQ-5D-5L;
- The analysis and interpretation of non-randomised studies to inform health economic evaluation;
- The use of multi-criteria value methods and their relevance for HTA decision-making;
- Economic evaluation methods for hospital-based assessments;

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- Measuring the fiscal impact of new healthcare interventions and incorporating this into HTA processes;
- HTA appraisal for orphan medicinal products; and
- HTA implementation: decremental cost-effectiveness

These WPs as well as their achievements and expected impact are discussed in the sections that follow.

Figure 1. The 10 work packages of IMPACT HTA

IMPACT HTA OUTCOMES AND IMPACTS

Development and application of a tool to combine and use RCT and observational/registry data in economic evaluation (WP2)

Objectives

This Work Package (WP2) focused on the development and application of a new, generic and publicly accessible platform to enable direct decision-analytic modelling for cost-effectiveness analysis (CEA) by HTA agencies.

HTA agencies (or their delegates) undertaking CEA to assess value for money normally have access to data on the efficacy of health care interventions and convert this into life-time health benefits through extrapolation. They must also extrapolate lifetime costs for the target population, including for treatment and for other healthcare resource use that may be modified by the intervention. However, HTA agencies are commonly constrained by the level of resources they are able to devote to the assessment of any given intervention. This work package provides guidance on the methods to be adopted to extrapolate both treatment costs and effects using data sets complimentary to RCT data, as well as providing an open-source Excel based platform that is simple, accessible, and generic in approach: The Discretely Integrated Condition-Event (DICE) simulation model.

The first task of this WP was to provide reviews of methods to match available HTA data with secondary observational data to facilitate such extrapolation. These reviews highlight the available methods that could be used to facilitate and support the development of the DICE simulation model - the primary objective within this WP - as any modelling approach can be improved when supported with better data. Such up-to-date reviews are important as newer techniques are continually being developed that allow matching across sample population distributions, thereby giving a better match to the whole of the sample population rather than a single parameter extracted from the distribution.

Methodology

For the review of extrapolation methods, the survival analyses (methods used, and justification for these methods) included in National Institute for Health and Care Excellence (NICE) Technology Appraisals between 2015-16 and 2019 were reviewed. NICE appraisals were selected because NICE

is a health technology agency that has focused on the use of cost-effectiveness in assessing new interventions and has developed a clear methodological stance for the extrapolation of evidence. NICE methods are also utilised as a benchmark by other HTAs internationally. The NICE Decision Support Unit (DSU) provides technical support documents to assist with HTA. NICE appraisals are also useful as WP2 used members of NICE to evaluate the DICE modelling approach that was developed within WP2.

The focus was on HTAs of treatments for metastatic cancer and on the use of extrapolation within Markov models (a frequently used modelling type in HTA, where future states depend only on the current state) to maximise comparability whilst maintaining a feasible sample of HTAs. We were particularly interested in the applicability of extrapolation methods for use in the DICE model captured within WP2. Metastatic cancer was chosen because of the recent debate over the use of overall survival *versus* progression-free survival as an endpoint for both trials extrapolated models in this area and also because it provides the opportunity to discuss the decision process for choosing appropriate end points.

DICE is a simulation method (Figure 2) that conceptualises a model in terms of its relevant information (“Conditions”) & how these change over time (at “Events”).

Figure 2. DICE in a snapshot

For the development of DICE, an early version of the engine (DICEd) was re-examined in light of the results of a survey of all European HTAs regarding the desirable features for such a tool. The DICE macro was extensively modified as follows:

1. Reading of all inputs into dictionaries in memory
2. All calculations moved to memory to speed up execution
3. Automatic handling of common expressions (turning off event recurrence; finding next event time and the corresponding next event)
4. Automatic naming of conditions and outputs from their respective tables
5. Filtering of patient profiles according to various user-defined criteria
6. Random selection of profiles
7. Weighted selection of profiles
8. Uncertainty table that can handle both deterministic (DSA) and probabilistic sensitivity analyses (PSA)
9. New scenarios tool to enable user to specify alternative structural options and reanalyse the model
10. Expression wizard that provides “point and click” approach to creating expressions
11. Equations handler that allows user to specify each model equation in a named table and then call it by name whenever needed
12. Suite of debugging tools including an active trace window with step through; Save log; equal sign toggle for verifying expressions; DICE name tester; Name lister.
13. New ribbon that makes all tools readily available to modeler

Several DICE trainings were held with the agencies and with academic teams involved in HTA (Appendix I). A website (<https://dice.impact-hta.eu/>) has been created as a repository of all the open-source materials, including the DICE engine, various templates, build guides, user guide, technical documentation etc. This site is freely available as an open-source site and all contents are available for download.

Key findings

Relevant HTAs between 2015-16 and 2019 were identified. All but two of these 47 HTAs provided some details of the selection process to choose an approach for extrapolating survival. Statistical tests were used in all but three HTAs (94%) and visual inspections were used in all but nine (80%).

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The plausibility of the distribution was a factor in 28 (60%) HTAs, and expert opinion was used in 19 (40%). The use of external data was limited to only ten (21%) of HTAs.

Several frameworks, guidelines or algorithms have been published to assist with choice of extrapolation model and help ensure these are chosen systematically. A framework produced by the DSU (Latimer 2013) has been used in recent HTA submissions. This approach was reviewed as well as a recent critique.

The DICE platform is a simple, yet sophisticated, tool that allows HTA staff to undertake quick, robust cost-effectiveness evaluations using local data with minimal training. The DICE model allows specification of a full choice of the type of structural CEA models commonly used in our field (cohort Markov models, microsimulations or discrete event simulations), operates transparently through an Excel workbook that is easily populated with local data, and gives fully presentational results in the form of forecasts of the health impact and extrapolations of the costs that support calculation of incremental cost-effectiveness ratios. The model is executed via a macro that is contained in an excel macro file (with extension xlam). The macro is generic in the sense that it executes any DICE model so long as it meets the simple requirements of such models. It is written in Visual Basic for Applications (VBA) and provided on an open-source basis to anyone who wishes to download it. It runs in both Windows and Mac environments.

Policy implications

Despite some developments, the extrapolation of survival and of costs for use in HTAs remains a work in progress. As the choice of extrapolation method can substantially alter the HTA conclusions, they should always be subject to extensive sensitivity analyses.

The ease with which DICE models are modified allows for easy local adaptation of a general structure. This flexibility enables sharing models across agencies and even from one appraisal to the next in a therapeutic area.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

- Carefully examine the assumptions made in extrapolating health benefits and costs
- Insist on extensive sensitivity analyses and quantification of structural uncertainty due to extrapolation

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- Adopt the DICE methodology for HTA as it provides for a common, open-source approach that discourages bespoke methods that are more difficult to review
- Provide support mechanisms for model sharing

Future Developments

Additional research is needed to ensure that the methods for extrapolation of benefits and costs are fit for purpose. Continued work in this area is in progress.

A further iteration of the DICE engine will include an interface to facilitate users adapting the model to their local context. It is hoped that an even faster engine and interface will be produced at a later stage, using an open-source language like Python.

Developing a costing methodology and a core dataset of costs for facilitating cross border comparisons in economic evaluation (WP3)

Objectives

To develop an easily accessible and usable core dataset of international healthcare costs for nine European countries (England, France, Germany, Italy, Poland, Portugal, Slovenia, Spain and Sweden), which can feed into health-economic evaluations carried out by transferring economic evaluation analyses and models across countries. The dataset may also be used to compare costs and explain the factors that account for differences in health care costs across settings. To achieve this, four specific objectives were set:

1. Produce a core dataset that incorporates direct health care costs across jurisdictions
2. Propose a methodological framework for computing homogenous cost data across countries on a sustainable basis over time
3. Enable cost comparability across settings, including the explanation of factors that account for differences in health care costs across settings
4. Produce a core dataset including both direct and indirect costs across a selection of countries (in collaboration with WP4)

Methodology

The first step was the design of the European Healthcare and Social Cost Database (EU HCSCD) structure, which was based on the literature review of different costing methodologies taking as references the manuals for economic evaluation, costing guidelines and accounting manuals of the Centre for Health Economics of the University of York. This included the decision on the number and type of costing items to be included, the category and subcategory each item belongs to and the number of attributes for each item.

The second step was verifying the costing methodology used in estimating the costs of items introduced into the EU HCSCD. A search through the Health Ministries' and health organizations' websites of each country identified cost databases of the items selected in the previous step and any publicly available documents describing the cost-accounting methodology used to construct them. Subsequently consortium partners verified these searches and identified any additional official databases with relevant data. Finally, a semi-structured questionnaire consisting of 14 questions grouped in 6 dimensions was designed to obtain information from partners (Appendix II). All

partners' responses were verified and clarified in an online workshop. All relevant documents were translated to English using online tools with the assistance of consortium partners in case of doubts.

Key Findings

The EU HCSCD can be freely accessed and used <https://www.easp.es/Impact-Hta/>. It includes 27 costing items organised in 3 main categories and 13 subcategories (Appendix III). The categories are organised as follows:

- Primary resources are those that cannot be further divided into smaller units and included medicines, medical devices, health products/ consumables and personnel
- Composite goods and services are bundles of several primary resources that are consumed jointly and include outpatient visits, hospitalizations, image diagnosis, laboratory tests, ambulance services, diagnostic procedures and therapeutic procedures
- Complex services and interventions are units of activity that aggregate diverse types of resources and are further divided into inpatient medical and surgical processes and day case procedures/outpatient services

To ensure the comparability of costing items in the database a number of attributes have been identified. Some attributes were purely informative, such as: 'Item subtype', that provides a more detailed description of the item; 'Bibliographic reference', that provide an URL of the associated cost database; 'Code', that is the combination of letters and/or numbers each costing item is described with in the original source; or 'Item in local language'. The latter three attributes help users to search the items in their original databases. However, most of the attributes were developed with the aim of providing users with information to assess the nature, quality and reliability of the unit cost estimates. These included 'Number of units' (number of items delivered in the year of observation that are included in unit price); 'Unit of measurement' (procedure, test, hour, visit, etc.); 'Type of unit value' (cost, tariff, public price, wholesale price, etc.); 'Type of institution' (hospital, primary care, ambulatory care, patient's home, etc.) or 'Notes' (includes all relevant information regarding costing methodology, such as what resources are included in the unit cost, identification of these resources –micro-costing or gross-costing–, valuation of resources –top-down or bottom-up–, etc.).

The database was designed to facilitate the transformation of the monetary value in the original year of the observation into the year defined for the analysis, using either the last available Gross Domestic Product (GDP) deflator or Consumer Price Index (CPI) in way that allows users to choose

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which they prefer. Costs of items that are introduced in local currency are automatically converted into euros.

The most important challenge in collecting the key information on the cost items searched was to identify the costing methodology used by the original source.

Regarding primary resources, the up-to-date public databases of medicines were found in each country. However, the English database can be accessed only from England. Costs of medical devices and health products/disposables were difficult to obtain and/or the costs were provided from past years. The comparison of costs of medicines, medical devices and health products is hampered by the variety of existing brands and/or models. Differences were also found in the type of unit value. In most countries, value added tax is included in the public price of medicines (France, Poland, Portugal and Sweden), but in England it is not. In Germany, Spain and Slovenia the reference price is available, while in Italy it is the ex-factory price. Possible monetary values placed on medical devices and health products were leasing price, ex-factory price, public price, purchase price, reference price and wholesale price. The personnel costs differ not only by type of cost elements included (e.g., travel, qualification costs, etc.), but also because of labour union negotiations, each country legislation, workers' seniority, etc.

The major reason of cross-country differences in costs of composite goods and services is the type of resources included in the costing item; however, in many cases these could not be verified because of the lack of transparency and/or the lack of publicly available costing documents. In England, all of the costs are based on DRGs, whereas in France, Germany, and Poland only some of them are, and in Italy, Portugal, Spain and Sweden none of them are. Cost of outpatient visit depends on whether it is led by a general practitioner, nurse or specialist, and whether it is performed at the centre, at the patient's home, web-based or by telephone. The type of specialist also influences the cost of visit. Usually, the cost is set per visit, but in Slovenia, the cost of an accident and emergency visit is costed by team/year as well. Day of hospitalization is not estimated in France, Germany, Italy and Slovenia. The cost of image diagnosis depends on duration, contrast (yes/no), patient's age, number of areas and whether the patient had accessed the service directly or through his/her primary doctor (England); part of the body scanned (France, Germany, Italy and Portugal); part of the body scanned, contrast (yes/no) and number of areas (Poland); and part of the body scanned, contrast (yes/no) (Spain and Sweden).

Regarding laboratory tests, the cost of an individual test is available in all countries except England. In Spain, the total cost excludes both the cost of extraction and processing the request. Cost of

ambulance services differs across countries because of the unit of measurement (journey, intervention, kilometre, patient/year, mobile unit/year, hour) and the type of service (urban, interurban, transport for dialysis, etc.). The cost of diagnostic and therapeutic procedures varies depending on item subtype (e.g., acute or chronic haemodialysis, oxygen therapy using liquid oxygen or portable concentrator, etc.).

Complex services and interventions are organised in diagnosis-related groups (DRGs), which may have attributed costs or tariffs (or both). Most direct costs and variable overheads are included in costing items of all countries. Fixed overheads - mainly teaching costs, research costs, depreciation of building and financial costs - are included in DRGs in some countries, but not in others. Teaching and research costs are included in Slovenia and very partially in Portugal. Depreciation of buildings is included in all countries except Germany, Slovenia and Spain. Financial costs are included in England, France, Poland, Portugal and Sweden.

Policy Implications

The EU HCSCD is the first publicly available European database of healthcare unit costs. It is a very user friendly and intuitive database with a simple user's manual. It saves researchers' time and effort in searching costs and allows cross-country comparisons and understanding of the variation in costs within and across countries. The detailed information included in the EU HCSCD provides an excellent input for reference unit cost templates developed as part of the PECUNIA project (<https://zenodo.org/record/4279100#.YH0ujOjHw2w>).

Recommendations to Stakeholders

Setting up a stable consortium in charge of improving, updating and ensuring the continuity of the EU HCSCD, mainly for economic evaluation analyses, is recommended. Although the database updates costs automatically according to the most recent GDP deflator and CPI, each time the cost of an item is updated in the database of a country, it needs to be modified in the EU HCSCD in order to maintain the database as up-to-date as possible. The list of cost items and the number of participating countries should progressively increase. The consortium could set up an EU Task Force to periodically revise, improve, harmonise, and standardise the costing methodologies in healthcare at EU level and apply them to the generation of unit cost data for the EU database. Finally, the consortium could develop a procedure to regularly issue standard country unit costs lists and use it

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as the preferred option (or base case) in economic evaluations for pricing and reimbursement decisions.

Future Developments

This WP proved the feasibility of having a database of healthcare costs and the challenge is to secure funding for its continuity and improvement.

We suggest that all users should propose amendments for amplifying the number of costing items and updating the costs in the future. Users who apply to access the database will also have the opportunity to submit data. The principal administrator (from the WP3 team) will be in charge of periodically revising the data and making the updates. All changes will be notified to the users by email. Those users wishing to be in the mail list can send an email to Prof Jaime Espin (jaime@easp.es). Each time a new item is proposed, subscribed users will receive a notification to search for that item in their country and to send it to the above contact.

The role of social costs in economic evaluations for health care decisions in Europe (WP4)

Objectives

The overall objectives of WP4 were divided into three different objectives (resulting in 3 different tasks):

1. To determine what wider effects, with specific emphasis on the societal perspective, need to be measured in the context of economic evaluation
2. To identify how such wider effects are valued and whether these can be incorporated into decisions within the health sector in a formal way
3. To produce a core dataset (together with WP3) that help to incorporate the societal perspective across jurisdictions and a methodology that will ensure sustainable data collection/reporting over time

Methodology and Key findings

Task 1: Revising the methodological aspects applied to the identification, measurement and valuation of social costs in economic evaluations

➔ *Methodology*

A narrative and analytic report was developed which reviewed the most relevant methodological studies on economic evaluations of valuation of social costs in the last decades. The report aimed to provide an overview of how social costs are usually defined in the literature of economic evaluation of health care technologies, taking an in-depth look at the valuation of paid and non-paid time of the person affected by a specific illness or injury and of their non-professional (informal) caregivers. The report also reviewed the recommendations of international guidelines for the consideration of a funder and/or societal perspective in economic evaluations and the recommendation on how social costs should be included. Finally, a systematic review was performed to test whether social costs were included in economic evaluations and which methods were applied looking at five diseases (Alzheimer's Disease, rare diseases, depression, Diabetes Mellitus, and multiple sclerosis).

➔ *Key findings*

With respect to the valuation of patient's paid time, the human capital approach is the most commonly used method in economic evaluations of health care interventions although the debate about whether the human capital approach or the friction cost method is preferred is far from over.

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While the theoretical debate has not progressed in recent years, there are advances in other lines such as the identification and incorporation of *presenteeism*. In contrast with the valuation of paid time, the evidence on methodological aspects related to patient's non-paid time is very scarce.

The debate about the different available methods for valuing informal caregiving time has been less intense. However, there seems to be an agreement in cost of illness studies and the economic evaluations reviewed on the ease of applying the opportunity cost method as it has been the most commonly used approach to value informal care costs.

The most appropriate perspective (the health care financier perspective; the societal perspective; or both) and the methods that should be applied when the inclusion of social cost is considered relevant is still not resolved and is discussed in international guidelines and in the applied literature: consensus has not yet been reached. When the societal perspective is recommended, some guidelines explicitly recommend a method of productivity-loss valuation. When informal care consideration is explicitly mentioned, only few guidelines establish recommendations on how it should be valued.

Task 2: Selected case studies to quantify different ways of incorporating the social perspective into an economic analysis to inform European decisions

→ *Methodology*

Several systematic reviews were carried out to analyse whether the inclusion/exclusion of social costs (mainly informal care and labour productivity losses) could modify the results and conclusions of the economic evaluations performed in Alzheimer's Disease, rare diseases, depression, Diabetes Mellitus, and multiple sclerosis. The search strategies covered 2000 through November 2018, using two different databases: Medline and the CEA TUFTS registry. The inclusion criteria used were: original studies published in a scientific journal; being an economic evaluation of any intervention related to each disease, including social costs (informal care costs and/or productivity losses); written in English; using quality-adjusted life-years (QALYs) as an outcome for the incremental cost-utility analysis; and separating the results according to the perspective applied.

→ *Key findings*

The conclusions are that, although a recommendation for the application of a wider perspective (societal perspective) has been included in several international guidelines, the inclusion of social costs - mainly productivity losses and informal care costs - is limited in the existing literature. The inclusion of social costs led to a relevant change in results ranging from 18% to 30% of the economic evaluations, depending on the case study considered. However, it should be noted that the

consideration of the societal perspective leads to changes in the conclusions regarding the adoption of the assessed intervention in only a small number of the economic evaluations reviewed, although differences between diseases were found. More precisely, in the case of Alzheimer's Disease, about 11% of the economic evaluations changed their main conclusions when social costs were included, 4% in rare disease, 10% for depression; 7% in the case of diabetes and 15% in multiple sclerosis (Appendix IV).

Task 3: Creating a database on unit costs in Europe of lost work time and the value of informal and formal care time (coordinated with WP3 on unit costs of health services).

→ Methodology

Unit costs of social resources were identified and collected based on the systematic literature review of task 1 & task 2. In the case of long-term care resources (formal and informal care), the unit cost of social costs reported by the original authors were extracted from the reviewed references. If the authors did not provide this information directly, the cited reference by the authors was accessed. In addition, the method used to estimate or collect these unit costs was collected along with the unit cost in the online database. The disease-related studies included in Task 2 were used to obtain up-to-date unit costs from a set of European sources. Regarding the unit cost of labour productivity losses, wages by age and gender, employment rates and the number of worked paid hours were obtained from Eurostat.

All collected data were uploaded to the European Healthcare and Social Cost Database (EU HCSCD; available at: <https://www.easp.es/Impact-Hta/Default>) which provides up-to-date unit costs adjusted by price and currency. Exchange and currency rates were obtained from official sites.

Policy Implications

Task 1 - The valuation of social costs has experienced considerable methodological developments in recent years, with remarkable accuracy of time identification and valuation tools, for both patients and informal caregivers. Nonetheless, research efforts in this field of interest should increase in the coming years to improve the volume of existing scientific evidence.

Task 2 - The consideration of the societal perspective instead of the healthcare funder's perspective can modify the conclusions of the economic evaluations performed. Depending on the therapeutic area considered, this change can be modest or more substantial. Moreover, the consideration of the societal perspective does not automatically result in a lower incremental cost-utility ratio for the healthcare technologies analysed. Several of the studies included revealed that the consideration of

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the societal perspective can make the ratio even higher. Although the reasons were diverse, the use of the societal perspective reveals that certain interventions increase the burden of informal care, which is not reflected in the analyses that use the perspective of the healthcare funder.

Task 3 - Researchers can access the online dataset freely and search for unit costs needed in economic studies when applying a societal perspective. Where future projects need to use unit costs this tool could be a useful repository where wages that might be imputed for the estimation of productivity losses or formal and informal care unit costs data can be easily located. The information in the database can be quickly accessed and ready to use (unit costs can be downloaded into a CSV file). Reducing the time to obtain unit costs of societal costs and facilitating the information required for performing economic evaluations from a societal perspective can increase the use of such a perspective.

Policy Recommendations

Although several international guidelines include recommendations for the application of the societal perspective, the inclusion of social costs - mainly productivity losses and informal care costs - is limited in the scientific literature.

To increase the consideration of the societal perspective in economic evaluations, it is necessary (i) to advance, in a greater methodological homogeneity, the evaluations performed in this field; (ii) to promote the inclusion of spillover effects on health of family members when informal care is a relevant resource for the intervention evaluated; (iii) to develop a general strategy to improve the access to data sources in the previous phases of identification and measurement of social resources; (iv) for those countries that recommend the consideration of the societal perspective in their guides to promote the application of their recommendations through appropriate incentives for researchers.

Our analyses show that the choice of perspective can change the conclusions of a certain percentage of economic evaluations. This can have direct consequences on financing and pricing decisions for medicines and other healthcare interventions. Decision-makers should request that economic evaluations apply a dual perspective, funder and societal, to have the most complete information when making decisions for pricing and reimbursement.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

The output generated in this WP could serve as a useful tool for several stakeholders, although the benefits or the applications could differ for each stakeholder.

The pharmaceutical industry could benefit by using the dataset generated when performing any cost analysis (cost-of-illness, economic evaluation) of a healthcare technology or pharmaceutical intervention. Moreover, by having access to this data, the industry could perform studies applying a broader perspective (the societal perspective) and compare those results with those of other perspectives.

The research community could benefit from having an accurate overview of several methodological issues in the valuation of social costs (mainly productivity losses and informal care costs), which could be useful when performing an economic evaluation from a societal perspective, depending on the available data. Secondly, based on the output created in the second task, researchers could decide which costs to include depending on the disease being studied, as our results have shown that the inclusion of social costs varies between diseases not only in terms of how often they are included but also in terms of which costs are considered. The reviews performed showed that the applications of the societal perspective should include both social costs and the health results on the patient's environment, which should be taken into account by researchers. Finally, when performing an economic evaluation from a societal perspective, the unit costs dataset would be an appropriate source of data that provides enough evidence regarding which costs to include depending on the chosen valuation method.

Patients' associations could use the information created in the second task to highlight the need to increase the investment in their disease-related interventions based on the evidence on which type of intervention could lead to more profitable outcomes since the results point towards a benefit from a societal point of view, which might be greater than when applying the narrower perspective of the healthcare payer/funder. In a small number of cases the application of a societal perspective might result in improvements to the health status of the patient and also to the health status of their caregivers, which could be another opportunity for patients' associations to gain more attention for their disease of interest.

The information provided here could be used by health technology assessment agencies, encouraging stronger recommendations in future guidelines to include the societal perspective when performing economic evaluations of healthcare technologies. Agencies should additionally recommend that it is relevant to take account of the impact on the health status (worsening of quality of life, greater burden and risk of burnout, etc.) of the relatives who care for patient. Finally,

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agencies could aim to foster a consensus on methodological issues when valuing and measuring social costs since wide methodological variations, limiting the comparability of studies, have been observed in the reviews performed, regardless of the disease.

Since the inclusion of all types of costs and health effects from a societal perspective would provide more detailed information, the conclusions of this WP could lead to a more efficient and equitable design of any health program or intervention which could eventually be implemented. The consideration of a societal perspective would help governments to consider the effect generated on all the agents involved in any healthcare intervention, and even to identify the target population who could benefit from those programs.

Future Developments

Firstly, it is recommended to extend the case studies to other disease areas to reveal if, and to what extent, the results of the five case studies are representative and can be extrapolated to all economic evaluations of healthcare technologies. Secondly, special case studies could be developed for other interventions/technologies such as vaccination programmes, medical devices, screening programmes, public health interventions, etc. And, finally, the EU HCSCD will require continuous maintenance and updating.

Exploring health preferences of different sub-population groups using EQ-5D (WP5)

Objectives

WP5 focused on patient reported outcome measures used in economic evaluation of treatments and health care approaches. Quality-adjusted life years (QALYs), combining life expectancy and health-related quality of life (HRQoL) are often used to express health gains in economic evaluations (Kennedy-Martin et al. 2020; Brazier et al. 2017; Drummond et al. 2015; Zentner et al. 2016). In that context, generic preference-based HRQoL instruments which have values sets available are necessary. Value sets are based on health state preferences, often those of the general population of a country, enabling the assignment of a value on a 1 (full health) to 0 (dead) scale to each health state described by the instrument, which can be used for QALY calculation. EQ-5D instruments are such preference-based HRQoL instruments and they are recommended in many national health economic guidelines (Kennedy-Martin et al. 2020). Even if it is the standard in most countries that value sets of HRQoL instruments are based on adult general population preferences, there is – in parallel – an ongoing discussion on these approaches and on the most appropriate reference population to obtain health state valuations to underpin HTA.

Within this scope, WP5 explored health state preferences of different sub-population groups using EQ-5D instruments. It examined differences in health state preferences of two patient groups compared to those of the general population in two countries, Germany and Spain. The relevance of this is that in some countries, e.g., Germany, value sets based on general population preferences are not accepted by health care decision makers and it is argued that patient preferences are more appropriate (Kennedy-Martin et al. 2020; German National Institute for Quality and Efficiency in Health Care 2017; Rowen et al. 2017). At the same time WP5 explored a perhaps more challenging topic, health state valuation for youth-specific instruments. There is currently a gap of generic preference-based HRQoL measures for children and adolescents that allow the descriptive system scoring needed for the calculation of QALYs (Rowen et al. 2020). Thus, WP5 aimed to develop value sets for the youth-specific EQ-5D instrument, the EQ-5D-Y (Youth) (Wille et al. 2010; Ravens-Sieberer et al. 2010), and to compare health state preferences obtained from the adult general population and from adolescents of the general population in three countries: Germany, Slovenia and Spain.

Methodology

Comparison of patient and general population preferences for EQ-5D-5L health states

EQ-5D-5L health state preferences were obtained from discrete choice experiments (DCEs) with rheumatic and diabetic patients in Germany and Spain using an online panel of a market research agency. Participants valued health states for themselves (Appendix V.A). EQ-5D-5L general population preferences were available from established national value sets in Germany and Spain and were used for comparison (Ludwig et al. 2018; Ramos-Goñi et al. 2018). Modelling of DCE data was based on a conditional logit framework and latent values of the patient populations were anchored using the national value sets to compare these to the general population preferences.

Comparison of adult general population and adolescent preferences for EQ-5D-Y health states

Online DCEs were used to obtain health state preferences from two samples recruited by a market research agency in three countries, Germany, Slovenia and Spain. In each country, a sample of adults of the general population valued EQ-5D-Y health states by imagining a 10-year-old child, while a sample of adolescents valued EQ-5D-Y health states for themselves (Appendix V.B). DCE data were modelled using mixed logit models and model coefficients were rescaled to a 1 (best) - 0 (worst) scale for purpose of comparison. The differences between preferences in both samples were analysed via the relative importance of health dimensions.

Value sets for EQ-5D-Y in Germany, Slovenia and Spain

Preference data for EQ-5D-Y health states obtained from adults of the general population in Germany, Slovenia and Spain by DCE (data collection see 2) were complemented with data from about 200 composite time-trade off (cTTO) interviews in each country (additional funding: EuroQol Research Foundation). This was necessary because values derived from modelling DCE data are estimated on a latent scale and these coefficients need to be rescaled to a 1 (full health) to 0 (dead) scale, e.g. by anchoring on the mean value of the pits state (i.e. worst possible health state of EQ-5D-Y, 33333) obtained through cTTO. Due to data structure, slightly different modelling approaches were used in each country.

Key findings

Comparison of patient and general population preferences for EQ-5D-5L health states

Preferences obtained from 1,700 patients (Germany: 937; Spain: 763) were compared to EQ-5D-5L general population preferences of established national value sets in Germany and Spain. In both countries, patients gave more importance to the dimensions of mobility, self-care, or usual activities and less importance to pain/discomfort and anxiety/depression than the general population. The size of differences was larger in Germany than in Spain. In Germany, preferences reported by both patient groups were more similar than in Spain (Figure 3). An approach combining patient preferences obtained by DCE and the utility scale from national values sets was developed (Ludwig et al. 2021).

Figure 3: Health state preferences of patients vs. health state preferences of the general population (Reference: Ludwig et al. 2021)

Comparison of adult general population and adolescent preferences for EQ-5D-Y health states

A sample of 3,109 adults and 2,129 adolescents (Germany: 1,030 adults and 710 adolescents; Slovenia: 1,074 adults and 717 adolescents; Spain 1,005 adults and 702 adolescents) completed the DCE survey with an acceptable quality of responses. Health state valuations showed significant differences between the two samples in all three countries. The overall relative importance of health dimensions was similar between adolescents and adults; however, adolescents usually gave more importance to mobility and self-care, and less to anxiety/depression. The rank-order of the

dimension levels between adults and adolescents differed slightly in Germany, Slovenia and Spain (Figure 4) (Rupel et al. 2021).

Figure 4: Relative importance of health dimensions and differences between adults and adolescents (Reference: Rupel et al. 2021)

Value sets for EQ-5D-Y in Germany, Slovenia and Spain

A value set for EQ-5D-Y was produced in Germany (preliminary results), Slovenia (Rupel et al. 2021) and Spain (Ramos- Goñi et al. 2021, submitted) according to the EQ-5D-Y valuation protocol (Ramos-Goñi et al. 2020). Each value set is based on preferences of a representative sample of the adult general population of each country.

Policy Implications

WP5 results are relevant for the outcome measurement in economic evaluation in the HTA and health care decision making context, as it is crucial to have appropriate and widely accepted HRQoL instruments available. Especially for QALY calculation and cost-utility analysis, instruments are needed that offer preference-based value sets. The evidence revealed by WP5 led directly to the development of new values sets for the youth-specific EQ-5D-Y. Secondly, the results impact the discussion on whose preferences should be used in the valuation of adult health states and for health states of children and adolescents.

Our results show that patient preferences differ from those of the general population and, further, adult preferences differ from adolescent preferences. We provide additional evidence that the reference group in valuation studies has an impact on the utility decrements and, thus, on economic evaluation in which value sets are applied. HTA institutions should be aware that decisions for using one value set might lead to different decisions in the context of HTA. Even with WP5 results, it remains unclear whose preferences are most appropriate. The differences of preferences between disease areas shown in our project suggest that several patient-based value sets for different disease groups would be required. Patient preferences reflect the preferences of those living with a disease. However, in the context of HTA and health care decision making, comparisons across diseases are commonly made, which are limited when using patient-based values sets. With that in mind, it could be argued that general population preferences are more appropriate as they reflect societal willingness to pay (tax-payer perspective). The question on which value sets to use will, to some extent, always involve a normative decision and will finally depend on the application context (clinical context vs. resource allocation), the health care system and the position taken by decision makers.

The preferences of diabetic and rheumatic patients in Germany and Spain show which dimensions of HRQoL are important for those patient groups. This information can be used for treatment decisions in clinical settings and for organising health care processes for those patients. The recruited patients represent population-based samples of both disease groups; thus, the data can be applied as a benchmark for comparison with further studies or sub-populations, e.g., patients undergoing specialised treatment.

Especially for youth-specific instruments, there is a lack of preference-based HRQoL measures. The work of WP5 contributed to the methodologically challenging topic of valuing youth health states and focused, also in this context, on the question of an appropriate reference population for valuing youth health states. Our results confirmed former evidence that adolescents' preferences for EQ-5D-

Y health states differ from those of adults valuing the health states of a child (Mott et al. 2021; Dalziel et al. 2020). However, we observed only small differences which varied by country. These results contribute to and inform the current discussion on the best approach to value youth health states. The information on the relative importance of HRQoL dimensions for adolescents might be relevant in the context of clinical decisions as well.

This is one of the first studies to use the recently developed EQ-5D-Y valuation protocol (Ramos-Goñi et al. 2020). The methods suggested in the protocol were shown to be feasible and experiences made in the three countries were reflected back to the EuroQoL Group to advise future EQ-5D-Y valuation studies. The three developed EQ-5D-Y value sets are some of the first value sets for this youth-specific instrument. They enable the use of EQ-5D-Y in economic evaluations of paediatric health care and treatment approaches moving forward. The advantage of EQ-5D-Y is that it is short and user-friendly. The adult measures, EQ-5D-5L and EQ-5D-3L, are well established and the most commonly used instruments worldwide (Kennedy-Martin et al. 2020). As EQ-5D-Y is comparable to these measures regarding structure and content, it has the potential for a wider use.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

We derive some recommendations that should be considered by stakeholders in the context of HTA in terms of health state valuation and application of value sets for HRQoL instruments:

- Our results show that patient preferences differ from general population preferences. For many countries, the established standard is the use of general population preferences in the HTA context, since it offers comparability of health gains across different disease groups and helps to avoid inequalities. From a health economics perspective, it is often argued that this approach is the most appropriate in terms of societal decision making (Brazier et al. 2017). However, for national contexts where patient preferences are preferred, our results suggest a feasible approach to combine patient preferences and national general population-based values sets (Ludwig et al. 2021).
- The generic youth-specific EQ-5D-Y now has value sets available in Germany, Slovenia and Spain and offers the possibility for the use EQ-D-Y as a youth-specific, preference-based measure in economic evaluations, mainly cost utility analyses of paediatric treatments in the three countries. The advantage compared to other youth-specific preference-based HRQoL instruments is that EQ-5D-Y offers comparability to the corresponding adult version EQ-5D-3L which is an established instrument for economic evaluations in many countries (Kennedy-Martin et al. 2020; Wille et al. 2010; Ravens-Sieberer et al. 2010).

- Overall, the discussion on whose preferences values sets of HRQoL instruments should be based, should not solely take place in the community of researchers. Especially for countries that base reimbursement decisions on economic evaluations, it would be important to initiate a discussion on that topic including different stakeholders, such as decision makers, representatives of the clinical perspective and HTA institutions. This applies to the question of patients vs. general population preferences as well as to the question of whether the preferences of adults or younger people should be used in the context of valuation of youth-related health states.

Future Developments

The discussion on the appropriate reference group in the context of health state valuation is ongoing and contains to some extent a normative decision. In the future, this discussion requires the involvement of different stakeholders. We suggested an approach to incorporate patient preferences in value sets, but it needs further exploration. In addition, further research is needed on the reasons why patients' preferences differ from general population preferences and why adolescents' preferences differ from adult preferences. With the progress in research, there is an increasing number of youth-specific HRQoL instrument available that provide youth-specific value sets. Inevitably, this leads to the question of how different value sets for children, adolescents and adults should be handled in economic evaluations of treatments that affect the whole life span including the transition from childhood to adulthood. It will be important to initiate research on this aspect in the future.

Methodological guidance on the analysis and interpretation of non-randomised studies to inform health economic evaluation (WP6)

Objectives

A key question in any assessment of a new health technology is: does this technology work?

Unbiased estimates of treatment effects are therefore essential components of regulatory and HTA decision-making. Traditionally, randomised controlled trials (RCTs) have been the mainstay of evidence generation for new health technologies, particularly for medicines. However, against a background of increased interest in early market access for new technologies and the promise of using big, linked “real world” data sources, non-randomised studies are likely to play an increasingly important role in regulatory and HTA decisions.

Given the inherent limitations of non-randomised studies with respect to internal validity, it is important to assess how the results obtained from non-randomised studies compare to randomised studies. There are no evidence-based recommendations on how to analyse and interpret the evidence obtained from such studies, in light of potential bias due to confounding and recent advances in analytical methods to contain risk of bias. There is, therefore, scope for improving existing guidance for HTA bodies when reviewing non-randomised evidence.

WP6 therefore had two key objectives:

1. To empirically assess whether non-randomised studies are likely to produce valid and unbiased estimates of relative effectiveness
2. To generate recommendations that help HTA agencies assess when and how non-randomised studies can inform coverage and reimbursement decisions

Methodology

Objective 1

The first objective was addressed through the largest empirical analysis of effect estimates in randomised and non-randomised studies to date. We addressed the question of whether we can trust that non-randomised studies produce unbiased estimates of treatment effects through a meta-epidemiological analysis that compared effect estimates obtained from randomised and non-randomised studies. Meta-epidemiology assesses the impact of a specific study characteristic on the

effect estimate it produces (Sterne et al. 2002) – in our case, random allocation of study participants to treatment and control groups.

We operationalised this approach through the following key steps:

1. We identified clinical topics with randomised and non-randomised studies answering the same clinical question in comparable populations (i.e., randomised and non-randomised studies that are matched on participants, intervention, comparator, outcomes). We focused on pharmacological interventions. Clinical topics were identified through existing meta-analyses including both types of studies since 2009, allowing us to capitalise on the subject matter expertise of the authors of these meta-analyses.
2. For each clinical topic, we extracted study-level information, including information on study design and other characteristics, as well as effect estimates. The latter were converted into odds ratios (OR) and coded so that an OR <1 indicates a favourable effect of the experimental intervention in the study.
3. For each clinical topic, we then compared effect estimates obtained from RCTs vs. non-randomised studies. We counted how often the two study types agreed and disagreed about the conclusions drawn for the effectiveness of a new medicine (is the new drug effective or not?) and how often they agreed and disagreed about effect sizes (how effective is the new drug?). As a summary measure, we calculated a ratio of odds ratios (ROR) for each clinical topic and then pooled the RORs across all topics to obtain an overall estimate of the discrepancy in effect estimates obtained from randomised vs. non-randomised studies.

A protocol for this meta-epidemiological study was prospectively registered on PROSPERO (CRD42018062204).

Objective 2

The second objective was addressed through two key activities. First, we undertook two pragmatic reviews. The first focused on empirical assessments of the internal validity of treatment effect estimates from non-randomised studies. The second explored best-practice recommendations for the generation of evidence on the effects of new technologies from academic literature, reports, and guidance from international HTA bodies, payers, and regulators. We did not aim to conduct an exhaustive review of all available guidance documents and scientific publications. Rather, we focused on outputs produced by, or relied upon by, key international networks and national bodies as these were likely to reflect key themes and considerations.

For the second review we drafted an initial list of key recommendations based on our literature review and revised these based on consultation with European HTA bodies and regulators. We held an online workshop in June 2020 involving 16 participants from 8 countries across Europe (the UK, Netherlands, Spain, Germany, Norway, Sweden, Austria, and Italy). Initial recommendations were shared with all participants prior to the meeting and the revised set were sent for written comment after the meeting. Written comments were incorporated to arrive at the list of considerations presented in this report.

Key Findings

We identified 346 clinical questions about the effectiveness of medicines that had at least one randomised and one non-randomised study conducted for the same population (totalling 2,747 unique studies; Figure 5). For each of the 346 questions, a median of 3 randomised and 2 non-randomised studies contributed information.

Figure 5: Flow chart of selection of clinical topics for meta-epidemiological study

Conclusions about the therapeutic benefit of novel pharmacological interventions differed for 38% of topics when focusing solely on either non-randomised or randomised studies. There was also frequent disagreement about the magnitude of effect. Figure 6 shows the agreement of effect estimates obtained from randomised (vertical axis) and non-randomised (horizontal axis) studies. For 38% of clinical questions, the effect estimate obtained from one study type was twice as large as that obtained from the other (dashed red lines in the figure). Disagreement between study types about the effect estimate was beyond chance for 16% of topics.

Figure 6: Agreement of pooled effect estimates (odds ratios, OR) obtained from randomised (RCT) and non-randomised studies (NRS) for 346 clinical topics.

These discrepancies included both over- and under-estimation of treatment effects obtained from RCTs. When pooling the discrepancies across all 346 clinical topics, the summary-level findings of the discrepancy in effect estimates obtained from one type of study versus the other are presented in Figure 7. Overall, there was no significant difference in magnitude of effect between randomised and non-randomised studies (pooled ROR across all 346 clinical topics: 0.95, with 95% confidence interval including 1). However, this masked substantial variation in the discrepancy of effect estimates. Subgroup analyses revealed that variation in discrepancies (as measured by phi-squared) was markedly reduced for topics with a mortality outcome, but not for other topic-level characteristics.

Experimental non-randomised studies, which accounted for approximately 13% of all non-randomised studies, produced on average 22% larger treatment effects compared to matched RCTs (ROR 0.78, 95% CI 0.66 to 0.93).

Figure 7: Pooled estimates of discrepancies between treatment effects obtained from randomised and non-randomised studies for the full set of 346 clinical topics, and for a set of subgroups.

These findings, in combination with previous empirical evidence and consultation with stakeholders, resulted in the development of a set of 13 evidence-based recommendations across six key topics. Recommendations were centred around the planning and design of non-randomised studies, their analysis and reporting, as well as the strengthening of HTA systems, issuing and enforcing of best practices, and supporting future research. Recommendations are described in more detail in the “Recommendations to stakeholders” section.

Policy Implications

Decision-makers assessing whether a new technology should be made available to the population, typically paid for by public funds, need to have robust evidence on whether the technology works. Our findings and recommendations provide much needed empirical evidence and guidance for regulatory and HTA bodies on the use of non-randomised studies for these decisions.

The meta-epidemiological study conducted as part of this WP showed – alongside previous studies – that decision-makers need to be aware of substantial scope for uncertainty about the effectiveness

of new health technologies, including potentially exaggerated treatment effects, when relying on non-randomised studies. Accordingly, we developed a set of evidence-based recommendations for the use of non-randomised studies to estimate treatment effects in HTA. The recommendations emphasise the importance of justifying the need for a non-randomised study, prospectively planning such studies and carrying them out with a clear idea about possible biases and how to address them, and transparently reporting the methods used.

The increasing use of non-randomised studies to estimate treatment effects also calls for a strengthening of HTA systems to enable better use and appraisal of such evidence.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

Table 1 presents the key recommendations for evidence developers and HTA bodies. Further details and justification for each recommendation are provided in the manuscript (Kent et al., submitted).

Table 1. Recommendations on non-randomised studies for evidence developers and HTA bodies

Audience	Domain	Recommendations
Evidence developers	Planning and design	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Justify the need for a non-randomised study and demonstrate that the research question is amenable to being answered using non-randomised data • Prospectively plan studies and engage with early scientific advice procedures
	Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Understand potential risks of bias and address using appropriate analytical strategies • Perform extensive sensitivity analyses
	Reporting	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Register study protocols before study conduct • Report data, methods, and results transparently • Describe potential biases and report the overall risk of bias • Convey and ideally quantify the uncertainty

HTA bodies	Strengthening systems	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen and standardise scientific advice procedures
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Strengthen conditional reimbursement processes to ensure generation of further informative evidence after initial reimbursement decisions
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Invest in and develop staff skills in the design, analysis, and interpretation of non-randomised studies
	Guidance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Issue and enforce best practice guidance
	Research/engagement	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Support future research and initiatives

Future Developments

The use of non-randomised studies to produce evidence on new health technologies is a fast-evolving field, requiring constant updating and refinement of recommendations. Future research should investigate the relative performance of different methods for the analysis of non-randomised studies, as well as the importance of data sources. This research will allow HTA bodies and other decision-makers to better define the situations where non-randomised studies can provide valuable evidence on new health technologies.

This work has also identified the need for HTA bodies to invest in the development of in-house expertise for the analysis and interpretation of non-randomised studies. Given the increasing use of non-randomised studies, there is clear scope for future research projects that allow European HTA bodies to exchange perspectives and share experiences to enable shared learnings.

Methodological tools using multi-criteria value methods for HTA decision-making (WP7)

Objectives

WP7's starting point is that the value of a health care technology spans across a multi-dimensional domain going beyond the clinical benefits and costs that are traditionally captured in economic evaluation approaches; as such, HTA decisions could be informed following a value assessment and appraisal process that includes all relevant value domains and stakeholders.

This WP first, developed an actionable model on the determinants of HTA recommendations, which is tested empirically, providing decision-makers with insights on the relative importance of different criteria beyond costs and effects at therapeutic class and country level (Task 1, D7.1); second, it used participatory processes, such as Delphi panels, decision conferences and workshops, to propose a value framework that captures the value concerns of different stakeholders that are involved in the decision-making process (Task 2, D7.2); third, it applied and tested this value framework to demonstrate its adaptability for different decision contexts focusing on a number of alternative therapies across settings; and, fourth, it contributed to the discussion on resource allocation by adopting a Multi Criteria Decision Analysis (MCDA) approach for the value assessment of medicines to inform decision-making by HTA agencies and health insurers (Tasks 3 & 4, D7.3).

Methodology

WP7 has involved different methodological instruments to meet its objectives, including statistical & econometric analysis, and quantitative decision analysis in the form of MCDA. First, a model of determinants of HTA recommendations was proposed capturing salient features of individual medicines, country characteristics, regulatory variables, therapy-related clinical and economic performance, evidence uncertainties, and social value judgements, and is tested empirically using historical evidence from eight country settings and based on a panel of 219 unique medicine-indication pairs. Second, it structured a generic MCDA model of value concerns within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, reflecting what is relevant for HTA agency decision-makers and the broader stakeholder community; in doing so, it brought together alternative participatory processes and questioning protocols to elicit value preferences. By engaging with a number of different stakeholders as part of a collaborative value modelling approach, comprised of a web-Delphi and decision conference process, it proposed the IMPACT HTA Value Framework capturing the value concerns of the different stakeholder groups. Third, it implemented the IMPACT HTA Value Framework through a collaborative value modelling approach

An expose of lessons learned and policy recommendations

in the form of case studies, for the context of different therapeutic and disease areas across countries to demonstrate its flexibility and adaptability to the requirements of individual therapies and the value concerns of decision makers across settings.

Methodological contributions relating to the development of IMPACT HTA Value Framework and model(s) have been tested in real policy-making contexts for the evaluation of medicines, in collaboration with national HTA agencies and national insurance organisations in different European settings.

In developing and testing the IMPACT HTA Value Framework, WP7 contributed to the discussion on resource allocation by using an MCDA approach to determine how value assessment of medicines can inform decision-making by HTA agencies and health insurers.

Key Findings

The statistical and econometric model

Funding recommendations are the outcome of a robust assessment by HTA agencies and are shaped by a multiplicity of criteria, most of which are linked to a new medicine's perceived value; among them, are the type of medicine under consideration and how it fits into therapeutic pathways, the clinical and economic evidence and their robustness based on scientific criteria and appropriate benchmarks, respectively, the restrictions in the new medicine's use, evidence uncertainty, considerations capturing value dimensions beyond costs and effects, and time. Consequently, the funding recommendation, F , in country i and product j , can be positive (either unrestricted or with restrictions) or negative and can be expressed as a function of a number of parameters as shown in equation (1):

$$F_{ij} = \gamma_0 + \delta_1 C_{ij} + \delta_2 D_{ij} + \delta_3 U_{ij} + \delta_4 W_{ij} + \delta_5 S_{ij} + \delta_6 Z_{ij} + v_i \quad (1)$$

Where F_{ij} , is the "HTA funding recommendation" for product i in country j ; C_{ij} is a group of parameters relating to the drug type, D_{ij} is a vector of parameters relating to the quality of evidence supporting HTA submissions, U_{ij} relates to the impact of clinical uncertainties, W_{ij} refers to the impact of economic uncertainties, while S_{ij} captures the range of social value judgments (SVJs) that may be relevant to the product or the therapeutic indication in question; Z_{ij} is a vector of country- and time-specific variables, while v_i is the error term.

Empirical analysis has found positive and statistically significant associations between funding decisions and clinical performance, economic variables and social value judgements; and negative associations between funding decisions and clinical and economic uncertainties. Whereas an overwhelming majority of drugs (87.3%) have been recommended for funding, empirical evidence suggests that most coverage recommendations are associated with significant clinical restrictions in new drug use or/and financial agreements in order to mitigate uncertainty and optimise on cost. More details on the conceptual framework, the econometric model, the variables deployed in analysis and the results of the statistical analysis are provided in Appendix VI.

The IMPACT HTA Value Framework

The empirical investigation informed the development of the IMPACT HTA Value Framework, which was dynamic, involving three distinct phases (Figure 8). In Phase 1, the HTA agency would involve its stakeholders and experts in setting a common but flexible multicriteria value frame in which a comprehensive set of value aspects would be identified as relevant for evaluations. These would be assigned a relevance level for different therapeutic contexts; the value aspects and their relevance, together with the respective evidence, data, and the MCDA procedure guidelines, would then be set for work by HTA committees. In Phase 2, committees work under the value frame set for the respective therapeutic indications and follow MCDA-specific procedures and guidelines provided by the HTA agency for the purpose of preference elicitation (e.g., using the MACBETH approach and the respective questioning protocols). In Phase 3 the HTA agency would analyse and reflect upon the evaluation results from HTA committees and on feedback from committee members, to continuously improve the value frame and tools for its use, and implementation in the future.

Figure 8: underlying development and testing cycle of the IMPACT-HTA framework by HTA agencies

Following the application of a collaborative value modelling approach with the Belgian health insurance fund, INAMI-RIZIV, earlier findings of the project on relevant value aspects for HTA stakeholders at international level were validated and supplemented with INAMI stakeholders to generate HTA agency-specific lists of generic value aspects for the evaluation of new medicines in Belgium, for two specific decision contexts: first, indication expansion relating to metastatic prostate cancer; and, second, a life threatening orphan disease (spinal muscular atrophy) (Table 2).

Table 2: The Impact-HTA Value Framework value aspects identified as part of a collaborative process with Belgian health insurance stakeholders (INAMI) in 2 separate decision contexts

IMPACT-HTA Value Framework criteria	Indication expansion w/in existing indication, for severe disease area with a number of treatments available, e.g. monoclonal antibodies expansion from post-chemo to pre-chemo in the case of metastatic prostate cancer	Life threatening orphan disease with limited number of symptomatic treatments available and new entry of very expensive advanced therapy with uncertain long-term benefits, e.g. gene therapy for spinal muscular atrophy
A - Severity of the disease	Essential	Essential
B - Unmet need of the disease	Essential	Essential
C - Medicine's impact on mortality	Essential	Essential
D - Medicine's impact on morbidity	Essential	Essential
E - Medicine's impact on health-related quality of life	Essential	Essential
F - Medicine's adverse events profile	Essential	Essential
G - Medicine's tolerability to patients	Essential	Influential
H - Medicine's ease and convenience for patients	Influential	Complementary
I - Medicine's impact on wider public health in terms of disease risk reduction in the community	Complementary	Complementary
J - Medicine's economic impact	Essential	Essential
K - Medicine's affordability	Essential	Essential
L - Medicine's efficiency	Essential	Essential
M - Risk of bias due to flaws in the design, conduct, analyses and reporting of the medicine's clinical trials	Essential	Influential
N - Impact of the medicine's adoption on the health care system's organisation and delivery of care	Complementary	Influential
O - Impact of the medicine's adoption on equity and ethical issues	Complementary	Complementary
P - Medicine's value as a bridge therapy	Influential	Complementary
Q - Medicines' impact on patient functionality	Complementary	Influential
R - Medicine's time for treatment effect	Complementary	Influential
S - Medicine's duration of treatment effect(s)	Essential	Essential
T - Medicine's duration of adverse/unwanted treatment effect(s)	Influential	Influential
U - Disease frequency (e.g. rarity)	Complementary	Essential
V - Medicine's spill-over effects	Complementary	Complementary
W - Medicine's mechanism of action	Complementary	Complementary

Colours indicate perceptions of criteria as “essential”, “influential”, or “complementary”. None of the criteria were deemed as “irrelevant” in the two disease contexts depicted.

As part of a two-step interactive process, a case study on Spinal Muscular Atrophy (SMA) initially involved a web-questionnaire to collect individual value judgments from 8 participants on the performance of three treatments relative to Best Supportive Care (BSC), on four clinical value aspects. Group majority judgements were then derived, based on which a prototype multicriteria clinical value model was built. Following the first web-questionnaire step, a virtual decision

conference took place with INAMI participants to develop a shared multicriteria model on clinical and non-clinical value aspects, enhancing the preliminary model prototype.

A comparison of treatments’ added clinical value scores (versus BSC) compared to treatments’ non-clinical value scores, is illustrated in the X-Y plot (Figure 9).

Figure 9: X-Y plot of SMA treatments’ added clinical value scores (versus BSC) compared to treatments’ non-clinical value scores for INAMI in the Belgian context

Policy Implications

Our research demonstrates a number of important findings relating to the value preferences underlying the evaluation of new medicines by HTA agencies and the prospects for developing more structured and flexible methodologies.

First, the results indicate that what matters in the evaluation of new medicines from the perspective of HTA agencies is not limited to their clinical benefits in terms of mortality and morbidity, e.g. in terms of Life Years or Quality Adjusted Life Years gained, and costs. The value of new medicines seems to represent a much more comprehensive concept, which could operationally be captured by a number of clinical and non-clinical value aspects. This concept of value becomes even more complex given that its components vary across different decision contexts: as part of different disease and therapeutic areas, what is judged to be relevant for the evaluation of new medicines

does not remain constant, even when the judgements are provided by the same members of HTA institutions (simulating HTA appraisal and payer evaluation committees). Furthermore, there are different degrees of relevance for value aspects, characterising their relative importance to the evaluation, which also vary between decision contexts. Therefore, what matters relatively more or less in the evaluation of a set of medicines for a particular disease indication, is likely to vary compared to another set of medicines targeting a different indication. These findings apply both in terms of evaluation within the same agencies or committees, but also between them. In other words, differences in terms of the relevance of value aspects in the evaluation, and their relative importance, seem to vary across different disease contexts both within and across institutions. It becomes evident, in the light of these differences, that HTA agencies would benefit from methodological tools and processes than are flexible enough to serve the individual needs of different HTA agencies or even committees, in a tailor-made way; at the same time, these tools and processes should be characterised by some common value benchmarks in order to be able to draw comparisons between different evaluations by the same agencies (for different decision contexts) and by different agencies (either for the same or different decision contexts). For that purpose, a similar enough but adequately flexible language, for the value analysis and value communication within and between agencies, would be vital: it should be characterised by technical characteristics but also by being easily adoptable by policymakers.

Second, the quantitative decision analytic methodological approach developed and tested, holistically represented by the IMPACT-HTA value framework, seems to have a number of benefits relating to the above key requirements. It is characterised by a common but flexible value frame, which can be adapted according to individual HTA agency needs, that is able to capture what matters to all relevant stakeholders as part of an engaging socio-technical approach, including experts and decision-makers, and by how much it matters, given the ability to incorporate and elicit value trade-offs. The empirical applications with the HTA partner agencies for different disease indications demonstrates that by taking into consideration any relevant non-clinical value aspects of new medicines, the results might be different compared to the evaluation based solely on clinical value aspects. The case study work also proved that evaluation results might differ due to differences in the value preferences of different groups of individuals, in that particular case representing members of evaluation committees. However, the existence of such differences should not be represented in a negative way; on the contrary, such variations would be very much expected, and as long as the differences in evaluation results can be identified and explained, any emerging variations in the decision recommendations would also be justifiable, improving the overall transparency of the evaluation and the credibility of the decisions.

Future research could focus on further empirical applications of the IMPACT-HTA value framework, in collaboration with more HTA agencies and for different decision contexts, in order to better understand its benefits and limitations. One point for further research could relate to the development of appropriately defined value benchmarks or value scales, possibly containing separate level definitions according to different therapeutic areas; these could be used to evaluate, score and compare alternative technologies making it possible to more readily adopt the results at implementation level, by linking them with pricing and coverage decisions. Additional case studies could be conducted with HTA agencies currently making use of such value score classifications, as is the case in France and Germany.

Based on the above, the impact of WP7 lies in the following domains:

- First, it has developed and validated a new methodological approach concerning the collection and analysis of evidence needed for the evaluation of new medicines in HTA, including the analysis of data and informing the design of information systems.
- Second, it has developed an actionable Value Framework on the determinants of HTA recommendations based on primary analysis of secondary micro-level data and primary data collection, which can provide valuable insights to HTA decision-makers and other stakeholders on the relative importance of different criteria beyond costs and effects at therapeutic class and country level.
- Third, it has proposed an innovative value-based assessment approach, the IMPACT HTA Value Framework, to assist with the evaluation of health technologies across multiple dimensions in a structured way. It has adopted a sociotechnical participatory process – leveraging a collaborative value modelling approach comprised of web-Delphi and decision conferences – enabling the collection of views from a large number of stakeholders located in different settings in a virtual format (while promoting consensus).
- Fourth, it has applied and tested the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework, via case studies on specific evaluation topics, combining objective data (quantitative and qualitative) with subjective judgments from committee members in a structured way, resulting in explicit evaluation ranking of therapies considering their performance on multiple value aspects and their trade-offs, not necessarily limited to clinical elements.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

Based on the outputs of WP7, both in terms of retrospective (econometric) analysis and prospective value framework development (through MCDA techniques), the following recommendations can be made:

First, what matters in the evaluation of new medicines from the perspective of HTA agencies is not limited to their clinical benefits in terms of mortality and morbidity, e.g. in terms of Life Years or Quality Adjusted Life Years gained, and costs. The value of new medicines seems to represent a much more comprehensive concept, which could operationally be captured by a number of clinical and non-clinical value aspects. Decision-makers, sponsors of technology and patients need to reflect carefully what these aspects are in each case and capture it.

Second, decision-makers need to consider that what matters relatively more or less in the evaluation of a set of medicines for a particular disease indication, is likely to vary compared to another set of medicines targeting a different indication. Consequently, a set of value aspects needs to be adapted to the circumstances in each disease and/or therapeutic area.

Third, while a flexible value framework has been produced, it is important to understand that, taking into consideration any relevant non-clinical value aspects of new medicines, the results might be different compared to the evaluation based solely on clinical value aspects. Additionally, evaluation results might differ due to differences in the value preferences of different groups of individuals, even those representing members of evaluation committees. If the existence of such differences are identified and explained, the results will be perceived as more responsive to the context and technologies under consideration.

Future Developments

In order to better understand the benefits and limitations of the IMPACT-HTA value framework, future research could explore further empirical applications, in collaboration with more HTA agencies, for different decision contexts. Additional research, related to the development of appropriately defined value benchmarks or value scales - possibly containing separate level definitions according to different therapeutic areas - could evaluate, score and compare alternative technologies and, by linking them with pricing and coverage decisions, make it possible to more readily adopt the results at implementation level. Additional case studies could be conducted with HTA agencies currently making use of such value score classifications, such as France and Germany.

Analysis of economic evaluation methods for hospital-based assessment (WP8)

Objectives

A significant challenge for HTA is the operational implementation of recommended technologies in clinical settings. Unfortunately, even in the most effective and efficient health care organisations, production and diffusion of HTA recommendations for the appropriate use of technologies do not automatically produce the positive change in clinical practice which would improve final performance.

The purpose of WP8 is thus to identify which, and to what extent, organisational/contextual factors influence the effectiveness of use of medical technologies and might cause clinical variation in their implementation, affecting hospital performance. Consistent with its overall goal, WP8 had the following specific objectives:

1. To outline improved methods for measuring performance in secondary care settings, which are central to hospital quality improvement, linking performance measurement with related organisational models
2. To identify and understand which organisational/contextual factors mostly impact on the benefit generated by health technologies and how
3. To produce a standardised method to measure the clinical variability with respect to the different organisational models in a secondary care setting based on evidence from a selection of therapeutic areas

Methodology

To achieve the ambitious and multifaceted goal of WP8, the underlying activities were addressed by the three main tasks described below, each corresponding to one of the objectives mentioned above and relying on specific research methods:

Task 1: Identifying appropriate methods and tools to measure the organisational performance in health care settings. To achieve its underlying objective, the following methodological approach was adopted (Figure 10). First, through a multidimensional approach, involving both qualitative and quantitative methods, a minimum set of indicators capturing variability in hospital performance has been identified and incorporated in a tool. Then a standard methodology to identify key

organisational variables (such as legal status, size, technology, human resources, managerial processes) able to have an impact on hospital performance was designed; this activity was informed by case studies and an extensive literature review. Lastly, a pilot study involving a network of collaborating hospitals was carried out to validate both the methodology and the tool developed (Table 3).

Figure 10. Conceptual Framework of data collection methods used to examine the association between contextual factors and hospital performance.

Table 3. List of participating hospitals

Country	Hospital name	Hospital address
Slovenia	Maribor University Medical Centre	Ljubljanska ulica 5, 2000 Maribor
Poland	The University Hospital in Krakow	Mikołaja Kopernika 36, 31-501 Kraków
Portugal	Hospital Cruz Vermelha	R. Duarte Galvão 54, 1549-008 Lisboa
Spain	Complejo Hospitalario de Poniente S. Público	Av. Almerimar, 04700 El Ejido, Almería
Spain	Sant Joan de Déu Barcelona Hopital	Passeig de Sant Joan de Déu, 2, 08950 Esplugues de Llobregat, Barcelona
Italy	Ospedali Riuniti Villa Sofia - Cervello	Viale Strasburgo, 233, 90146 Palermo PA
Italy	Careggi University Hospital	Largo Piero Palagi, 1, 50139 Firenze FI
Italy	Humanitas Research Hospital	Via Alessandro Manzoni, 56, 20089 Rozzano MI

Task 2: Analytical tools to appraise the transferability of evidence across hospitals. To design and develop a systematic approach to appraise the transferability of evidence across settings and the applicability of full HTA conducted at a European, National and Regional level, the following methodology was applied (Figure 10). First, a standard approach to assess organisational factors affecting health technologies' effectiveness and related variation in the cost of care was designed through a systematic literature review, case studies and surveys (questionnaire was included as Appendix 2 in deliverable D8.1) addressed to a representative sample of hospitals across Europe. Subsequently findings were validated through a panel of experts, which included both managerial and clinical professionals, from three hospitals belonging to the network of the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore, two of them being located in Italy and one in Denmark. These activities allowed the development of a user-friendly tool to assess the transferability of evidence produced in other jurisdictions and decision-making levels.

Task 3: Identifying analytical tools to appraise correlation and impact between clinical variability due to a non-evidence-based clinical approach and the organisational variables. This task foresaw the use of a mixed approach including the development of case studies combined with other sources such as literature reviews and/or data previously gathered on additional technologies such as the ones used for hip and knee replacement. The first proposed case study, performed in 12 hospitals' Emergency Department and Intensive Coronary Unit, concerns the diagnostic use of high sensitivity troponin and its impact on NSTEMI myocardial infarction (Non-ST elevation myocardial infarction) diagnosis and treatment. The second proposed case study was on the use of robotic surgery with Da Vinci Robot and was performed through a survey in different hospitals. The results regarding organisational aspects and adoption of health technologies were linked to tasks 1 and 2, to complete and enhance the theoretical framework. The activities performed enabled the definition of key elements and interdependencies between technologies, clinical variability and organisation models that impact the organisational efficiency of hospitals.

Key Findings

WP8 contributed to an in-depth understanding of variations in the concrete success of health technologies across different settings through an investigation of the variability in hospital performance under several dimensions, and the contribution of healthcare technologies to such performance, with a focus on variation in their adoption and use across hospitals.

Addressing issues related to quality of care is one of the major concerns of healthcare systems. It is a current topic on the agenda of policy makers at different levels and worldwide because of a growing

need to control costs and guarantee sustainability, reduce variability in healthcare delivery, ensure transparency and accountability, and improve patients' clinical outcomes and their satisfaction. However, despite the broad literature on this topic, disagreement persists on what the expressions "quality of care" and "performance" include and there is no unanimous understanding of the terms. The main findings show that quality is not exactly a synonym of performance, but rather an important component of it. This latter concept is therefore wider than the one of quality and describes the extent to which health systems are able to reach their goals in general. Monitoring healthcare providers' performance is recognised as relevant globally, especially in settings such as hospitals, given their significant weight in terms of both health and economic effects.

The case studies based on an analytical assessment of international health agencies and scientific literature obtained through a systematic literature review, allowed the definition of a common and exhaustive list of 503 indicators (provided in Annex 1 of deliverable D8.1) to measure hospital performance and the categorisation of these into the following 8 hospital performance dimensions: (1) appropriateness; (2) effectiveness; (3) accessibility; (4) safety; (5) patient-centeredness; (6) efficiency; (7) quality and outcomes of care; and (8) healthcare activities. The analyses performed allowed the design of a possible common way of measuring hospital performance, which is key at the organisational, regional/national and possibly international levels. In particular:

- At the organisational level, the way in which performance is assessed is likely to have strong and direct effects on internal organisational and managerial equilibria, as well as on the overall strategy of the hospital. Depending on the choice of 'key' performance dimensions, some units or directorates are likely to be identified as performing more or less well. This, in turn, can affect internal equilibria due to, for example, prestige and allocation of resources.
- At the regional/national level, this sort of assessment may have crucial effects on the access to resources, not only in terms of monetary remunerations (due to patients' choice of being assisted in a certain hospital or to the decision of regions on the volume of clinical activities they will finance within that hospital, as is the case in some healthcare systems), but also in terms of their appeal to professionals and manufacturers of health technologies.
- At the international level, a common ground to assess performance would allow an indirect assessment of different healthcare systems. These are highly differentiated across countries and benchmarking efforts are frequently hindered by the lack of comparable data.
- The above findings clearly demonstrate that hospital performance is a multi-faceted concept and must be measured accordingly. This implies that multiple hospital contextual factors impact overall hospital performance and change the ways in which health technologies may affect it (Table 4).

Table 4. Main contextual domains and sub-topics

<p>Hospital infrastructure and architecture</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • University/ non-university hospital • Architectural type of hospital • Organizational chart of hospital (e.g. Vertical vs Horizontal) • Patient pooling approach(es) in order to group patients within ward units • Number of staffed beds in the hospital • Current number of employees in the hospital • Yearly number of discharges performed at hospital • Number of ambulatory consultations at hospital per year • Roles of hospital in the uptake territory (Hub/Spoke) • Clinical pathways and itineraries for patients' categories (e.g. emergency pathway or mother and child pathway) • ICT tools regularly used within the hospital • Level at which electronic health records are fully integrated and coordinated • Health Technology Assessment activities or initiatives within the hospital • Presence of a dedicated Hospital Based-HTA unit in hospital
<p>Hospital's availability of financial resources</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Which responsibility centres hold an annual budget (e.g. Departments, clinical wards, horizontal clinical pathways) • The assignment process of a budget to the various clinical settings (e.g. defined by top management, negotiation with clinical settings) • How the annual budget of the clinical setting is broken down • Use of a Balanced Scorecard or similar method to evaluate key performance areas and indicators
<p>Leadership styles</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Top-down vs. bottom-up approach • Rigid vs. shared decision-making processes
<p>Human resource management tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Job evaluation activities • People evaluation activities • Performance evaluation activities • Activities aimed at evaluating human resources' potential

These overall findings have been highlighted in two toolkits (provided in Annexes 3 and 4 of Deliverable D8.1): the first aims to assess the overall hospital performance and provides a standard methodology to identify key organisational variables responsible for hospital performance, whereas the second one aims to provide a methodology to assess the contribution of contextual factors in the full implementation of a technology, with the ultimate goal of supporting the assessment of the

transferability of evidence produced in other jurisdictions and decision-making levels to inform decision-making.

Further analyses investigated clinical variability and its relation to organisational models, through two structured case studies¹ and an extensive literature review. Indeed, even though structured guidance on how health technologies should be introduced, used and disseminated exists and is distributed in hospitals, the operational uptake and implementation of evidence-based practice is often insufficient to change clinical behaviour and reduce clinical variability. This may happen because hospitals are complex organisational systems and the performance of health professionals and the way they utilise health technologies are largely dependent on the local-organisational contexts of the hospital in which they practice.

Although classical HTA and other evaluation models assay a wide spectrum of domains when analysing the effects of technologies (among which are organisational aspects), the inverse relationship, i.e., how organisational/contextual factors may affect the implementation and use of the health technology, is surprisingly unexplored. For instance, the evidence emerging from the case studies only partially matches the main contextual domains that affect the overall hospital performance. The impression is that the contextual factors detected in the case studies belong to the most accessible types of information available. In other words, many of the dimensions may not be concretely analysable because of a reluctance by hospitals to share this information. Domains such as leadership style or role ambiguity may constitute confidential information. If this is so, this could mean that, although all the domains may affect technology implementation, it is necessary to design future research in new ways, to overcome the problem of capturing such information. In turn, policymakers and governmental institutions should incentivise more transparency in sharing information on other managerial aspects of hospitals.

Additional findings, arising from an analytical model developed under WP8 and aimed at assessing the clinical variation due to the use of health technologies (in this case medical devices), clearly show that the use of technologies that were previously inefficient is still possible when the organisation supports a more efficient use of health resources (i.e., professionals, duration of the surgical operation, use of other medical equipment). In particular, the model has been tested by using data that rely on hip and knee replacement procedures in three health organisations of

¹ see section *Methods for more details*.

Region Marche, where different types of prosthesis and single prosthesis components are used (Figure 11).

The additional findings concerning clinical variability and its relationship with organisational models, which completed the framework developed by WP8, were included in a third toolkit (provided in deliverable D8.2).

Figure 11. Example of two outputs of the model: estimated probabilistic frontiers for Metal on Metal (MoM) and Metal on Polyethylene (MoP) prosthesis in the hip replacement procedure

Policy Implications

HTA activities should be carried out in consideration of hospitals' particular features. These are a key element in driving the contribution of health technologies. In this view, the provision of a solid guidance to hospital decision makers when introducing costly technologies within their hospitals will allow then integration of standard procedures, based on general health assessment, with procedures that take into account all the contextual factors that may interfere with the evidence and recommendations of the HTA reports.

More broadly, the toolkits developed by WP8 represent a methodology aimed at supporting, advising, informing, and recommending strategic decisions in the field of medical devices. They

increase the set of information available about the way in which they are used during the overall clinical pathway, which also involves the utilisation of organisational assets and resources.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

Hospital performance is not homogeneous across organisational settings but is dependent largely on local contexts. Although managerial tools, such as the Balanced Scorecard, are already available to appraise both clinical and non-clinical outcomes systematically, there is little evidence on the role of organisational variables and the extent to which they contribute to overall hospital performance. Specifically, the legal status, the local characteristics of the hospital, the professional skills involved, the availability of facilities, the managerial processes and IT architectures may all contribute to the variability in the way organisations succeed based on their mandate.

The case of health technologies as a contextual factor being increasingly crucial in defining health outcomes is exemplar in this context. The heterogeneity in the use of health technologies can affect the final patient benefit in different ways. High levels of effectiveness and appropriateness in the use of technologies can increase patient benefit, while misuse may decrease health outcomes.

The benefit generated by technologies in terms of effectiveness, cost, and cost-effectiveness may largely be affected by organisational arrangements. These eventually contribute to generating the variability in terms of use and diffusion of innovations and quality of care, especially in those cases where evidence supporting the adoption of a technology is not compelling, or where an evidence-based clinical guideline approach is not adopted by professionals as a reference standard.

Future Developments

The ambition of WP8 is to provide instruments to appraise the variability across settings in terms of performance of technologies in different contexts related to organisational factors and on how to take this variability into account when adapting evidence produced elsewhere to a specific local context with the ultimate goal of reducing the duplication of assessment efforts using evidence efficiently and effectively.

To further strengthen and refine the toolkits developed by WP8 and to allow their routine use by decision-makers, these should be tested in a network of European collaborating hospitals on Hospital-Based HTA (HB HTA). Indeed, through continuous involvement and engagement of the subjects in case study work, any barriers to ongoing acceptance or implementation will be reduced

or eliminated. In addition, the toolkits could support the provision of EU countries with new indications for hospital accreditation systems (based also on which organisations gain “real” value from specific health technology) and the promotion of better practice for health technology procurement (rooted on HB-HTA).

Expanding economic analysis for HTA: methods for measuring fiscal impact of new healthcare interventions (WP9)

Objectives

The overarching objective of this WP was to define a consistent methodology to capture the broader economic impact for individuals, businesses, and society of the introduction of healthcare interventions within healthcare systems.

This WP is introducing and developing a ‘proof of concept’ of fiscal impact intended as an innovative formulation for the economic evaluation of healthcare interventions that focus on productivity gains, consumption increases and potential tax revenues deriving from the health gains of new healthcare interventions. Operationally, the objectives of WP9 are fourfold:

1. To implement a data collection protocol incorporating productivity gains, consumption increases, and increased tax revenue estimations related to the implementation of new healthcare interventions
2. To create a decision framework (and capture it in an algorithm and simple software application) in order to incorporate productivity gains and potential tax revenues in economic evaluations
3. To test the data collection protocol and the decision framework on a number of healthcare interventions in the field of public health (e.g., telemedicine and homecare, among others)
4. To support decision-making for pricing and reimbursement of new technologies (drugs, vaccines, and other health technologies) by providing an integrated view of the economic and social impact of new healthcare interventions

The investigation of the fiscal impact of health technologies implies the adoption of a ‘government perspective’ cyclical approach. We define the fiscal impact as the decrease in tax revenue resulting from the reduction in individual income due to a specific condition / disease. Tax revenues are typically derived from individual income, which is correlated with productivity. Productivity in turn strongly depends on people's health. Therefore, the sustainability of national health services may depend on their ability to ensure high levels of productivity through maintaining or improving health. This is particularly relevant for technologies with a strong impact on labour force participation, medical disability, early mortality, or retirement decisions.

Methodology

A range of qualitative, quantitative and action-oriented research methods were used by the research team. Questionnaires and templates were built by HTA experts in Italy to compare case studies. The surveys have been disseminated through patient associations of the conditions under study. In particular, the surveys aimed to investigate the working status and loss of productivity of patients and caregivers resulting from the condition.

Literature searches explored assessment methods associated with fiscal impact and an analytical framework was developed (Figure 12) and published (Ruggeri et al, 2020). One of the most used methods to estimate productivity losses is the human capital approach. The human capital approach can be used to extend the societal perspective beyond the effect of the productivity losses on individuals, social health insurance or employers. The fiscal impact estimate is defined as the decrease of income tax revenues caused by lower pay following illness. The sustainability of national health services depends on their capacity to ensure high levels of productivity through maintenance or improvement in health.

This process can be simplified to the following cause-effect formalisation:

$$+ H \xrightarrow{\text{yields}} + y \xrightarrow{\text{yields}} + W \xrightarrow{\text{yields}} + T \xrightarrow{\text{yields}} + G$$

where: H = number of healthy individuals; Y = employers’ productivity (i.e., number of final outputs produced); W = employee income; T = total fiscal revenues; and G = public expenditure for health.

Figure 12. Fiscal Impact Model (Ruggeri M, Di Brino E, Cicchetti A, 2020)

The accumulation of human capital and the increase in population health are the key-drivers for economic growth and the result of an endogenous process. Hence, governments should invest in new medical technologies to increase population health and enhance productivity growth. Increases in productivity would increase income and, therefore, consumption and tax revenue that could be used to increase investment in health.

To estimate the fiscal impact (algorithm) of medical technologies in Italy, two therapeutic areas were selected: type 2 diabetes (T2D), and ostomy and incontinence care.

Two assumptions were made:

- implementing a specific home telehealth programme for T2D patients assuming an increase in treatment adherence and a reduction in hospitalisations by 18%.
- implementing an increase of 5% in the home distribution for patients with ostomy and incontinence care assuming a reduction in productivity loss.

Key Findings

Type 2 Diabetes

To estimate the fiscal impact of T2D, a questionnaire was developed to investigate the current scenario of T2D in Italy. The questionnaire involved a representative sample of the population with T2D and had 132 total respondents. The analysis focused on the population of working age.

Our model estimated that, based on 3 million people with T2D per year, the current fiscal impact and social costs associated were EUR 205 million and EUR 2.99 billion, respectively.

The implementation of a specific home telehealth programme, able to increase the treatment adherence in the target population and to reduce hospitalization by 18%, can reduce the number of affected people by 500,000, decrease the productivity loss by EUR 172 million and increase tax revenues by nearly EUR 1.6 million in the first year (Table 5).

Table 5. Baseline scenario results for T2D care in Italy

MEAN AGE	NUMBER OF PATIENT	FISCAL IMPACT	SOCIAL COSTS	TOTAL (FISCAL IMPACT + SOCIAL COSTS)	INCREASE IN TAX REVENUE (CUMULATIVE)	DECREASE IN PRODUCTIVITY LOSS (CUMULATIVE)
53	3,059,608	€ 205,764,143.31	€ 2,996,295,842.97	€ 3,202,059,986.28		
54	2,508,879	€ 204,163,926.05	€ 2,823,784,918.69	€ 3,027,948,844.73	€ 1,600,217.26	€ 172,510,924.29
55	2,057,281	€ 167,414,419.36	€ 2,315,503,633.32	€ 2,482,918,052.68	€ 38,349,723.95	€ 680,792,209.65
56	1,686,970	€ 137,279,823.87	€ 1,898,712,979.33	€ 2,035,992,803.20	€ 68,484,319.43	€ 1,097,582,863.65
57	1,383,316	€ 112,569,455.58	€ 1,556,944,643.05	€ 1,669,514,098.62	€ 93,194,687.73	€ 1,439,351,199.93
58	1,134,319	€ 92,306,953.57	€ 1,276,694,607.30	€ 1,369,001,560.87	€ 113,457,189.73	€ 1,719,601,235.67
59	930,141	€ 75,691,701.93	€ 1,046,889,577.98	€ 1,122,581,279.91	€ 130,072,441.38	€ 1,949,406,264.99
60	762,716	€ 62,067,195.58	€ 858,449,453.95	€ 920,516,649.53	€ 143,696,947.72	€ 2,137,846,389.02
61	625,427	€ 50,895,100.38	€ 703,928,552.24	€ 754,823,652.61	€ 154,869,042.93	€ 2,292,367,290.74
62	512,850	€ 41,733,982.31	€ 577,221,412.83	€ 618,955,395.14	€ 164,030,161.00	€ 2,419,074,430.14
63	420,537	€ 34,221,865.49	€ 473,321,558.52	€ 507,543,424.02	€ 171,542,277.81	€ 2,522,974,284.45
64	344,840	€ 28,061,929.71	€ 388,123,677.99	€ 416,185,607.69	€ 177,702,213.60	€ 2,608,172,164.98
65	282,769	€ 23,010,782.36	€ 318,261,415.95	€ 341,272,198.31	€ 182,753,360.95	€ 2,678,034,427.02

A multi-way bootstrap analysis was conducted to investigate the variability and the generalisability of the results. One-thousand iterations were performed, where all the covariates of the model were subject to a resampling procedure assuming a normal distribution.

One-way bootstraps were performed to observe the elasticity of the fiscal impact estimation according to the variation in age and number of episodes. In all bootstrap simulations (10th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th percentiles), the analysis demonstrated no substantial differences in terms of fiscal impact, considering different percentiles (Table 6).

Table 6. Bootstrap analyses for T2D in Italy

MEAN AGE	FISCAL IMPACT (BASE CASE)	10TH percentile	25TH percentile	50TH percentile	75TH percentile	90TH percentile
53	€ 205,764,143.31	€ 153,024,671.31	€ 178,006,982.18	€ 205,764,143.31	€ 233,521,304.43	€ 258,503,615.30
54	€ 204,163,926.05	€ 151,834,606.24	€ 176,622,630.95	€ 204,163,926.05	€ 231,705,221.14	€ 256,493,245.86
55	€ 167,414,419.36	€ 124,504,377.11	€ 144,830,557.38	€ 167,414,419.36	€ 189,998,281.34	€ 210,324,461.60
56	€ 137,279,823.87	€ 102,093,589.23	€ 118,761,057.05	€ 137,279,823.87	€ 155,798,590.70	€ 172,466,058.52
57	€ 112,569,455.58	€ 83,716,743.17	€ 97,384,066.78	€ 112,569,455.58	€ 127,754,844.37	€ 141,422,167.98
58	€ 92,306,953.57	€ 68,647,729.40	€ 79,854,934.76	€ 92,306,953.57	€ 104,758,972.38	€ 115,966,177.75
59	€ 75,691,701.93	€ 56,291,138.11	€ 65,481,046.50	€ 75,691,701.93	€ 85,902,357.36	€ 95,092,265.75
60	€ 62,067,195.58	€ 46,158,733.25	€ 53,694,458.13	€ 62,067,195.58	€ 70,439,933.03	€ 77,975,657.92
61	€ 50,895,100.38	€ 37,850,161.26	€ 44,029,455.67	€ 50,895,100.38	€ 57,760,745.09	€ 63,940,039.49
62	€ 41,733,982.31	€ 31,037,132.24	€ 36,104,153.65	€ 41,733,982.31	€ 47,363,810.97	€ 52,430,832.38
63	€ 34,221,865.49	€ 25,450,448.43	€ 29,605,405.99	€ 34,221,865.49	€ 38,838,325.00	€ 42,993,282.55
64	€ 28,061,929.71	€ 20,869,367.72	€ 24,276,432.91	€ 28,061,929.71	€ 31,847,426.50	€ 35,254,491.69
65	€ 23,010,782.36	€ 17,112,881.53	€ 19,906,674.99	€ 23,010,782.36	€ 26,114,889.73	€ 28,908,683.19

Ostomy and continence care

To estimate the fiscal impact of ostomy and incontinence care in Italy, a questionnaire was developed to investigate the current scenario of the disease. The questionnaire had 752 total respondents with an average age of 51, of which 67% were males.

Our model estimated that, based on 100,000 people with ostomy and incontinence care per year, the current fiscal impact and social costs associated with the disease were EUR 39 million and EUR 423 million, respectively.

Assuming an increase of home distribution for ostomy and incontinence devices in the Italian clinical setting, we estimated a decrease in productivity losses due to the reduced time required for collecting the devices needed for their condition. The implementation of the service provision under analysis has been associated with an increase in the number of people switching to the home

distribution framework equal to 5,000 yearly and to a decrease in productivity losses by EUR 21 million. This trend generated an increase in tax revenues by nearly EUR 1.9 million in the first year (Table 7).

Table 7. Baseline scenario results for Ostomy and continence care In Italy

MEAN AGE	NUMBER OF PATIENT	FISCAL IMPACT	SOCIAL COSTS	TOTAL (FISCAL IMPACT + SOCIAL COSTS)	INCREASE IN TAX REVENUE (CUMULATIVE)	DECREASE IN PRODUCTIVITY LOSS (CUMULATIVE)
50	101,235	€ 38,937,879.79	€ 422,862,381.92	€ 461,800,261.71		
51	96,174	€ 36,990,985.80	€ 401,719,262.82	€ 438,710,248.63	€ 1,946,893.99	€ 21,143,119.10
52	91,365	€ 35,141,436.51	€ 381,633,299.68	€ 416,774,736.19	€ 3,796,443.28	€ 41,229,082.24
53	86,797	€ 33,384,364.69	€ 362,551,634.70	€ 395,935,999.38	€ 5,553,515.11	€ 60,310,747.22
54	82,457	€ 31,715,146.45	€ 344,424,052.96	€ 376,139,199.42	€ 7,222,733.34	€ 78,438,328.96
55	78,334	€ 30,129,389.13	€ 327,202,850.32	€ 357,332,239.44	€ 8,808,490.66	€ 95,659,531.60
56	74,417	€ 28,622,919.67	€ 310,842,707.80	€ 339,465,627.47	€ 10,314,960.12	€ 112,019,674.12
57	70,696	€ 27,191,773.69	€ 295,300,572.41	€ 322,492,346.10	€ 11,746,106.10	€ 127,561,809.51
58	67,162	€ 25,832,185.00	€ 280,535,543.79	€ 306,367,728.79	€ 13,105,694.79	€ 142,326,838.13
59	63,804	€ 24,540,575.75	€ 266,508,766.60	€ 291,049,342.35	€ 14,397,304.04	€ 156,353,615.32
60	60,613	€ 23,313,546.97	€ 253,183,328.27	€ 276,496,875.24	€ 15,624,332.82	€ 169,679,053.65
61	57,583	€ 22,147,869.62	€ 240,524,161.86	€ 262,672,031.47	€ 16,790,010.17	€ 182,338,220.06
62	54,704	€ 21,040,476.14	€ 228,497,953.76	€ 249,538,429.90	€ 17,897,403.65	€ 194,364,428.16
63	51,968	€ 19,988,452.33	€ 217,073,056.08	€ 237,061,508.41	€ 18,949,427.46	€ 205,789,325.84
64	49,370	€ 18,989,029.71	€ 206,219,403.27	€ 225,208,432.99	€ 19,948,850.08	€ 216,642,978.65
65	46,902	€ 18,039,578.23	€ 195,908,433.11	€ 213,948,011.34	€ 20,898,301.56	€ 226,953,948.81

In all bootstrap simulations (10th, 25th, 50th, 75th and 90th percentiles), the analysis demonstrated no substantial differences in terms of fiscal impact, considering different percentiles (Table 8).

Table 8. Bootstrap analysis for Ostomy and continence care

MEAN AGE	FISCAL IMPACT (BASE CASE)	10TH percentile	25TH percentile	50TH percentile	75TH percentile	90TH percentile
50	€ 38,937,879.79	€ 28,957,699.63	€ 33,685,239.63	€ 38,937,879.79	€ 44,190,519.95	€ 48,918,059.95
51	€ 36,990,985.80	€ 27,509,814.65	€ 32,000,977.65	€ 36,990,985.80	€ 41,980,993.96	€ 46,472,156.95
52	€ 35,141,436.51	€ 26,134,323.92	€ 30,400,928.76	€ 35,141,436.51	€ 39,881,944.26	€ 44,148,549.11
53	€ 33,384,364.69	€ 24,827,607.72	€ 28,880,882.33	€ 33,384,364.69	€ 37,887,847.05	€ 41,941,121.65
54	€ 31,715,146.45	€ 23,586,227.33	€ 27,436,838.21	€ 31,715,146.45	€ 35,993,454.69	€ 39,844,065.57
55	€ 30,129,389.13	€ 22,406,915.97	€ 26,064,996.30	€ 30,129,389.13	€ 34,193,781.96	€ 37,851,862.29
56	€ 28,622,919.67	€ 21,286,570.17	€ 24,761,746.48	€ 28,622,919.67	€ 32,484,092.86	€ 35,959,269.18
57	€ 27,191,773.69	€ 20,222,241.66	€ 23,523,659.16	€ 27,191,773.69	€ 30,859,888.22	€ 34,161,305.72
58	€ 25,832,185.00	€ 19,211,129.58	€ 22,347,476.20	€ 25,832,185.00	€ 29,316,893.81	€ 32,453,240.43
59	€ 24,540,575.75	€ 18,250,573.10	€ 21,230,102.39	€ 24,540,575.75	€ 27,851,049.12	€ 30,830,578.41
60	€ 23,313,546.97	€ 17,338,044.44	€ 20,168,597.27	€ 23,313,546.97	€ 26,458,496.66	€ 29,289,049.49
61	€ 22,147,869.62	€ 16,471,142.22	€ 19,160,167.41	€ 22,147,869.62	€ 25,135,571.83	€ 27,824,597.01
62	€ 21,040,476.14	€ 15,647,585.11	€ 18,202,159.04	€ 21,040,476.14	€ 23,878,793.24	€ 26,433,367.16
63	€ 19,988,452.33	€ 14,865,205.86	€ 17,292,051.09	€ 19,988,452.33	€ 22,684,853.57	€ 25,111,698.81
64	€ 18,989,029.71	€ 14,121,945.56	€ 16,427,448.53	€ 18,989,029.71	€ 21,550,610.90	€ 23,856,113.87
65	€ 18,039,578.23	€ 13,415,848.28	€ 15,606,076.11	€ 18,039,578.23	€ 20,473,080.35	€ 22,663,308.17

Policy Implications

The resources dedicated to the health sector might become investments to the extent that they generate value for individuals, the community, and the economic system. The sustainability of

national health service depends on its capacity to ensure high levels of productivity while guaranteeing the maintenance of the improvements achieved in health outcomes.

This WP provides a consistent methodology to incorporate fiscal impact in economic evaluations, focusing on productivity gains, consumption increases and potential tax revenues derived from health gains arising from new healthcare interventions. In doing so, it supports decision making for pricing and reimbursement of new drugs, vaccines, and other health technologies by providing an integrated view of the economic and social impact of new healthcare interventions.

The preliminary results of this research were presented in national conferences organised by the Italian Ministry of Health. The results were also presented to the scientific secretariat of the Ministry of Health in the presence of other Health Institutions: the Italian Drug Agency (AIFA), the Regional Health Agency (AGENAS), and the Ministry of Economy.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

The WP provides a validated and replicable methodology, coupled with an algorithm and simple software (provided in deliverable D9.1), that can be used immediately by decision-makers in Europe and beyond. The framework is a consistent methodology to incorporate fiscal impact in economic evaluations, focusing on the productivity gains, consumption increases and potential tax revenues deriving from the health gains of new healthcare interventions. Consideration should be given to adopting this methodology in the pricing and reimbursement approach to future health technologies. The economic burden related to the loss of health in adulthood grows significantly (i.e. comorbidity), so it is necessary to allocate resources based on a shared concept of "value" and a change of perspective from "how much does it cost?" to "how much is it worth?". It is necessary to overcome the historical distrust of the NHS institutions (and others) towards the economic evaluations of health programmes and HTA diffusion.

It may be desirable to initiate a collaboration in EU countries to investigate the potential for adopting the fiscal model and to engage with institutions and stakeholders who could benefit from the potential tax revenues.

Future Development

The sharing and standardisation of the algorithm developed during the project could become an integral part of HTA, when relevant, in relation to the type of technology evaluated. Additionally, the availability of validated tools and data sources for this kind of analysis could facilitate its use as a

criterion to be considered when performing decision analysis, for instance in the context of multi-criteria decision analysis.

By means of engaging HTA agencies, other competent authorities, and stakeholders in the development of its methodology, this WP disseminated its outputs widely and can have an immediate impact on the assessment of new health care technologies.

Finally, it is recommended to extend the number of case studies to other therapeutic areas to analyse the benefits derived from the fiscal impact model and to assess the global value of health technologies, considering a wider perspective.

Guidance to support consistent HTA appraisal for orphan medicinal products (WP10)

Objectives

This work package has focused on an area where the use of economic evaluation within HTA is most complex, that is: to inform decisions about access and reimbursement of orphan medicinal products (OMPs), or more generally rare disease treatments (RDTs)². The small number of rare disease patients available for study and the limited clinical understanding of disease progression and optimal outcomes to study, mean that the clinical studies to support marketing authorisation may rely on small (uncontrolled) trials, short-term outcomes and interim analyses. This can create many uncertainties in the clinical evidence base for HTA appraisal of clinical and cost effectiveness (Annemans et al. 2017), (Nicod et al. 2019), (Nicod et al. 2020) for treatments that are often high price but in areas of substantial unmet need. Given all these issues, appraisal of OMPs within a wider setting of fair resource allocation is challenging and Member States address the challenges in different ways.

The objectives of WP10 were threefold:

1. To develop guidance on novel approaches to appraising RDTs beyond conventional economic evaluation - including tools to support the use of Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) and Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreements (OBMEA)
2. To identify how evidence and knowledge obtained from a range of sources (including economic evaluation) can be integrated into an HTA appraisal to inform robust and accountable decisions
3. To bring together existing initiatives and different stakeholder perspectives to advance the understanding on the appropriate ways forward for OMP appraisals

Objectives 2 and 3 outline the manner in which objective 1, the key deliverable of this work package, has been developed.

2 This includes medicines for rare diseases for which the company does not seek an orphan designation and interventions that may not be classified in reimbursement as medicines (such as cell therapies).

Four workstreams (WS), were originally established to explore how evidence and knowledge from different sources and stakeholders can be integrated to inform robust, accountable, deliberative decisions about the value of treatments for rare diseases.

- WS1: Documentation of existing HTA appraisal/reimbursement processes for rare disease treatments across the EU, Canada, Australia and New Zealand
- WS2: Ethnographic observation to optimise evidence and knowledge input to HTA appraisal processes for rare disease treatments at NICE, the Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC) and the Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH)
- WS3: Use of patient-reported outcome measures (PROMs) in the appraisal of rare disease treatments
- WS4: Implementation of OBMEA for rare disease treatments

During the project an additional workstream (WS5) was added as extra activities were needed to develop the appraisal framework, drawing on emerging findings from all workstreams, other sources (such as international methods and process guides) and engaging with stakeholders to obtain their feedback.

Methodology

A range of qualitative, quantitative and action-oriented research methods were used by the multidisciplinary research team including expertise in statistics, social anthropology, health services research, HTA, health psychology, health service commissioning and health economics.

Questionnaires (Nicod et al. 2020) and templates (Whittal et al. 2021) (Xoxi et al. 2021) were sent to HTA experts in Europe, Canada, Australia and New Zealand to document processes and compare case studies. Systematic literatures searches were undertaken to explore assessment methods associated with PROs and health state utility values (HSUVs) (Meregaglia et al. 2020). Multi-stakeholder and expert workshops (with HTA/Payers and patient group representatives) explored implementation of OBMEA with RDTs. Desktop research of HTA-related information was used to extract information about assessment methods for RDTs, documentation of evidence and inputs in HTA reports, and construct of OBMEAs in Italy.

Innovative ethnographic research was undertaken of meetings during the appraisal processes of three HTA bodies involving six different processes to explore in-depth the nuances of appraisal and the deliberative processes used. In close collaboration with the HTA leaders in the organisations,

challenging RDT cases were identified that were going through different processes and meetings were observed at various points in the appraisal process (Appendix VII). These committee observations were augmented by 25 interviews with 30 individuals from all stakeholder groups (Appendix VII), which helped explore the interstitial space between what happened and the perceptions of those involved.

All work was intended to influence HTA policy and practice and so there were several consultations, issued via the researchers' extensive networks and social media, conference discussions and webinars with the HTA community to gain feedback on emerging proposals, in addition to the expert meetings held in each workstream (Appendix VIII).

Key Findings

Appraisal processes

WS1 centred around the collection of information from country experts about their standard appraisal processes for medicines, and any adaptations or special features for handling RDTs. After clarifications with each expert a 'vignette' was produced and verified with the expert. These were first published on the IMPACT HTA website in winter 2019 and were updated in spring 2021.

Vignettes for 35 countries are now available [here](#), with countries like Russia and the USA added given our interactions during the project. An example is also shown in Appendix IX.

When the responses had been received from 32 countries, they were reviewed to categorise the special features and 'decision modifiers' used to appraise RDTs. Forty-one percent of the 32 countries use supplemental processes for rare disease treatments, some of which are separate while others are enshrined within the existing standard process (Figure 13).

Figure 13. Overview of supplemental processes for rare disease treatments according to their integration within standard appraisal processes

The process features within these supplemental processes were categorised and included, for example, different willingness-to-pay thresholds, different evidence submission requirements or different (appraisal) committees. Their role in allowing for more lenient scrutiny of evidence, for greater willingness to pay, for processes better adapted to rare disease specificities or for HTA exemptions were then explored (Nicod et al. 2020) and findings are summarised in Figure 14. Then we examined how these features are reflected in practice through case study analyses comparing the appraisal processes for two RDTs in countries with and without special processes (Whittal et al. 2021). Findings suggest that separate or adapted approaches for RDT appraisal may facilitate more structured, consistent decision-making and better management of RDT specificities. These learnings from WS1 laid the foundation for all other workstreams.

Figure 14. Forms of supplemental appraisal processes for RDTs

WS2 explored the gap between stated processes and principles for appraisal of RDTs and the actuality of the complex deliberative processes for some challenging RDT cases.

This work identified that the common clinical effectiveness issues arising for RDTs were:

- Studies involving small numbers, non-comparative and open label evaluations leading to potential biases
- Challenges matching external comparators and undertaking indirect treatment comparison
- Study of outcomes that do not capture the most important elements of the condition in terms of patient benefit
- Discussion about what is a clinically relevant effect and what the effect means in daily life
- Long-term effectiveness and safety
- Generalisability from the trial to implementation in clinical practice.

For cost effectiveness, the common issues related to:

- Model – construction of health states and estimation of transition probabilities
- Extrapolations for BSC and treatment – often using complex modelling
- Derivation of utilities and differential use by treatment group
- Costings – high costs for some states but low costs related to side effects.

Appraisal Framework

Based on the review of processes in 32 countries and detailed exploration of what works well and what could be improved in six observed processes, the following recommendations were developed.

A fair appraisal process for RDTs requires:

- leniency in critical assessment of evidence to recognise the inherent limitations
- flexibility in process to support the determination of value
- consistency in application of leniency and flexibility.

This leads us to recommend an appraisal process that includes a decision-making framework beyond clinical and cost effectiveness (e.g., including nature of condition, organisational issues, ethics issues – such as in the HTA Core Model[®]), along with modifiers that can deliver levels of flexibility in appraisal. This decision-making framework and modifiers then need to drive all parts of the HTA process, so that all those involved (stakeholders and appraisal committee members) can better contribute evidence and inputs. On this basis, Figure 15 presents the IMPACT HTA WP10 Appraisal Framework that will support consistent and fair appraisal of RDTs. It includes eight recommendations (four relating to critical assessment, four to appraisal), with an underpinning recommendation relating to stakeholder involvement. Each recommendation has operational guidance outlined in the first deliverable of the WP (D10.1).

Figure 15. Appraisal Framework to Support Consistent Appraisal of RDTs

Evidence Submission and Critical Assessment processes address all dimensions of value and identify uncertainties	Appraisal Deliberation considers all dimensions of value
1. The entire HTA process is shaped around clearly defined decision-making domains and any decision modifiers	5. Appraisal committees are bespoke for rare disease treatments, or general appraisal committees include several rare disease specialists
2. All relevant evidence is obtained for each domain of decision-making and all decision modifiers	6. The deliberative appraisal discussion is driven by the domains of decision-making, and use of modifiers is clearly understood
3. Critical assessment of clinical evidence explicitly considers what evidence could have been generated in the rare condition	7. Uncertainties are characterised in terms of form, extent and implications for decision-making
4. Critical assessment of economic models takes account of paucity of knowledge in rare diseases and judges whether the model is sufficient for decision-making	8. Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreements may be used to resolve decision-relevant uncertainties, if collection of sufficient data is feasible
Clinical and patient experts are involved iteratively throughout the appraisal process to explain context of condition, existing care pathway and to help resolve uncertainties related to determination of treatment value	
<i>Delivering fair appraisal of Rare Disease Treatments through consistent flexibility</i>	

PROs

A guidance document on the use of PROs and health state utility values (HSUVs) in HTA for RDTs was created. This guidance was informed by several research outputs within workstream 2 and the other workstreams, e.g. country vignettes (WS1), ethnographic research (WS2). In workstream 2, we first defined the nuances important to be aware of around use of PROs (Whittal et al. 2021) and use of HSUVs (Meregaglia et al. 2020) in rare disease treatments. A systematic review of use of mapping techniques was also conducted to gain a fuller understanding of the extent to which these are being used in rare diseases and the nuanced challenges to be aware of when appraising this type of evidence (Meregaglia et al. 2020). We then assessed how PRO evidence and HSUVs are appraised in practice (Nicod, Meragaglia et al., n.d.). These informed the development of the five recommendations shown in Table 9, which are accompanied in deliverable D10.2 with a detailed

guidance document, aiming to ensure the appropriate use of PROs and development of health state utility values in rare disease populations (Nicod, Lloyd et al., n.d.).

Table 9. Recommendations to support better use of evidence from patient-reported outcomes measures in HTA of rare disease treatments

1. When appraising rare disease treatments, it is essential to understand impacts of the condition and treatment on patients’ QoL
2. When critically assessing PRO evidence, challenges related to development and administration of PROs should be taken into account
3. During the appraisal, interpretation of PRO evidence should recognise that lack of significant effect does not necessarily imply lack of benefit on QoL
4. Other forms of evidence such as qualitative evidence and expert input should be considered to enable a fuller appreciation of the impact of a medicine on QoL
5. It is important to consider family and carer perspectives to better capture the added benefit of a medicine

OBMEA

When an appraisal process does not recommend a treatment due to uncertainties in the clinical and/or cost effectiveness evidence, an OBMEA could resolve or reduce uncertainties. OBMEA may be based on the outcomes achieved by individual patients, only paying for achievement of a certain outcome, or providing a full or partial refund if response is not achieved or stopping treatment if there is a decline in response. OBMEA may also aggregate data across patients to create population-based analyses in Coverage with Evidence Development (CED). Given the uncertainties it is known will exist with RDTs, OBMEA, particularly CED, would seem a promising solution to patient access. However, our research shows that there are many challenges in implementing CED with a heavy burden of data collection placed on clinicians, producing data that is of poor quality and not sufficient to inform re-appraisal. Hence HTA/Payers believe they should be the ‘exception and not the rule’, even for RDTs.

Identifying good practices from some health systems and with open discussions among HTA/Payers about the implementation of OBMEA, our recommendations aim to ensure a purposive approach to developing sufficient high-quality data for an OBMEA for RDTs, when it is feasible as shown in Table 10.

Table 10. Overview of OBMEA tools for RDTs

Tool	Issue and Resolution
Checklist to determine feasibility of an OBMEA [PDF]	<p><i>OBMEA should be the “exception not the norm” given the burden to the system (even in web-based platforms like those of AIFA).</i></p> <p>Clear criteria are presented that seek to ensure the OBMEA will be able collect sufficient good quality data to reduce the uncertainties in HTA.</p>
Template for an OBMEA [WORD DOC]	<p><i>The data collection elements of an OBMEA need to be separated from confidential pricing agreements into public documents. Data collection needs to be more purposeful to address decision-relevant uncertainties.</i></p> <p>A template for adaptation by HTA bodies and use by all stakeholders involved that outlines the key elements of an OBMEA to be presented in a public document. This includes</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • purpose of the OBMEA - linking to the appraisal and uncertainties to be resolved • the legislative or policy basis for the OBMEA • patient entry and approval process • data sources, data management and information governance • reviews to monitor data quality and sufficiency • re-appraisal • responsibilities of all involved.
Terms of Reference for an OBMEA Monitoring Committee [WORD DOC]	<p><i>When data are not collected in a national registry system and come from a variety of sources, careful oversight is needed to ensure the data collected in clinical practice are of high quality and that clinical centres undertake clinical assessment of patients appropriately.</i></p> <p>To ensure purposeful monitoring of the progress of the OBMEA a “Monitoring Committee” is proposed that includes all signatories and key stakeholders (such as clinicians). A Terms of Reference for this committee is presented for adaptation by HTA bodies that presents issues the committee should keep under careful review and so be able to take remedial action if any issues arise. The governance of the committee is also outlined.</p>
Patient Group Submission Form for Re-Appraisal after an OBMEA [WORD DOC]	<p><i>OBMEA data collection is often shaped by the construct of the original clinical trial and may miss other benefits or disadvantages of a treatment as perceived by patients and their carers and families.</i></p> <p>A patient group submission form is provided for adaptation by HTA bodies. This draws out experiences of patients, carers and families about what life was like before and after treatment in the OBMEA and any practical issues in the OBMEA.</p>

Policy Implications

The interdisciplinary collaboration among the WP10 members over this research has enabled us to consider in depth how a multi-stakeholder committee deliberates on evidence and uses stakeholder inputs to inform their value judgements and come to a recommendation or decision. We are not aware of other research initiatives concerning the appraisal of RDTs that have been afforded the same degree of access to undertake in-depth qualitative research of comparative, cross-jurisdictional scope. This has meant that we have been able to develop recommendations that not only build on the EUnetHTA Core Model for assessment, but address issues of appraisal that could be considered in each Member State. As the new EC regulation for HTA identifies OMPs as a priority for joint assessment it is hoped that this work can inform the operationalisation at joint EU and in Member State jurisdictions.

The country vignettes showing national appraisal systems have been updated during the project and are now widely available to the rare disease community through our partnership working with Orphanet, who link to the vignettes on their database. This provides access to all stakeholders in the rare disease community and their public availability has been welcomed by many stakeholders.

The PRO work furthers our understanding of the types of issues around generating PRO data and HSUV estimates from small, heterogeneous, and young populations, and provides recommendations on how to ensure that decision-making is based on a more complete understanding of the impact of disease and treatment on QoL. This enables more optimal use of PRO evidence and HSUV for rare diseases, which is critical considering the impact of these diseases on the QoL of patients and their carers.

The OBMEA tools will not only support implementation of OBMEA for RDTs in individual countries, but also promote transparency, alignment of requirements and collaboration across countries in terms of data collection and ultimately optimisation of patient care. This work has already fed into the international RWE4Decisions initiative, with presentation at two meetings in DG Sante.

Furthermore, strong links have been maintained throughout the research with OECD and the tools have recently been presented to that international community. Presentations have also been made to government and HTA teams and industry bodies, as well as conferences as presented earlier.

Recommendations to Stakeholders

The WP10 tools and recommendations provide guidance and tools to HTA bodies and payers, as well as important information and guidance to industry, clinicians and patients. Collaborations with Orphanet and RWE4Decisions ensure that outputs are relevant for a wide range of audiences.

Future Developments

Future developments of this work include:

- Working with HTA bodies to review/observe their practices compared with the Appraisal Framework and co-produce process improvements in HTA processes that will deliver consistent appraisal of RDTs
- Annual updating of country vignettes outlining appraisal processes for RDTs
- Comparison of HSUV estimation approaches used in NICE appraisals with those available in the literature
- Pilots implementing the OBMEA tools with feedback leading to revised versions
- Development of an HTA/Payer network to discuss OBMEA methodological issues and specific cases

From HTA results to guidance implementation: paving the way (WP11)

Objectives

Policymaking in healthcare is most often dealing with quality- and cost-increasing interventions compared to usual care. WP11 focuses on cost-saving technologies that might marginally diminish individual health outcomes; these technologies are labelled *decrementally cost-effective interventions* (d-CEIs). Such interventions still present an optimal cost-outcome combination; as is the case for their incrementally cost-effective (i-CEIs) counterparts, ‘there are no other interventions that provide a better (or identical) health outcome at a lower cost’ (HAS 2020). Yet d-CEIs’ potential remains undervalued and they have received much less attention from HTA bodies. For instance, d-CEIs are not explicitly mentioned as such in the *EUnetHTA core model for screening technologies*, established and funded by the EU, in order to contribute towards a more homogenous presentation of outputs by Member States HTA bodies. In cases of both lower costs and lower clinical effectiveness, the EUnetHTA core model suggests that further analysis is necessary before deciding on adoption. In fact, based on its incremental cost-effectiveness ratio (ICER), a d-CEI should be considered cost-effective if the society considers that the cost savings compensate for the lower effectiveness (EUnetHTA 2016). How society may consider that the cost savings compensate for the lower effectiveness is, however, not addressed in the core model. Neither is it precisely defined in NICE³ guidelines. Such is the question addressed in WP11, i.e. under which conditions will a decision-maker consider, and possibly adopt, a d-CEI. It bridges the more general issue of the relationship between individual and collective benefits. Should the collective interest override the individual interest? In order to document this societal issue, economists must work closely with other disciplines, philosophy and ethics, but also public health (health policy) and psychology. That strategy was adopted here, by bringing on board the ethics perspective and using methods from behavioural economics to study individual and collective preferences.

The rationale for studying d-CEIs is two-fold: 1) they may become more attractive as the sustainability of healthcare expenditure is gaining importance in the public debate within European health democracies; 2) these technologies offer the prospect of improving population health in

³ [NICE's guidelines manual](#) states that such interventions should be recommended if they free up sufficient resources that can be re-invested in public sector care or services to increase the welfare of the population receiving care. This has been more explicitly addressed by the recent CHTE methods review, *Decision making, Task and finish group report, September 2020, item 1.4.*

various policy-environments, such as: in resource-limited countries (e.g. prevention of vertical HIV transmission (Kent 2004)); when improving population health requires considering all available effective interventions (e.g. COVID vaccination); or when savings might be reallocated to priority health interventions (e.g. when adapting the scale and intensity of interventions to tackle inequalities, adopting a proportionate universalism approach, as suggested by Marmot (2010)). Whether to improve financial sustainability or population health, d-CEIs are seldom explicitly considered as a potential lever, and sometimes are simply equated to rationing or cost-minimisation. Structured, transparent, and evidence-based discussions of their added value is missing, and the economic, ethical, experimental and health policy analyses developed in WP11 aim at filling this gap.

WP11 sets out to explore d-CEIs, which meet strong implementation obstacles, despite being cost-effective. WP11 pursues a dual objective:

- 1) To shed light on d-CEIs implementation issues, using behavioural economics techniques: because they maximise collective gains at the expense of some individual benefits, it is essential to understand the interplay of individual and collective preferences in such situations. By designing a discrete choice experiment, WP11 contributes to a better understanding of the obstacles and levers to d-CEIs implementation
- 2) To offer recommendations on how to appropriately consider d-CEIs in allocation decisions as well as practical guidance, bringing broader ethical and policy issues to bear on those decisions. In so doing, WP11 aims to provide decision-makers with tools to identify candidate d-CEIs with the highest social value, as well as deliberative methods improving patient and societal acceptability.

Methodology

WP11 has applied two complementary, documentary and experimental, methodologies: a systematic literature review and a discrete-choice experiment. It was split into three tasks, one per method implemented and a third task synthesizing the outputs.

Task 1: A systematic review was carried out to identify d-CEIs studies published since 2005 to inform researchers and decision-makers about the level and quality of evidence on d-CEIs. The review was conducted in accordance with the five-step approach for systematic review of economic evaluations published in the 'Expert Review of Pharmacoeconomics & Outcomes Research' journal. The systematic review protocol was published on PROSPERO (Registration number: CRD42018095504)

and was reported according to the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses Protocols (PRISMA-P) guidelines.

The willingness of decision-makers to consider, and possibly adopt, a d-CEI was analysed through a scoping literature review carried out as a complementary contextual data collection for the design of the discrete choice experiment in task 2. It focused on studies exploring policymakers' stated preferences. The research was carried out on Econlit and of the 80 results produced by the search, 15 articles were retrieved to focus on stated preferences studies involving policymakers. The selected articles were used to gain a better understanding of how stated preferences methods have been previously used to elicit preferences from policymakers. This review was used as a first step to help design the experiment.

Task 2: The main method used in task 2 entails a discrete choice experiment, which is commonly used in behavioural economics. It was kept generic, with no reference to specific interventions or illnesses, in order to avoid strong anchoring effects, as recommended in the behavioural economics literature. Another distinguishing feature is the fact that respondents were asked to act as a policy officer in charge of a regional budget. This role playing was meant to minimise the hypothetical bias and the difficulty encountered by respondents in the pilot phases to acknowledge the existence of limited resources and therefore the need to make such trade-offs. The risk of incomplete or no-response was minimised by defining an 'escape' route early on in the experiment to ensure that respondents would answer a minimal set of questions even if they refused to enter the experiment itself. A specific question enabled documenting such no response cases by distinguishing whether respondents objected to the duration of the experiment, to the experimental design or to the actual focus of the study, i.e. d-CEIs. Based on findings from the ethical inquiry and the preliminary qualitative analysis, a two-step decision-making process was defined to enable distinguishing between 1) willingness to consider and 2) willingness to adopt. As a result, for each choice-set, respondents had first to select one option between two d-CEIs after which they were asked whether they would be ready to adopt the chosen d-CEI which would then replace the existing treatment (usual care). The choice-sets were constructed with three central attributes: 1) health loss (as perceived by the patient population, categorical); 2) possibility to switch back from the d-CEI to usual care (categorised in terms of delays); 3) cost-savings (expressed in a percentage of a fixed budget) (Figure 16) Regarding levels, a choice was made to adopt low levels of health losses in order to ensure respondents' participation. This is also in-keeping with the objective of selecting attributes and levels as close as possible to situations in which policymakers will be most likely to consider d-CEIs. Indeed, high health losses would not be acceptable to them, acting on behalf of society. Two

additional attributes were introduced as sensitivity attributes by asking respondents, for two choice sets, whether they would reconsider their choice of adopting the d-CEI in case disease severity or uncertainty about the cost-savings were to increase. While these two additional attributes do not have weights attached to them, compared to the three chosen attributes, this sensitivity analysis allows capturing their potential impact on changes in decision-makers’ willingness to adopt the chosen option.

Figure 16. An illustration of a choice set for the three attributes and three levels

	OPTION 1	OPTION 2
HEALTH LOSS (as perceived by the patient population)	Very small	Significant
POSSIBILITY TO SWITCH BACK FROM D-CE INTERVENTION TO USUAL CARE (expressed in time)	Hardly possible due to long delays	Possible, at anytime
COST-SAVINGS (expressed in % of a fixed 100M€ healthcare budget)	5%	15%

Which option would you choose?

Option 1
 Option 2

Would you be ready to substitute usual care by the option you selected?

Yes

No

Given a fixed budget, respondents were invited to act as a local health officer and to choose eight times among two hypothetical d-CEIs; they also answered questions, notably about their knowledge of decremental cost-effectiveness, the practice in their country, their preferences regarding reallocation of savings (to the condition that generated the savings, to other conditions, to other

services than healthcare, such as education), their perception of how the COVID-crisis might have affected their answers and how it might affect the acceptability of these interventions in the future. The design of the discrete choice experiment was innovative at two levels: 1) characteristics of the choice situations (attributes and levels of each choice set) were carefully chosen through a preliminary qualitative analysis as well as three subsequent pilot studies in order to allow participants to engage in the experiment without feeling uncomfortable about difficult decisions; 2) anticipating a possible reluctance of respondents to adopt a d-CEI in replacement of usual care, the discrete-choice experiment offered an 'escape route' allowing them to participate and to give their views without being forced to go through the choice-sets. The discrete-choice experiment finally allowed respondents to further express their views and heuristics in open-comment boxes, providing deeper insights of the decision-making process they adopted. In parallel to the standard econometric methods used to analyse the results of the discrete choice experiment, a thorough qualitative analysis of the open comments has been undertaken to provide additional material to be used for the discussion of results.

Task 3: This task brings together findings from tasks 1 and 2 which are synthesised in a political economy report (PER) and further analysed. Recommendations and guidance were provided, with a matching toolbox identifying the sequence of information and decisions in order to consider, and possibly adopt, a d-CEI. The PER analyses the probability that decision-makers will consider that the benefits of adoption (in terms of cost-savings) compensate the health losses. For policymakers, such a decision involves complex trade-offs between health losses as perceived by the patient population and the savings generated by substituting usual care by d-CEIs, even though the reallocation of the savings to other cost-effective uses will ultimately contribute to increasing the overall population's health. Should the collective interest override the individual interest? In order to document this societal issue, economists have worked closely with other disciplines to further document the interplay of individual and collective preferences. The PER offers an analysis of the main determinants of policymakers' willingness to adopt these interventions beyond cost-effectiveness, such as reversibility of the adoption decision or the level of uncertainty on the expected financial gains. Regarding the ethics of d-CEIS, the method proceeds into two complementary steps with a view to avoid pre-empting the democratic debate by the use of moral justifications: 1) an ethics inquiry offers a systematic discussion of the arguments raised against the prospect of adopting d-CEIs, in order to make the case that it can be ethically licit for decision-makers to take such interventions into consideration in healthcare; 2) it is completed by an ethics contribution to the

toolbox provided by WP11 in which decision-makers are provided with ethical reference landmarks and guidance into the possible adoption of d-CEIs in healthcare.

Key Findings

Task 1: Ninety-four decrementally cost-effective interventions (d-CEIs) were identified by performing a systematic review of clinical trials registries and published literature. Nearly a third of these were services (n=29) and another third were medicines (n=27). The papers were almost equally split between new/alternative technologies and strategies that were using the same technology but were comparing reduction or tapering drug doses or using a different method of administration of the same molecule, compared with usual care. Among the 94 d-CEIs, seven were selected for analysing HTA agencies' and medical associations' decisions and recommendations. Among the seven health technologies selected, two with high potential financial gains were selected for Budget Impact Analyses (BIA) from the French healthcare system perspective: triple conventional synthetic disease-modifying anti-rheumatic drugs (csDMARD) therapy in rheumatoid arthritis (RA) and total knee replacement (TKR) due to knee osteoarthritis (OA). The savings estimated for implementing these two d-CEIs were €51m over three years.

However, decision makers may be reluctant to accept that a small Quality Adjusted Life Years (QALY) loss in one area may generate gains in another and considering d-CEIs as an acceptable alternative is not routinely done by HTA agencies when assessing interventions for reimbursement decisions. This review focused on these priority-setting issues where evaluation results are often most difficult to implement and the results of the systematic review and the BIAs were used in task 2 and 3 as illustrations, in an attempt to quantify the types of gains that may be obtained.

Task 2: The discrete choice experiment has been fulfilled by 156 respondents (80% of total respondents) from 18 countries, but with a strong representation of French respondents. The fact that very few respondents took the 'escape route' can be viewed as an indicator of the high acceptability of the study design. In addition, respondents used the open-comments sections extensively, providing rich qualitative material for the interpretation of the results. The econometric results of the discrete choice experiment are statistically significant and robust. They are also corroborated by the qualitative analysis of the open comments.

The following main findings can be highlighted (Appendix X). Health loss and reversibility are the more important attributes, which is coherent with our hypotheses, with a clear advantage to the

former (nearly two thirds of respondents); however, savings are playing a more important role in the decision-making than anticipated. Interestingly, compared to the hypothesised decision sequence which ranked the reversibility argument as second after the health loss attribute, a larger than expected number of respondents ranked the size of costs savings as the second most important attribute, with reversibility ranked third. Participants put in balance health loss and reversibility, a hardly reversible but small loss being judged acceptable, just as would be a significant health loss but reversible at any time. Disease severity and uncertainty about the cost-savings were treated as sensitivity attributes in the discrete choice experiment; a lower health loss could be balanced with a higher disease severity (low to moderate – the discrete choice experiment intentionally excluded high severity or end-of-life care). Uncertainty about the cost-saving also tended to play a more important role in the decision-making than expected: a lower uncertainty acts as a guarantee of the appropriateness of choosing a decrementally cost-effective intervention, although higher levels of cost-savings might understandably come along with a greater level of uncertainty. When asked which additional attributes would need to be addressed when considering d-CEIs' adoption and their rank, respondents placed uncertainty about the health losses as being the most important attribute. This finding validates the approach taken in the discrete choice experiment in which uncertainty about health losses was left out as it would have dominated the other attributes. Respondents also ranked age of the population and size of population suffering the health loss as other important additional attributes to consider. On average, 71% of respondents were willing to substitute usual care by the proposed hypothetical d-CEI when both disease severity and uncertainty related to cost-savings were low, and this proportion decreased significantly to 45% and to 26% when disease severity changed to moderate, and cost-savings changed to high, respectively. These results show the importance of these two sensitivity attributes.

Task 3: The synthesis offered in the political economy report (PER) brings together results from tasks 1 and 2 and further develops the economic, ethics and health policy analyses. The first part of this report offers a thorough micro-economic analysis of d-CEIs in order to identify their distinctive characteristics and their welfare properties. It focuses on one of the most central questions, namely the symmetry between willingness to accept and willingness to pay, and addresses the controversy on the slopes of the thresholds in the N-E and S-W quadrants. The second part consists of an inquiry into the ethics of d-CEIs. It questions the validity of the justification often used by policymakers for not considering d-CEIs: their unethical nature. The third part analyses health policy in the making, by documenting HTA bodies' willingness to adopt d-CEIs whose cost-effectiveness has been

scientifically established. The fourth part of this report presents the quantitative and qualitative results of the discrete choice experiment specifically designed for this research project.

Based on the PER findings, four main policy-recommendations were offered on how to facilitate d-CEIs adoption: **1) Mainstreaming**: when deciding about implementing a new intervention, decision-makers should be encouraged to systematically mainstream d-CEIs, thereby ensuring that they are systematically considered when defining the range of alternative treatments; **2) Inclusiveness and transparency** in the deliberation that governs decisions is an important component in securing stakeholders' understanding, participation in documenting the stakes (e.g. disease experience), and possible adherence in case of adoption; **3) Exhaustivity**: All forms of d-CEIs should be considered, such as complementary non-pharmaceutical interventions or stepped care approaches, which imply that disease level should be monitored and treatment adjusted accordingly, stepping up when more intensive treatments are deemed necessary, stepping down where less intensive treatments become appropriate, stepping out when an alternative – possibly non-pharmaceutical intervention, or watchful waiting - is appropriate. **4) Social justice and ethics**: Mainstreaming d-CEIs in the HTA process should provide an incentive to explicitly discuss the underlying value-judgements, ethical and social justice principles considered in the anticipated savings reallocation.

The toolbox provides guidance for the implementation of these four policy-recommendations and comprises three tools, each covering a different stage in the decision-making process from d-CEI consideration to adoption.

1. The first component is **the actual discrete choice experiment** which can be used in many different settings, such as HTA committees or for teaching purposes, to illustrate the individual and collective stakes associated with adopting d-CEIs. Indeed, the different pilots and the workshop that were organised to discuss the discrete choice experiment (DCE) framework have shown that beyond its value in documenting decision-makers' preferences, it was also very useful in debating the interplay of individual and collective preferences. The experiment will be made readily and publicly available for further circulation and studies, for instance in candidate national settings.
2. The second component of the policy toolbox is an **ethical/political check-list** that aims to inform the appropriateness and acceptability of considering d-CEIs as part of the treatment choice set (Appendix XI). It takes the form of additional information requirements, beyond

those routinely documented when carrying out an assessment (see EUnetHTA’s core model⁴).

Questions are ordered, following each of the four main recommendations.

- The third component is a **decision-tree** (Figure 17), focusing on the three main attributes which have been found to be most influential in the discrete choice experiment, i.e. health loss, cost-savings and reversibility. This ‘decision-tree’ is meant to guide decision-makers’ choice of adoption of decremental cost-effective interventions. The navigation involves answering a set of questions which should help ensure that adoption is **appropriate and acceptable to patients and more generally to society**.

Figure 17. Decision tree

Policy Implications

D-CEIs imply both cost-savings and potential health losses, as perceived by the patient population, compared to incrementally cost-effective alternatives. Some of these interventions have been found to be highly cost-effective but are rarely adopted. The objective of these interventions is not cost containment but rather to maximise the cost-effectiveness of the interventions included in the

4 <https://eunetha.eu/hta-core-model/>

healthcare basket, which may contribute to the overall sustainability of the healthcare system (by eliminating obsolete or dominated interventions), to maximise population health (by reallocating savings to interventions bringing the most health improvements), and to accommodate special needs (by prioritising costlier alternatives on target populations according to their health or social statuses). **Hence, by providing an extensive and multidisciplinary analysis of d-CEIs, WP11 offers margins of actions to scale up interventions and to maximise population health, while ensuring core values identified for European the healthcare systems.**

Recommendations to Stakeholders

Based on these findings, recommendations are offered to encourage d-CEIs' appropriate use.

1. **Mainstreaming:** when deciding about implementing a new intervention, decision-makers shall be encouraged to systematically consider d-CEIs as ethically licit and politically acceptable alternatives to usual care. The objective is to make d-CEIs 'mainstream', thereby ensuring that they are systematically considered when defining the range of alternative treatments. Decision-makers will be encouraged to pay attention to how different healthcare systems might condition their willingness to consider the implementation of d-CEIs. By doing so, they may better prevent decisional biases and improve their ability to reach inclusive and evidence-based decisions.
2. **Inclusiveness and transparency:** For a successful implementation of d-CEIs, decision-makers should be encouraged to actively involve all stakeholders early in the decision-making process. Discussing the objectives and potential benefits of adopting a d-CEI helps focus on priority needs and inequities to redress. Transparency in the deliberation that governs decisions is an important component in securing stakeholders' understanding, participation in documenting the stakes (e.g. disease experience), and possible adherence in case of adoption.
3. **Exhaustivity:** All forms of d-CEIs should be considered, such as complementary non-pharmaceutical interventions or stepped care approaches, which imply that disease level should be monitored and treatment adjusted accordingly, stepping up when more intensive treatments are deemed necessary, stepping down where less intensive treatments become appropriate, stepping out when an alternative – possibly non-pharmaceutical intervention, or watchful waiting - is appropriate.

4. **Social justice and ethics:** Mainstreaming d-CEIs in the HTA process should provide an incentive to explicitly discuss the underlying value-judgements, ethics and social justice principles considered in the anticipated savings reallocation.

Future Developments

Multi-disciplinary research in d-CEIs is only just beginning, compared to other fields of application. WP11 has attempted to fill this gap by using behavioural economics methods to investigate decision-makers preferences and by initiating a dialogue based on the results of the discrete choice experiment. Workshops have shown the potential of the experiment to illustrate the interplay of individual and collective preferences and the potential value of d-CEIs but also their risk of being simply associated with cost-containment. **More collaborative research action is needed, jointly with HTA agencies, to further investigate the willingness of decision-makers in the European Union to consider the implementation of d-CEIs according to the specifics of their national healthcare systems and of the institutional differences in their legal systems.** By enhancing the current European representativeness of the discrete choice experiment results, by reaching out to lay persons to document population preferences to be compared with those of decision-makers, and by expanding research to mixed approaches, such as stepped care or combined use of pharmaceutical and non-pharmaceutical interventions, useful complementary evidence could be collected on the true potential of d-CEIs.

KEY ACHIEVEMENTS AND CONCLUDING REMARK

IMPACT HTA has produced methodological improvements and tangible deliverables and toolkits that are immediately actionable by health care decision-makers and HTA agencies. These key achievements are presented as take-away messages below.

- 1. Development and application of a tool to combine and use Randomised Clinical Trials (RCT) and observational/registry data in economic evaluation:** HTA staff will now be able to undertake quick, robust cost-effectiveness evaluations using local data. The Discretely Integrated Condition-Event (DICE) simulation model and all the open-source materials that support it are freely available for download at <https://dice.impact-hta.eu/>. DICE models are easily modified for local adaptation and this flexibility enables sharing models across agencies and from one appraisal to the next in a given therapeutic area.
- 2. Development of a costing methodology and a database of unit costs in health and social care.** The first European common database of health & social care unit costs in nine countries is now available. The European Healthcare and Social Cost Database (EU HCSCD) is easily accessible and can be used to feed into health-economic evaluations carried out by transferring economic evaluation analyses and models across countries. It not only saves researchers' time in searching costs, but also allows cross-country comparisons and provides an understanding of the variation in costs within and across countries. The database is publicly available on the IMPACT HTA website (<https://www.easp.es/Impact-Hta/>).
- 3. Health preferences of different sub-population groups using EQ-5D.** HTA institutions need to take into consideration the differences between patient health state preferences and the general population preferences as the choice of value set might lead to different decisions in the context of HTA. For national contexts where patient preferences are favoured, it is feasible to combine patient preferences and national general population-based value sets. Patient preferences which show the dimensions of health-related quality of life (HRQoL) that patients consider important can be used for treatment decisions in clinical settings and in organising health care processes. Value sets derived from the generic youth-specific EQ-5D-Y can be used in economic evaluations, particularly cost utility analyses, of paediatric treatments in the countries in which they were developed (Germany, Slovenia and Spain).
- 4. Methodological guidance on the analysis and interpretation of non-randomised studies to inform health economic evaluations.** The lack of randomised data continues to be a challenge in HTA because of the substantial scope for uncertainty about the effectiveness of new health

technologies, including potentially exaggerated treatment effects. IMPACT HTA has developed a set of evidence-based recommendations for the use of non-randomised studies to estimate treatment effects in HTA, including the need to justify the use for a non-randomised study, to prospectively plan such studies. Such studies should consider possible biases and how to address them and should transparently report the methods used. HTA systems need to be strengthened to allow effective appraisal of non-randomised evidence.

- 5. Methodological tools using multi-criteria value methods for HTA decision-making, including the creation of the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework.** Recognising that the relative value of a health care technology spans across a multi-dimensional domain going beyond the classical concept of “economic efficiency” as measured by incremental cost effectiveness ratios (ICERs), two distinct contributions are made in developing and testing the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework: first, a model of the parameters associated with HTA coverage recommendations has been developed and tested empirically, encompassing product- and country-specific variables, regulatory variables, critical clinical and economic evidence parameters, the role of evidence uncertainties and the importance of social value judgements. Second, informed by primary and secondary evidence, the IMPACT-HTA Value Framework captures the value concerns of decision-makers and other stakeholder groups within a common framework to evaluate new medicines within the context of HTA, reflecting on what is important for HTA agency decision-makers and the broader stakeholder community.
- 6. Analysis of economic evaluation methods for hospital-based assessment.** Implementation of HTA recommendations can be challenging and the anticipated improvement in outcome might not be achieved. Hospital performance is multi-faceted and multiple hospital contextual factors can affect the ways in which health technologies are adopted. With a focus on medical devices, two toolkits were developed: the first assesses the overall hospital performance; and the second provides a methodology to assess how contextual factors affect the full implementation of a technology. The toolkits are supported by a decision model, which identifies the technologies with the same efficacy and safety but which are more subject to clinical variation and assesses different interventions with the goal of improving the performance and efficiency of healthcare delivery.
- 7. Expanding economic analysis for HTA: Methods for measuring the fiscal impact of new healthcare interventions.** Alongside the cost of a medical intervention, the fiscal impact of productivity losses provides an additional dimension characterizing the value for money of the intervention. This approach is based on the concept that an individual contributes to society and this contribution should be considered when assessing a new technology and that

governments should invest in new medical technologies to increase the population's health and thereby enhance productivity. There is a strong recommendation that fiscal impact should not be used to inform rationing policies or perform cross-group comparisons among different socio-economic categories as it can lead to discrimination against the elderly and low-income subgroups.

- 8. Appraisal of Orphan Medicinal Products (OMPs) and associated guidance.** A new appraisal framework for OMPs, or more generally rare disease treatments (RDTs) has been created that ensures a fair, lenient, flexible and consistent appraisal, beyond clinical and cost effectiveness in an effort to overcome the associated challenges, notably the small number of patients (which can make clinical trials challenging) and the high cost of the technology. The framework is supported by recommendations and guidance for the appropriate use of Patient-Reported Outcomes (PROs) and Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreements (OBMEA) with RDTs. The Appraisal Framework can be used by individual health systems in the EU (which currently use different processes described in country vignettes <https://www.impact-hta.eu/country-vignettes>) and beyond, or for collaborative HTA initiatives and proposes ways of collaborating, such as an international repository for OBMEA plans and reports.
- 9. From HTA results to guidance implementation: behavioural considerations in the adoption of decrementally cost-effective technologies.** Decremental cost-effective interventions imply cost-savings at the price of a reduction in efficacy compared to usual care. Some of these interventions have been found to be highly effective but are much less studied compared to interventions implying both higher costs and efficacy gains. A Discrete Choice Experiment was designed to investigate under which conditions policymakers (or participants acting as such) might be willing to adopt decremental cost-effective interventions. A 'decision-tree' based on the results of the Discrete Choice Experiment is delivered together with a *Political Economy Report* that addresses the broader economic, ethical and political aspects associated with the assessment and adoption of decremental cost-effective interventions. These outputs provide policymakers with guidance on whether and under what circumstances to adopt potentially decremental cost-effective interventions.

Concluding remark

IMPACT HTA proposed and delivered both new and improved methods across ten research work packages (WPs). In terms of understanding variations in costs and health outcomes within and across countries, IMPACT HTA researched factors on the supply- and demand-side of a health system that have major effects on the costs and outcomes of health-related interventions. This included methods for more robust measures of wellbeing and quality of life, patient preferences, and experience, patient-reported outcomes (which are explored in-depth in WP5 and WP10), how stakeholder views can be better incorporated into value assessments (WP7), developing methods for cost comparability leading to better generalisability of economic evaluations as well as measuring broader economic and societal impacts such as on productivity and incorporating these in economic evaluations (WP3, WP4, WP9) and improvements in performance at hospital and system level (WP8). In the development of these methods, the perspectives of different important stakeholder groups in the health system and the broader economy were taken into account, including patients, HTA agencies, the macro-economy, hospitals and hospital networks. These perspectives were obtained through participation in research and preference elicitation (patients, hospitals, hospital networks), or derived explicitly through participation in the IMPACT HTA consortium (HTA agencies). With respect to data integration, IMPACT HTA developed new methods to integrate data on direct and indirect costs of illness (WP3, WP4) and on health outcomes from various sources, such as randomised controlled trials, observational studies and registries (WP2, WP6, WP11). New methods proposed made use of the strengths of real-world data, while addressing their limitations (WP2, WP6). The development of new tools and frameworks (WP7) will also facilitate a continuous and informative assessment of health technologies, services and systems over time.

On the submission of the original proposal in 2017, IMPACT-HTA had the ambition to deliver on each of the 10 distinct research areas it proposed. From an over-arching perspective and based on the results achieved four years later, IMPACT HTA has contributed to the creation and implementation of new methods, tools, guidance and processes in several distinct areas of economic evaluation and performance measurement, where there was urgent need for these.

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APPENDICES

Appendix I. List of DICE trainings performed with the agencies and with academic teams involved in HTA

Date	Institution	Training Topic
25-Feb-21	Association for Regenerative Medicine Foundation	DICE Model Demo
9-Mar-21	DMC (Danish Medicine Council)	DICE Training
5-May-21	CADTH	DICE Training
Q1 2021	National University of Singapore (NUS)	DICE Training
Jun-2021	DICE Model Cost Effectiveness in Health Care	LSE HE Course
20-Apr-21	University of Warwick	Introduction to DICE
22-Jan-20	U MASS Medical & ICER	DICE Model Demo
20-Feb-20	iHEA Webinar	DICE for Modelling Obesity
1-Jul-20	HTAi Annual Meeting	Making HTA Easier: DICE
28-Sep-20	14th Vaccine Congress	SARS-COV-2 Vaccine DICE
20-Oct-20	Annual Meeting SMDM	DICE COVID-19-ICU LOS
3-Dec-20	ICPE	COVID-19 DICE model
Jul-20	US National Institute of Health (NIH)	WAVE Model Demo
27-Oct-20	LSE	DES for HTA
20-Apr-20	Dutch Authorities (ZINL)	DICE Training
21-Sep-20	NUS (National University of Singapore)	Introduction to DICE
13-Oct-20	SMDM	Designing a DICE
11-Jan-19	AOTMIT, Poland	DICE Training
16-Jan-19	York University	DICE Training
6-Mar-19	URC ECO	DICE Training
9-Apr-19	Hospinnomics, Paris	DICE Training
10-Apr-19	URC Eco, Paris	DICE Training
18-Apr-19	ICER, Boston	DICE Training
25-Apr-19	NICE, London	DICE Training
3-Nov-19	ISPOR EU, Copenhagen	DICE Course
26-Feb-19	NUS (National University of Singapore)	DICE Training
19-May-19	ISPOR Intl, New Orleans	DICE Course
16-Jun-19	HTAi Annual Meeting	DICE for HTA
12-Sep-19	ISPOR Latin America	Modelos en DICE
15-Jul-19	University of Sheffield / SchARR	DICE Training
29-Oct-19	York University	DICE Training
25-Jul-18	NICE, London	DICE Training
17-Sep-18	Institute for Health Economics	DICE Training
31-Oct-18	ARM Foundation	DICE Training
9-Nov-18	NICE, London	DICE Training
21-Mar-18	Society of Clin Pharmacology & Therapeutics	DICE Demo
20-May-18	ISPOR Intl, Baltimore	DICE Course
10-Sep-18	ISPOR Asia, Tokyo	DICE Course
11-Nov-18	ISPOR EU, Barcelona	DICE Course

Appendix II. Survey for Official costing methodology of health care services used to derive unit health care costs for economic evaluation analyses

QUESTIONNAIRE INSTRUCTIONS

This questionnaire aims to obtain information about the cost accounting methods used in your country to calculate the cost of health care services on which the unit costs in economic evaluation analyses are usually based. It would also be helpful if you could indicate the source or internet address of any documentation that would provide further detail for each question. Please, find enclosed a glossary of terms used in the questionnaire at the end of this document.

Please, send the completed survey to Jaime Espín (jaime.espin.easp@juntadeandalucia.es) and Zuzana Špacírová (zuzana.spacirova.easp@juntadeandalucia.es) by May 3rd, 2019. If you have any questions, please do not hesitate to contact us via email or by telephone +34600160806.

Thank you for your timely response and participation.

Responder Information
Country:
Institution:
Name:
Email:
Position:
Department:
Telephone:

1. **Is there in your country one or several official or frequently used sources of unit costs for economic evaluation?** Please list them and provide access link if available.
2. **Are the unit costs in the former databases based on accounting costs of public or private health care institutions or on other types of monetary values?** (e.g. market, prices, tariffs, public prices, etc.)

3. Background about the health system in your country:

3.a) How is the publicly funded health care system financed in the country (e.g. general taxation, social security contributions). Is there a significant role for private insurance? Can people voluntarily opt-out of the public system?

3.b) How is the provision of publicly funded health care (hospitals, primary care, etc.) organised in the country (e.g. public providers, private providers or a mix).

3.c) How are providers in the publicly funded system reimbursed in the country (e.g. annual block grants / payment by activity)

4. General information about the scope and purpose of the official or more widely used accounting system for healthcare services in your country

4.a) How are the hospitals or healthcare providers sampled to be included in the accounting system or ad-hoc costing exercise? (e.g., all providers are included / only hospital providers / only publicly owned hospitals are included / only a sample of hospital providers)

4.b) How often is the costing exercise undertaken? (E.g. Annually? Ad-hoc?)

4.c) What is the primary purpose of the official costing exercise? (E.g. Estimating unit costs for economic evaluation? / Setting hospital tariffs or prices? / Benchmarking efficient providers?)

5. Description of how the accounting system or ad hoc costing exercise classifies the outputs of the costing exercise (the cost objects)

5.a) What system is used to categorise hospital inpatient and outpatient activity? (e.g. DRG / other)

5.b) What system is used to categorise primary care activity? (e.g. GP visits / other)

6. Description of how the accounting system or ad hoc costing exercise identifies which resource items (healthcare inputs) are directly associated with the final outputs (the cost objects)

6.a) Is the resource use for each cost object estimated in a very detailed way (micro-costing method or activity-based costing) or at a relatively aggregate way (gross-costing)?

7. Description of how the value of each resource item or overhead is estimated

7.a) Please describe how resource use items are valued (E.g. from published tariffs / from the hospital database / from standard unit costs, etc.)

7.b) Which variable and fixed overheads are included in the final cost object and how are they assigned to those cost objects

8. Reporting variation and uncertainty

8.a) What is the level of aggregation at which unit costs are available or published? (e.g., hospital level, region, national average, etc.)

8.b) Are only average (national) costs reported? Are the costs reported for each provider in the sample? Are measures of variation reported (e.g. IQR, range, SD)?

8.c) If average (national) costs are reported, how many institutions and/or observations are they based on? Is this information available in the respective databases?

8.d) How up to date are the costs published by the healthcare sector? (E.g. they refer to costs estimated during the previous financial year, or two years ago, or three years ago, etc.)

Many thanks for your collaboration!

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Terms	Definition in cost accounting	Explanation and example
Direct costs	A cost that is used by a single cost object.	An expenditure that can be traced directly to a particular cost object. E.g., a high-cost pharmaceutical that is used for treating only a particular DRG and no other.
Indirect cost (variable overheads)	The cost of a resource that is used by more than one cost object, but varies with the quantity used.	E.g. Expenses which are recorded at departmental level which are shared between several patients, such as medical staff or nursing staff
General overheads (fixed overheads)	Expenses which are incurred at organisational level, do not vary with the number of patients treated, and are shared between several departments.	E.g. amortization of buildings, staff training costs, cost of water, electricity and heating
Top-down costing	A costing method where all costs the organization incurs over a given period are allocated to cost objects.	Direct costs are identified directly to cost objects. Indirect costs are "apportioned" to cost objects. In full costing, both variable and fixed overheads will be apportioned to cost objects
Full-absorption costing	A top-down costing method. 100% of an organisations costs incurred over a given period are allocated to all the cost objects	Direct costs, variable overheads and fixed overheads are apportioned to cost objects. Sometimes required by financial reporting standards
Activity-based costing	A method of top-down micro-costing	Indirect expenditure is first allocated to tasks or activities, so that it can be apportioned to cost objects at a more detailed level of disaggregation than used in traditional top-down gross costing
Micro-costing	Costs are identified at very detailed level.	Drug costs, cost of surgeon, cost of nurse, material costs,

		amortization, capital costs, energies, etc.
Gross-costing	Costs are identified at highly aggregated level.	Inpatient costs, costs of department of traumatology, etc.
Cost object	Final product, process or service that are going to be costed.	E.g., Hospital GRDs. Normally in top-down methods, all final services performed by the organisation during the accounting period will be costed
Bottom-up	Cost components are valued by identifying resource use directly employed by each patient.	Patient-specific costs

Appendix III. European Healthcare and Social Cost Database (EU HCSCD) structure

Category	Subcategory	Item
Primary resources	Medicines	Paracetamol Atorvastatin Trastuzumab
	Medical devices	Drug-eluting stent Wearable cardioverter-defibrillator
	Health products	Glucose test strips
	Personnel	General practitioner Nurse Specialist
Composite goods and services	Outpatient visits	General practitioner visit Specialist visit Accident & Emergency visit
	Hospitalization	Day of hospitalization at "normal" ward Day of hospitalization at Intensive Care Unit
	Image diagnosis	Ultrasound Scan Computerised Tomography Scan
	Laboratory tests	Creatinin Ferritin
	Ambulance services	Non-emergency patient transport Intensive care ambulance
	Diagnostic procedures	Colonoscopy
	Therapeutic procedures	Haemodialysis Oxygen therapy
Complex processes and interventions	Inpatient medical and surgical processes	Heart failure (ICD10: I50) Hernia inguinal, femoral, umbilical (ICD10: K40, K41, K42)
	Day case procedures/ Outpatient surgery	Laparoscopic cholecystectomy Cataract extirpation

Appendix IV. WP4 Task 2 Key Findings

Appendix IV.A. Alzheimer's Disease. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Appendix IV.B. Diabetes Mellitus. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Appendix IV.C. Rare Diseases. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Appendix IV.D. Multiple Sclerosis Disease. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Appendix IV.E. Depression. Incremental Cost-Utility Ratios from the healthcare and societal perspectives

Appendix V. Snapshots of DCE Tasks

Appendix V.A. Snapshot of a DCE task as used for respondents of the patient groups and for adolescent respondents.

Which health state do you prefer?

- Some problems walking about
- Some problems washing or dressing myself
- A lot of problems doing my usual activities
- Some pain or discomfort
- A bit worried, sad or unhappy

- Some problems walking about
- A lot of problems washing or dressing myself
- No problems doing my usual activities
- No pain or discomfort
- A bit worried, sad or unhappy

Next

Appendix V.B. Snapshot of a DCE task as used for respondents of the adult general population valuing child health states.

Which health state do you prefer for a 10-year-old child?

- Some problems walking about
- Some problems washing or dressing myself
- A lot of problems doing my usual activities
- Some pain or discomfort
- A bit worried, sad or unhappy

- Some problems walking about
- A lot of problems washing or dressing myself
- No problems doing my usual activities
- No pain or discomfort
- A bit worried, sad or unhappy

[Next](#)

Appendix VI. Analysis of factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations

Appendix VI.A. Conceptual framework

The inclusion of a new medicine in the list of products covered by a health care system is characterized by two distinct phases: first, the market entry and the associated speed with which market entry occurs once regulatory and coverage decision-related requirements have been met; and, second, market penetration, notably the outcome of an assessment by a competent authority in order to assess the new medicine's value in terms of its capacity to deliver (therapeutic) benefit.

Obtaining marketing authorization (MA) from a regulatory authority is a clear pre-requisite for medicinal products to be marketed. Across health care systems, achieving coverage implies a positive outcome following an evaluation by a competent authority, including HTA agencies or reimbursement committees in which a product's benefits (and costs) are deemed acceptable based on an assessment from a health care system perspective. Conceptually, following MA, the speed of market entry, i.e. the time between receiving MA and coverage recommendation by an HTA agency is dependent on a number of criteria: the first is the extent to which a drug fulfils certain pre-conditions which may justify early market entry. Accelerated approval pathways (AAPs), such as conditional marketing authorization, in principle provide a signal to HTA agencies that drugs approved through these pathways may only require expedited appraisal or should be subject to different levels of robustness when assessed. As such, medicines approved via AAPs could receive funding recommendations faster compared with non-AAP medicines. A second criterion relates to the type of medicine, whether its development has benefited from specific incentives or it has a priority status because of its asserted "therapeutic promise"; for example, orphan designation status, suggests that lower thresholds of evidence may be accepted at licensing level and, in principle, signals to HTA agencies that orphan medicines could be considered more favourably. Similarly, the type of therapy and its purpose, notably curative, preventive or offering symptomatic relief, may carry important coverage implications. A third criterion is the type of funding modality that may be agreed upon following the completion of the assessment process. If significant uncertainties relating to clinical benefit have been identified, the possibility to conclude a risk mitigation strategy may act as a decision modifier and a product can be offered coverage or coverage may occur faster, instead of being rejected. Restrictions of use may shape the nature and extent of coverage, either on clinical (e.g. use in certain sub-populations only, where evidence on benefit is strongest), or financial grounds (e.g. a financial arrangement based on risk-sharing (RSA)), or inclusion into a special funding programme other than RSA (which can be restrictive in terms of the number of patients

A horizontal and vertical expose of lessons learned and policy recommendations

accessing the drug, such as the Cancer Drugs Fund (CDF) in England [NHSE, 2016],

or the Exceptional Access Programme (EAP) in Ontario [OMH, 2020]). Evidence shows that clinical and economic restrictions facilitate and accelerate coverage by limiting budget impact, improving cost-effectiveness, or both [Lakdawalla et al, 2018; Logviss et al, 2018; Davis et al, 2009; Lewis and Warlow, 2004].

A fourth criterion relates to the evidence supporting the HTA submission process, such as, the trial phase, the extent to which a direct comparator has been used and whether a clinical, rather than a surrogate, endpoint supported claims on clinical benefit. Concerns about trial designs, type of comparator and the magnitude of clinical benefit can delay considerably positive funding recommendations and may lead to rejections. Finally, if a submission has received a rejection already, a re-submission is more likely to be delayed in receiving a positive recommendation. The above are captured in equation (1),

$$ME_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 OD_{ij} + \beta_2 MA_{ij} + \beta_3 FM_{ij} + \beta_4 RESUB_{ij} + \beta_5 EVID_j + \beta_6 Z_{ij} + \varepsilon_i \quad (1)$$

where ME_{ij} is market entry in country i and product j , OD_{ij} is orphan designation, as a proxy for special product characteristics, MA_{ij} is the type of marketing authorization pathway the product has undergone; FM_{ij} is the funding modality, $RESUB_{ij}$ indicate whether a HTA dossier was previously rejected for product j in country i , $EVID_j$ is a vector of variables concerning the evidence that supported the HTA submission (i.e. trial phase, comparator and endpoint), Z_{ij} is a vector of country and time-specific variables and ε_i is the error term.

Market penetration, on the other hand, is contingent on the funding recommendation a new medicine will receive. The funding recommendation is the outcome of a robust assessment by HTA agencies and is shaped by a multiplicity of criteria, most of which are linked to a new medicine's perceived value; among them, are the type of medicine under consideration and how it fits into therapeutic pathways, the clinical and economic evidence and their robustness based on scientific criteria, the restrictions in the new medicine's use, evidence uncertainty, considerations capturing value dimensions beyond costs and effects, and time.

Important criteria shaping market penetration include clinical evidence and value parameters, such as clinical study type and design, which ultimately influence internal and external validity, the evidence on and the performance of the clinical benefit in terms of size, clinical meaningfulness and statistical significance and the extent to which the new drug's demonstration of clinical benefit relies on a clinical or a surrogate endpoint. Economic variables can be critical in the context of value assessment and HTA. The incremental cost effectiveness ratio (ICER), as an indicator of efficiency, underscores the additional investment required to obtain an additional unit of health gain; its acceptability on a case-by-case basis reflects national willingness-to-pay (WTP) thresholds, where they exist. Budget impact, by contrast, is an indicator of affordability. Drugs can be efficient (cost-effective) compared with the standard of care, but may not be affordable; therefore, efficiency may be a necessary but not a sufficient condition for coverage.

Uncertainties, both clinical and economic, may also have an impact on coverage

recommendations. Uncertainties capture the concerns of decision-makers on assumptions and baseline characteristics of clinical trials, trial design issues, treatment discontinuation, the economic evidence submitted (e.g. model and modelling, cost and utility data, comparator issues, relationship to current clinical practice), all of which render the results uncertain and non-generalisable and, if not addressed, have a negative effect on coverage recommendations. Crucially, addressing clinical and economic uncertainties forms an important dimension in HTA in order to achieve coverage. A further set of criteria that may influence the direction of coverage recommendations is the extent to which social value judgements (SVJs) are considered; these capture elicited (e.g. human dignity and solidarity principles in Sweden; end-of-life criteria in the UK) and non-elicited considerations (e.g. emotional and financial strain on patients and their families, treatment administration advantages) beyond a new therapy's costs and effects. SVJs may influence decision-making and factors that have been shown to have some impact, include the explicit recognition of disease severity, unmet need, and administration advantage [Annemans et al, 2017; Jadad et al, 1996; Harris et al, 2008; Dakin et al, 2015].

Consequently, the funding recommendation, F , in country i and product j , can be positive (either unrestricted or with restrictions) or negative and can be expressed as a function of a number of parameters as shown in equation (2):

$$F_{ij} = \gamma_0 + \delta_1 C_{ij} + \delta_2 D_{ij} + \delta_3 U_{ij} + \delta_4 W_{ij} + \delta_5 S_{ij} + \delta_6 Z_{ij} + v_i \quad (2)$$

Where the dependent variable, F_{ij} , is the "HTA funding recommendation" for product i in country j ; C_{ij} is a group of parameters including the drug type, D_{ij} is a vector of parameters relating to the quality of evidence supporting HTA submissions, U_{ij} relates to the impact of clinical uncertainties, W_{ij} refers to the impact of economic uncertainties, while S_{ij} captures the range of social value judgments (SVJs) that may be relevant to the product or the therapeutic indication in question; Z_{ij} is a vector of country- and time-specific variables, while v_i is the error term.

Appendix VI.B. The Model

Based on the conceptual framework our objective was to determine empirically which factors were associated with (a) time to HTA recommendations and (b) HTA coverage recommendations, respectively.

(a) Time to HTA recommendation

To assess factors influencing delay in reaching an HTA recommendation, a linear regression was considered, as shown in (3):

$$E(Y) = \alpha + \beta_1 X_1 + \beta_2 X_2 + \dots + \beta_k X_k \quad (3)$$

Where the expected value of the distribution of the response variable Y , $(E(Y))$, is assumed to be a linear combination of the explanatory variables $(X_1 \dots X_k)$.

Building on both equations (1) and (3), the following empirical model where the HTA_TIME_{ij} variable was regressed on regulatory as well as product-specific variables was deployed:

$$HTA_TIME_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 COMPARATOR_j + \beta_2 ENDPOINT_j + \beta_3 PHASEIII_j + \beta_4 ORPHAN_j + \beta_5 APPROVAL_j + \beta_6 FUDNING_{ij} + \beta_7 HTAMODEL_i + \beta_8 AGENTTYPE_i + \beta_9 GDP_i + \beta_{10} YEARHTA_i \quad (4)$$

Where i and j indicate the country and the product, respectively. Details on the response and explanatory variables can be found in Table 1.

(b) Factors associated with HTA recommendation

To determine what variables impacted on HTA coverage recommendations, we considered a range of options. Due to the ordinal nature of the variable of interest (negative, positive with restrictions and positive coverage recommendation), an ordered multinomial logistic approach was initially considered. However, as the present analysis focuses on how positive recommendations, either with or without restrictions, compare with negative ones, this approach was rejected. A panel data approach was also contemplated, but due to HTA coverage recommendations being unique rather than recurring events over time, this was deemed unfeasible. Finally, multinomial level modelling was explored to assess whether results of the analysis were robust to accounting for intra-agency correlation, but the computational complexities in running a multilevel multinomial unordered regression warranted this to be a robustness check rather than the principal analysis. Based on the above, a multinomial logistic regression was deployed, as shown on (5):

$$\log \left[\frac{P(Y=j)}{P(Y=0)} \right] = \alpha_j + \beta_{j1} X_1 + \beta_{j2} X_2 + \dots + \beta_{jk} X_k \quad (5)$$

Where $\log \left[\frac{P(Y=j)}{P(Y=0)} \right]$ represents the log of the odds of outcome j conditional on explanatory variables $X_1 \dots X_k$.

Following (2) and (5), the empirical model that was considered in our analysis is shown in (6):

$$HTA_RECOMMEND_{ij} = \alpha_0 + \beta_1 RESUBMIT_j + \beta_2 ONCOLOGY_j * \beta_3 ORPHAN_j + \beta_4 QUALITY_j + \beta_5 HTAMODEL_i + \beta_6 AGENTTYPE_i + \beta_7 GDP_i + \beta_8 YEARHTA_i + \beta_9 SEVERITY_{ij} + \beta_{10} INNOVATION_{ij} + \beta_{11} ADMINAD_{ij} + \beta_{12} UNEED_{ij} + \beta_{12} CLINBEN_{ij} + \beta_{13} GENERAL_{ij} + \beta_{14} MODELLING_j + \beta_{15} INPUT_{ij}$$

(6)

Where *i* and *j* indicate the country and the product, respectively. Details on the response and explanatory variables can be found in Table 1. The categories of the response variable *HTA_RECOMMEND_{ij}* are the achievement of positive (L), positive with restrictions (LWC) or negative (DNL) HTA recommendations. No ranking was assumed between the categorical outcomes and DNL was used as the baseline group against which L and LWC were compared. Coefficients were exponentiated to relative risk ratios (RRR) for ease of interpretation. RRR lower/higher than 1 indicate a lower/higher likelihood in observing the outcome of interest versus the base outcome (e.g. LWC vs DNL). Coefficients represent deviations from a negative recommendation and positive recommendations with and without restrictions were not be directly compared. A set of product-specific variables were initially considered in an initial, reduced form model and different permutations were run to investigate whether results were sensitive to the inclusion and exclusion of explanatory variables, namely social value judgements and clinical and economic uncertainties. All variables were then included in a final model, which represents the principal model of this analysis and is shown in (6) above.

A number of interactions were explored. Interactions were tested for those variables whose effect was expected to change depending on the level of another independent variable. For example, the interaction between the type of product (oncology drug or not) and whether a product received an orphan designation was run based on our assumption that an orphan drug for a cancer indication would be more likely to be listed, with or without restrictions.

All analyses controlled for country-specific effects to account for heterogeneities at country level by including country GDP per capita and variables indicating the model of HTA prevailing in each country (clinical and cost-effectiveness vs comparative clinical benefit assessment) and the country practice in terms of topic selection (whether the HTA agency assesses all or some of the new products approved by regulatory agencies); in order to account for product-specific heterogeneities we included oncology and orphan designation as covariates. Finally, the year of the HTA recommendation was also added as a control to account for time effects.

The models in (4) and (6) were run (a) for the full sample comprising all 8 countries and (b) a sub-sample comprising 6 countries based on the HTA model they follow (i.e. clinical and cost-effectiveness), thereby

A horizontal and vertical expose of lessons learned and policy recommendations excluding France and Germany (that follow comparative clinical benefit assessment). The latter was undertaken to investigate the effect of incremental cost effectiveness on the HTA recommendation; France and Germany were excluded in (b) because economic evaluation is either not performed as part of the HTA process (Germany) [Vreman, 2020], or plays a minor role in decision-making [CEPS, 2019]. All statistical analyses were performed in Stata Version 16 [StataCorp, 2020].

Appendix VI.C. Tables of (a) variables, (b) descriptive statistics and (c) results of the econometric analysis of “Time-to-HTA recommendations” and of “Factors associated with HTA recommendations”

As noted earlier, Table 1, summarises all variables deployed in the analysis.

Table 2 shows a series of descriptive statistics.

Table 3 summarises the results of the linear regression on “Time-to-HTA”.

Tables 4 and 5 summarise the results of the econometric modelling on the factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations for the entire sample (Table 4) and for countries that use clinical and cost effectiveness analysis only as a model of HTA (therefore excluding countries using comparative clinical benefit assessment) (Table 5).

Table 2. Variables deployed in the analysis

Variable	Type	Variable abbreviation	Definition/Explanation
Coverage decision outcome & Timelines			
Final coverage decision ¹	Categorical	HTA_RECOMMEND	1 = L (List; IQWIG /HAS: Level 1/2); 2 = LWC (List with Criteria; IQWIG/HAS: level 3/4/5); 3 = DNL (Do Not List; G-BA= Level 6; SMR=insufficient);
Time to HTA coverage decision	Continuous	HTA_TIME	Time between Marketing Authorisation and final HTA/coverage decision in months
Regulatory variables			
Regulatory approval type	Categorical	APPROVAL	1 = Standard (EMA, Health Canada, TGA) 2 = Accelerated Approval Pathway 3 = Parallel Review
Re-submission	Binary	RESUBMIT	1= Drug has had at least one prior rejection on an earlier submission; 0= no prior rejection
Drug- and diagnosis-specific parameters			
Orphan drug	Binary	ORPHAN	1= Drug has orphan status/designation; 0= no orphan status/designation
Oncology drug	Binary	ONCOLOGY	1= Drug has an oncology indication; 0= no oncology indication
Economic (funding) and clinical restrictions			
Funding restrictions	Categorical	FUNDING	0= Not applicable/not funded; 1 = Unrestricted funding; 2 = Risk sharing agreement; 3 = Special funding arrangement [non-risk-sharing] (e.g. CDF, new drug funding programme, etc)
Clinical restrictions	Categorical	-	0 = No restrictions; 1 = Population restriction; 2 = Dosing restriction; 3 = both
Clinical evidence considerations			
Type of evidence	Binary	PHASEIII	1 = Phase III RCT; 2 = All other types of clinical trial
Comparator ²	Binary	COMPARATOR	1= At least one direct comparator informing the decision; 0= No direct comparator
Primary endpoint	Binary	ENDPOINT	1 = Clinical endpoint as primary endpoint; 0 = Surrogate endpoint as primary endpoint
Quality of evidence	Categorical	QUALITY	1= High quality of evidence (no issues with study design, comparator used in study and follow up period); 2= Average quality of data (there are issues in one of the categories); 3= Poor quality of data (there are issues in more than one category).
Follow up quality of data	Binary	FOLLOWUP	1= If there are no issues explicitly expressed by the HTA body around the follow-up and the long-term data, the quality of evidence is considered 'high QoE'; 0= Otherwise the quality of evidence is considered 'low QoE'.
Economic evidence considerations			
ICER	Categorical	ICER	1= ICER submitted and publicly available; 2= confidential ICER; 3= Other analysis submitted; 4= No ICER submitted.
Clinical uncertainties			
Size of clinical benefit ³	Binary	CLINBEN	1= At least one uncertainty around the size of clinical benefit extrapolated from the evidence submitted; 0= No uncertainties.
Generalisability ⁴	Binary	GENERAL	1= At least an uncertainty related to generalisability to the country's population or local clinical practice; 0= No uncertainties.
Economic uncertainty			
Modelling ⁶	Binary	MODELLING	1= At least an uncertainty around the modelling approach; 0= No uncertainties.
Input ⁸	Binary	MODEL	1= At least an uncertainty around the inputs (cost and utilities) used by the manufacturer in the economic model presented; 0= No uncertainties.
Social value judgements			
Severity	Binary	SEVERITY	1= Severity of the disease explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Severity not recognised.
Administration route/frequency	Binary	ADMINAD	1= Route and the frequency of administration of the treatment explicitly recognised by HTA agency as offering advantage; 0 = Not recognised as offering advantage.
Unmet need	Binary	UNEEED	1= Unmet need for the new treatment (e.g. few or no alternatives exist, need for additional treatments, high BoD) explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Unmet need not recognised.
Innovation	Binary	INNOVATION	1= Novel mechanism of action and overall innovativeness of the treatment explicitly recognised by HTA agency; 0 = Not recognised.

Country-specific variables			
GDP per capita	Continuous	Ln_GDP	Log of Country GDP per capita
Model of HTA	Binary	HTAMODEL	1= Clinical and cost-effectiveness; 0 = Comparative clinical benefit assessment
Type of HTA agency	Binary	AGENTYPE	1=All products approved by regulatory agencies are assessed by the HTA agency; 0 = Not all products approved by regulatory agencies are assessed by the HTA agency
Time-specific variables			
Year of HTA approval	Continuous	YEARHTA	Year of HTA approval

Notes: ¹ France and Germany follow a different approach to the other countries in the sample that follow the incremental cost effectiveness model. As such, the classification is not explicitly the same as 'List', 'List with Criteria' and 'Do not List', but subscribes to a specific ranking order, as follows: in France, there is the improvement in the therapeutic benefit (amelioration du service medical rendu – ASMR) that includes 5 scales ranging from major (ASMR=1) to no improvement (ASMR=5); at the same time, the total clinical benefit (service medical rendu) is an indicator of whether a technology is considered beneficial, ranging between SMR=1 (important) and SMR=4 (insufficient), the latter implying an outright rejection, as a drug with SMR=4 will not be included in France's positive list. In the case of Germany, a comparable rating is followed, with the added (clinical) benefit ranging between 1 (major) – 6 (below what is currently available). Ratings between 1-4 imply that drugs enter a price negotiation the rating they receive influences the final price premium over comparator, while if a rating of 5 or 6 is given, the drug is included in the reference pricing categories. Based on the above and in order to ensure comparability across our sample countries with regards to the coverage recommendations received for the same medicine-indication pair across countries, the following was undertaken: Levels 1 and 2 in the French and the German incremental benefit rating were considered as 'List', while Levels between 3 and 5 in both countries' systems were considered as 'List with Criteria'; Level 6 in the German rating and SMR=4 in the French system were considered rejections, i.e. 'Do not List'.

² When an indirect comparison informs the submission as main clinical evidence, it is considered that a direct comparator is not present and therefore categorizes the evidence as 'low'.

³ Concerns raised around the magnitude of clinical benefit (e.g. is too little or confounded by other factors that are not related to the clinical design) may comprise but are not limited to: (1) Modest or low clinical benefit from trial; (2) The response of the pharmaceutical varied from study to study; (3) The response of the pharmaceutical is effective only in a sub-population; (4) The response of the pharmaceutical is not statistically significant compared with the comparator.

⁴ Concerns raised around the **generalizability of the population** used in the clinical evidence to the country of the HTA body may comprise but are not limited to: (1) the trial population is not generalizable to the country population due to ethnicity/ baseline characteristics and prevalence; (2) The trial population is not included/underrepresented the population of the indication under review; (3) Only a subgroup of the trial is considered suitable for the indication. Concerns raised around **generalizability of the clinical practice** of the clinical trials submitted by the manufacturer (e.g. administration route or pre- and concomitant medication or a different use of the resource of the health system) may comprise but are not limited to: (1) differences in the pathway in the clinical practice of the country; (2) differences in the administration and dose in comparison with the standard of care; (3) When the treatment criteria (e.g. baseline of the patients for starting the treatment) differed between the study and clinical practice; (4) A pharmaceutical may have limited use in the study country (e.g. PBAC clinical pathways).

⁵ Concerns around the safety profile of the medicine under evaluation stemmed from the clinical benefit evidence or the EPAR. It may comprise but is not limited to: (1) Substantial number of patients discontinuing the therapies due to adverse events; (2) EPAR with too many safety issues in comparison with current treatment used; and (3) There are notable adverse events that would lead to specific monitoring.

⁶ Concerns around the modelling used (e.g. in Markov/ partitioned survival model), or the extrapolation technique used for the clinical data may comprise but is not limited to: (1) the modelling used is not suitable; (2) the use of curves is not appropriate; (3) extrapolations method is not appropriate; (4) misrepresentation of the population under review or of some specific subgroup; (5) any computational errors.

⁷ Concerns around the use of a certain model (cost-minimization or cost-utility etc) in that may not suitable for the analysis.

⁸ Concerns around the **cost data** used to build the model leading to over- or under-estimation of the ICER may comprise but is not limited to: (1) some costs included in the model are too low or too high; (2) the model does not include specific cost that would lead to a over-estimation or under-estimation of the cost-effectiveness such as administration cost or wastage. Concerns around the **utility data** used to build the model leading to over- or under-estimation of the ICER may

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comprise but are not limited to: (1) the utility values used in the model are not suitable leading to over-estimation or under-estimation of the ICER; (2) the utility source is not suitable/ or the measured was not appropriate.

Source: The authors.

Table 3. Descriptive statistics

HTA/funding outcome				
Outcome type (DNL/LWC/L) N (% of total)	Do Not List (DNL) N=180 (13%)	List With Criteria (LWC) N=1,004 (71%)	List (L) N=231 (16%)	Total N=1,415 (100%)
Country (Agency) $\chi^2 = 253.395 (0.000)$				
Canada (CADTH)	29 (16%)	160 (16%)	9 (4%)	198 (14%)
France (HAS)	10 (6%)	156 (16%)	34 (15%)	200 (14%)
Canada (INESS)	65 (36%)	91 (9%)	24 (10%)	180 (13%)
Germany (IQWIG)	1 (1%)	107 (11%)	42 (18%)	150 (11%)
England (NICE)	11 (6%)	123 (12%)	13 (6%)	147 (10%)
Australia (PBAC)	36 (20%)	149 (15%)	5 (2%)	190 (13%)
Scotland (SMC)	18 (10%)	133 (13%)	45 (19%)	196 (14%)
Sweden (TLV)	10 (6%)	85 (8%)	59 (26%)	154 (11%)
Orphan status¹ $\chi^2 = 3.610 (0.164)$				
No	164 (91%)	891 (89%)	197 (85%)	1,252 (88%)
Yes	16 (9%)	113 (11%)	34 (15%)	163 (12%)
Therapeutic area $\chi^2 = 4.203 (0.122)$				
Non-oncology	103 (57%)	648 (65%)	153 (66%)	904 (64%)
Oncology	77 (43%)	356 (35%)	78 (34%)	511 (36%)
Funding mechanism <i>p-value = 0.000, Fisher's exact test</i>				
No funding	180 (100%)	0 (0%)	0 (0%)	180 (13%)
Unrestricted funding	0 (0%)	512 (51%)	231 (100%)	743 (53%)
Risk sharing	0 (0%)	439 (44%)	0 (0%)	439 (31%)
Special funding agreement	0 (0%)	53 (5%)	0 (0%)	53 (4%)
Prior rejection by HTA $\chi^2 = 28.469 (0.000)$				
No	124 (69%)	747 (74%)	206 (89%)	1,077 (76%)
Yes	56 (31%)	257 (26%)	25 (11%)	338 (24%)
Endpoint $\chi^2 = 9.657 (0.000)$				
No clinical endpoint	138 (77%)	848 (84%)	181 (78%)	1,167 (82%)
At least one clinical endpoint	42 (23%)	156 (16%)	50 (22%)	248 (18%)
Scheme of approval $\chi^2 = 13.150 (0.011)$				
Standard	127 (71%)	736 (73%)	191 (83%)	1,054 (74%)
Early approval	33 (18%)	153 (15%)	29 (13%)	215 (15%)
Parallel review	20 (11%)	115 (11%)	11 (5%)	146 (10%)
Comparator $\chi^2 = 23.961 (0.000)$				
No active comparator	113 (63%)	454 (45%)	92 (40%)	659 (47%)
At least one active comparator	67 (37%)	550 (55%)	139 (60%)	756 (53%)
Trial phase $\chi^2 = 2.203 (0.332)$				
No phase III trial	35 (19%)	155 (15%)	41 (18%)	231 (16%)
At least one phase III trial	145 (81%)	849 (85%)	190 (82%)	1,184 (84%)
Clinical restrictions $\chi^2 = 494.980 (0.000)$				
No restrictions	180 (100%)	352 (35%)	231 (100%)	763 (54%)
Population restrictions	0 (0%)	400 (40%)	0 (0%)	400 (28%)
Dosing restrictions	0 (0%)	142 (14%)	0 (0%)	142 (10%)
Population and dosing restrictions	0 (0%)	110 (11%)	0 (0%)	110 (8%)

Quality of evidence (QoE) $\chi^2 = 25.160 (0.000)$				
Good quality	20 (11%)	201 (20%)	69 (30%)	290 (20%)
Average quality	88 (49%)	483 (48%)	88 (38%)	659 (47%)
Poor quality	72 (40%)	320 (32%)	74 (32%)	466 (33%)
ICER (categorical) $\chi^2 = 33.386 (0.000)$				
Cost utility & explicit ICER	68 (38%)	396 (39%)	73 (32%)	537 (38%)
Cost utility & confidential ICER	37 (21%)	114 (11%)	14 (6%)	165 (12%)
Other models ²	38 (21%)	222 (22%)	58 (25%)	318 (22%)
Economic evaluation not conducted ³	37 (21%)	272 (27%)	86 (37%)	395 (28%)
Social value judgments				
Severity $\chi^2 = 0.568 (0.753)$				
Not considered	134 (74%)	737 (73%)	175 (76%)	1,046 (74%)
Considered	46 (26%)	267 (27%)	56 (24%)	369 (26%)
Unmet need $\chi^2 = 20.443 (0.000)$				
Not considered	99 (55%)	546 (54%)	163 (71%)	808 (57%)
Considered	81 (45%)	458 (46%)	68 (29%)	607 (43%)
Administrative advantage $\chi^2 = 5.361 (0.069)$				
Not considered	139 (77%)	774 (77%)	194 (84%)	1,107 (78%)
Considered	41 (23%)	230 (23%)	37 (16%)	308 (22%)
Innovation $\chi^2 = 10.268 (0.006)$				
Not considered	160 (89%)	842 (84%)	211 (91%)	1,213 (86%)
Considered	20 (11%)	162 (16%)	20 (9%)	202 (14%)
Clinical uncertainties				
Clinical benefit $\chi^2 = 8.057 (0.018)$				
No uncertainty	80 (44%)	515 (51%)	135 (58%)	730 (52%)
At least one uncertainty	100 (56%)	489 (49%)	96 (42%)	685 (48%)
Adverse events $\chi^2 = 3.048 (0.218)$				
No uncertainty	122 (68%)	733 (73%)	174 (75%)	1,029 (73%)
At least one uncertainty	58 (32%)	271 (27%)	57 (25%)	386 (27%)
Generalizability $\chi^2 = 12.917 (0.002)$				
No uncertainty	102 (57%)	659 (66%)	170 (74%)	931 (66%)
At least one uncertainty	78 (43%)	345 (34%)	61 (26%)	484 (34%)
Economic uncertainties				
Modelling $\chi^2 = 15.452 (0.000)$				
No uncertainty	117 (65%)	648 (65%)	180 (78%)	945 (67%)
At least one uncertainty	63 (35%)	356 (35%)	51 (22%)	470 (33%)
Model inputs $\chi^2 = 12.745 (0.002)$				
No uncertainty	115 (64%)	714 (71%)	184 (80%)	1,013 (72%)
At least one uncertainty	65 (36%)	290 (29%)	47 (20%)	402 (28%)
HTA model $\chi^2 = 42.959 (0.000)$				
Clinical benefit assessment	11 (6%)	263 (26%)	76 (33%)	350 (25%)
Clinical & cost-effectiveness	169 (94%)	741 (74%)	155 (67%)	1,065 (75%)
HTA Agency type $\chi^2 = 16.364 (0.000)$				
Not all molecules evaluated	122 (68%)	540 (54%)	112 (48%)	774 (55%)
All molecules evaluated	58 (32%)	464 (46%)	119 (52%)	641 (45%)
Months from MA to HTA/funding decision $\chi^2 = 187.891 (0.033)$				
Mean (SD)	14.85 (15.19)	12.10 (13.99)	9.68 (12.37)	12.05 (13.96)
Min ⁴	0	0	0	0

Max	115	113	82	115
HTA/funding decision year $\chi^2 = 48.946 (0.000)$				
Mean (SD)	2015 (2)	2015 (2)	2014 (2)	2015 (2)
Min	2009	2009	2008	2008
Max	2018	2018	2018	2018
GDP⁵ $\chi^2 = 295.756 (0.000)$				
Mean (SD)	46,913 (3,619)	46,020 (3,812)	45,884 (4,504)	46,112 (3,919)
Min	37,154	34,712	34,712	34,712
Max	56,689	56,689	56,689	56,689

Note: ¹ No orphan status designation is present in Canada.

² Other models include cost minimization, cost comparison and cost consequence analyses.

³ Economic evaluation may be required in France, but it is not a key decision criterion and is not required in Germany. In the Canadian province of Quebec, cost-effectiveness analysis is not conducted if clinical benefit is deemed to be insufficient.

⁴ Zero months from MA to HTA/funding decision are recorded in Australia, where the parallel review process allows PBAC to approve pharmaceutical products concurrently before their marketing authorization.

⁵ OECD (2021), Gross domestic product (GDP) (indicator). doi: 10.1787/dc2f7aec-en (Accessed on 17 February 2021).

Source: The authors.

Table 4. Results of linear regression for Time to HTA recommendation analysis

Variables (base)	All Countries	Excluding France and Germany
ACTIVE COMPARATOR (NO ACTIVE COMPARATOR)	-0.201* (0.121)	-0.260* (0.154)
CLINICAL ENDPOINT (NO CLINICAL ENDPOINT)	0.0373 (0.136)	0.0201 (0.177)
PHASE III RCT (OTHER PHASE/INDIRECT COMPARISON)	0.740*** (0.207)	0.953*** (0.255)
RESUBMIT (NO RESUBMIT)	0.842*** (0.146)	0.871*** (0.186)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (NON-OPRHAN)	0.431*** (0.153)	0.763*** (0.183)
ACCELERATED APPROVAL (STANDARD APPROVAL)	0.0502 (0.147)	0.0918 (0.187)
PARALLEL REVIEW (STANDARD APPROVAL)	-2.521*** (0.380)	-2.330*** (0.372)
UNRESTRICTED FUNDING (NO FUNDING)	-0.116 (0.174)	0.0179 (0.194)
RISK SHARING AGREEMENT (RSA) (NO FUNDING)	-0.758*** (0.188)	-0.784*** (0.195)
SPECIAL FUNDING (NO FUNDING)	0.383 (0.292)	0.310 (0.297)
HTA MODEL (CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS)	0.240* (0.126)	
HTA AGENCY TYPE (NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	-0.362*** (0.124)	-0.530*** (0.137)
ln_GDP	-6.028*** (1.062)	-9.889*** (1.508)
HTA YEAR	0.397*** (0.0571)	0.552*** (0.0756)
Constant	-734.4*** (105.8)	-1,004*** (138.6)
Observations	1,415	1,065
R-squared	0.233	0.250

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 5. Factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations: Results of multinomial regression for core variables (full sample of 8 countries)

Variables	Full model	
	LWC	L
DNL base case	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)
RESUBMIT	0.833	0.295***
(NO RESUBMIT)	(0.160)	(0.0810)
ONCOLOGY	0.580***	0.799
(no ONCOLOGY)	(0.118)	(0.208)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION	0.469*	0.637
(NON-OPRHAN)	(0.193)	(0.309)
ONCOLOGY#ORPHAN	3.765**	4.579**
(Interaction)	(2.288)	(3.207)
HIGH QoE	2.168***	3.278***
(LOW QoE)	(0.633)	(1.111)
AVERAGE QoE	1.297	1.033
(LOW QoE)	(0.246)	(0.255)
HTA MODEL	0.122***	0.104***
(CLINICAL EFFECTIVENESS)	(0.0409)	(0.0390)
HTA AGENCY TYPE	2.785***	2.271***
(NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	(0.677)	(0.648)
ln_GDP	0.0932	1.942
	(0.200)	(4.930)
HTA YEAR	0.909	0.736***
	(0.0739)	(0.0676)
SEVERITY RECORDED	1.160	1.451
(SEVERITY NOT RECORDED)	(0.261)	(0.404)
INNOVATION RECORDED	2.292***	1.675
(INNOVATION NOT RECORDED)	(0.682)	(0.645)
ADMIN ADVANTAGE RECOR.	1.563*	1.439
(ADMIN ADVANTAGE NOT RECOR.)	(0.368)	(0.437)
UNMET NEED RECORDED	1.552**	0.864
(UNMET NEED NOT RECORDED)	(0.332)	(0.236)
CLINICAL BENEFIT RECORDED.	0.618**	0.623*
(CLIN BENEFIT NOT RECORDED)	(0.139)	(0.169)
GENERALISABILITY RECORDED	0.561***	0.533**
(GEN/BILITY NOT RECORDED)	(0.117)	(0.138)
MODELLING RECORDED	2.229***	1.506
(MODELLING NOT RECORDED)	(0.483)	(0.438)
INPUT RECORDED	0.682*	0.684
(INPUT NOT RECORDED)	(0.142)	(0.188)
Constant	1.418e+96	3.525e+26
		5***
	(2.081e+9	(5.815e+26
	8)	7)

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Observations (1,415)

Pseudo R-squared 0.102

Chi2 217.5

Prob > chi2 0

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Table 6. Factors associated with HTA coverage recommendations: Results of multinomial regression for core variables (sample of 6 countries, excluding France and Germany)

Variables	<i>Full model</i>	
	LWC	L
<i>DNL base case</i>	RRR (SE)	RRR (SE)
RESUBMIT (NO RESUBMIT)	0.861 (0.171)	0.220*** (0.0757)
ONCOLOGY (no ONCOLOGY)	0.614** (0.133)	0.394*** (0.133)
ORPHAN DESIGNATION (NON-OPRHAN)	0.500 (0.224)	0.416 (0.248)
ONCOLOGY#ORPHAN (Interaction)	3.929** (2.708)	11.29*** (9.914)
HIGH QoE (LOW QoE)	1.939** (0.583)	3.704*** (1.351)
AVERAGE QoE (LOW QoE)	1.326 (0.264)	1.198 (0.345)
EXPLICIT ICER (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)	1.926** (0.499)	2.774** (1.102)
OTHER ECONOMIC MODELS (CONFIDENTIAL ICER)	1.338 (0.347)	2.309** (0.912)
HTA AGENCY TYPE (NOT ALL MEDICINES ASSESSED)	2.829*** (0.717)	2.470*** (0.748)
ln_GDP	0.156 (0.379)	0.626 (1.926)
HTA YEAR	0.896 (0.0776)	0.782** (0.0809)
SEVERITY RECORDED (SEVERITY NOT RECORDED)	1.096 (0.261)	1.245 (0.409)
INNOVATION RECORDED (INNOVATION NOT RECORDED)	2.069** (0.631)	1.423 (0.625)
ADMIN ADVANTAGE RECOR. (ADMIN ADVANTAGE NOT RECOR.)	1.497* (0.356)	1.653 (0.536)
UNMET NEED RECORDED (UNMET NEED NOT RECORDED)	1.547** (0.334)	0.797 (0.242)
CLINICAL BENEFIT RECORDED. (CLIN BENEFIT NOT RECORDED)	0.659* (0.152)	0.736 (0.225)
GENERALISABILITY RECORDED (GEN/BILITY NOT RECORDED)	0.630** (0.137)	0.433*** (0.132)
MODELLING RECORDED (MODELLING NOT RECORDED)	2.054*** (0.449)	1.425 (0.444)
INPUT RECORDED (INPUT NOT RECORDED)	0.645** (0.135)	0.658 (0.194)
Constant	5.010e+1 04 (7.743e+1 06)	1.043e+217 *** (1.915e+21 9)

A horizontal and vertical expose of lessons learned and policy recommendations

Observations (1,062)

Pseudo R-squared 0.110

Chi2 176.2

Prob > chi2 0

Robust standard errors in parentheses

*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Appendix VII. Lists of Ethnographic observations of appraisal processes and stakeholders interviews

Appendix VII.A. Ethnographic Observations of Scottish Medicines Consortium (SMC)

Treatment indication and regulatory authorisation	Process Modifiers	Patient & Clinician Engagement (PACE)	SMC Appraisal	Recommendation (5 weeks after appraisal)
Tisagenlecleucel (Kymriah) One-off cell therapy pats up to 25 years old with B-cell acute lymphoblastic leukaemia in relapse post-transplant or 2 nd /later relapse	Ultra-orphan framework <i>End-of-life</i>	11 Nov 2018	8 Jan 2019	Accepted as per indication
Patisiran (Onpattro) IV infusion every 3 weeks hATTR amyloidosis in adults with stage 1 or 2 polyneuropathy	Ultra-orphan framework <i>Unmet need¹, Substantial improvement in QoL</i>	9 Apr 2019	7 May 2019	Accepted as per indication
Lumacaftor-ivacaftor (Orkambi) ² Tablet or granules twice daily cystic fibrosis ≥6 years old and 2-5 years homozygous for 508del mutation	Orphan-equivalent <i>Unmet need¹</i>	11 Jun 2019	2 Jul 2019	Not recommended ³
Tezacaftor-ivacaftor (Symkevi) & Ivacaftor Combination tablet in morning, monotherapy in evening Cystic fibrosis ≥12 years old homozygous 508 del mutation or with a range of other stated mutations	Orphan-equivalent <i>Unmet need¹, Substantial improvement in QoL</i>			Not recommended ³
voretigene neparvovec (Luxturna) One-off gene therapy Vision loss due to inherited retinal disorder caused by biallelic RPE65 mutations and with sufficient viable retinal cells	Ultra-orphan pathway <i>None stated as no recommendation</i>	Not applicable, but attended New Drugs Committee 24 Sep 2019	5 Nov 2019	Initial assessment of clinical and cost effectiveness before mandatory data collection
Onasemnogene abeparvovec (Zolgensma) One-off gene therapy 5q SMA with bi-allelic mutation in SMN1 gene and clinical diagnosis of spinal muscular atrophy (SMA) Type 1, or up to 3 copies of SMN2	Orphan-equivalent <i>Substantial improvement in life expectancy Substantial improvement in QoL</i>	13 Jan 2021	2 Feb 2021	Accepted with restriction specifying pre-symptomatic patients “expected to develop SMA Type 1”

¹“absence of other treatments of proven benefit”; ²previously rejected by SMC in 2016;

³Revised pricing agreement 4/9/20 to include - ivacaftor-tezacaftor-elexacaftor (Kaftrio) at time of licensing “which means that many patients with rare mutations which fall outside of scope of EMAs current licensing considerations will also be able to benefit from Kaftrio” CF Trust explains this is for patients with rare mutations covered in US FDA license.”

Appendix VII.B. Table B: Ethnographic Observations of National Institute for Health and Care Excellence, England

Treatment indication and regulatory authorisation	Process	Appraisal Observation	Process after Observation	Recommendation
Voretigene neparvovec 2020) (Luxturna) One-off gene therapy Vision loss due to inherited retinal dystrophy caused by confirmed biallelic RPE65 mutations with sufficient viable retinal cells	Highly Specialised Technology (HST)	25 July 2019	Draft report published Aug 2019 (recommended use)	Recommended as per indication 9 Oct 2019
Volanesorsen (Waylivra) Sc injection once weekly for 3 months, then once fortnightly with stopping rule Adjunct to diet in adults with genetically confirmed familial chylomicronaemia syndrome and at high risk for pancreatitis in whom response to diet and triglyceride lowering therapy has been inadequate	HST	28 Nov 2019	26 Feb 2020 2 nd Appraisal Committee to discuss responses to draft report	Recommended as per indication 21 Oct 2020
Emapalumab (Gamifant) iv infusion every 3-4 days until stem cell transplant Primary paediatric haemophagocytic lymphohistiocytosis with refractory, recurrent or progressive disease or intolerance to conventional HLH therapies	Technology Appraisal (TA)	(Technical Engagement 6 Mar 2020) 6 May 2020	23 Jul 2020 EMA refusal, so suspension of appraisal	Suspended
Onasemnogene abeparvovec (Zolgensma)* One-off gene therapy 5q SMA with bi-allelic mutation in SMN1 gene and clinical diagnosis of SMA Type 1, or up to 3 copies of SMN2	HST	8 Oct 2020 public information only	10 Feb 2021 2 nd Appraisal Committee	<i>Draft Guidance 8 March 2021</i> <i>Symptomatic</i> - 6 months or younger, - 7 to 12 months and agreed by national multidisciplinary team via auditable criteria, (excluding those who require permanent ventilation for >16 hrs/day or tracheostomy) <i>Pre-symptomatic</i> - via conditions in OBMEA

* observation non-focal and/or confirmatory

Appendix VII.C. Ethnographic Observations of CADTH, Canada

Treatment indication and regulatory authorisation	Process	Appraisal	Process after observation	Recommendation
Voretigene neparvovec (Luxturna) One-off gene therapy patients with vision loss due to inherited retinal dystrophy (IRD) caused by RPE65 mutations	Canadian Drug Expert Committee (CDEC)	16 Sep 2020	Interactions with MAH re draft recommendation	Recommended, subject to <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • initiation criteria • prescribing conditions • pricing conditions (reduction in price) November 2020 Reports available January 2021

Appendix VII.D. Interviews

Coded Number	Interviewee role	HTA body	Duration (minutes)
1	Committee member	SMC	30
2	Committee member	SMC	61
3	Committee member	SMC	79
4	Patient Group representative	n/a	83
5	Committee member	SMC	37
6	Committee member	SMC	51
7	Patient Group representative	n/a	70
8	Committee member	NICE	48
9	Committee member	NICE	65
10	Committee member	SMC	54
11	Committee member	NICE	53
12	HTA staff (4 individuals)	SMC	108
13	Committee member	SMC	50
14	Committee member	SMC	67
15	Patient group representative	n/a	47
16	Clinical expert	NICE	45
17	MAH	n/a	57
18	HTA staff	NICE	77
19	Patient group representatives (2 individuals)	n/a	61
20	Committee member	SMC	60
21	Committee member	NICE	64
22	Committee member	NICE	63
23	Committee member	NICE	58
24	HTA assessment group	NICE	40
25	HTA assessment group/TA member (2 individuals)	NICE	59

Appendix VIII. Stakeholder engagement and dissemination activities

Free Public Meetings	
WP10 webinar series January-May 2021	Webinar #1: Special processes to appraise rare disease treatments (RDTs) – developing feasible, consistent approaches – January 2020 Webinar #2: Outcomes-Based Managed Entry Agreements (OBMEA) for Rare Disease Treatments – February 2021 Webinar #3: Better use of Patient Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) and Health State Utility Values in appraisal of Rare Disease Treatments – March 2021 Webinar #4: Appraisal Framework suitable for Rare Disease Treatments – May 2021
Conferences	
HTAi 2021 June 2021	Panel: Innovating HTA to support novel interventions for rare diseases Panel: Using OBMEA to develop evidence for RDTs Workshop: Patient group submission template for re-appraisal after OBMEA
HTA conference, Greece March 2021	Presentation: An appraisal framework for Rare Disease Treatments
World Orphan Drug Conference Europe (WODC) November 2020	Panel: Special processes to appraise rare disease treatments – developing feasible, consistent approaches
ISPOR Europe November 2020	Panel: Do HTA need special approaches for patient reported outcomes in rare diseases? Presentation: Using PROMs in HTA for rare diseases
Orphan Drugs for Rare Diseases Conference October 2020	Key note: Appraising orphan drugs – how should we determine value?
HTAi September 2020	Panel: do we need special processes to appraise rare disease treatments?
PSI June 2020	Panel: Real-World Evidence for HTA of highly innovative technologies
DIA ATMPs workshop May 2020	Moderation of panel: Resolving HTA/Payer uncertainties with real-world evidence (RWE)
European Conference on Rare Diseases May 2020	Panel: Do we need special processes to appraisal rare disease treatments?
WODC Europe November 2019	Panel: RWE and Early Dialogues for HTA of rare disease treatment
ISPOR Europe November 2019	Poster: Predicting health utilities from patient reported outcome measures in rare diseases: a systematic review of mapping studies
DIA ATMPs workshop October 2019	Presentation: RWE for decisions about highly innovative technologies
iHEA July 2019	Presentation: Predicting Health Utilities from Patient-Reported Outcome Measures (PROMs) in Rare Diseases: a systematic review and quality appraisal of ‘mapping’ studies
AIES October 2019	Presentation: Predicting health utilities from PROMs in rare diseases: a systematic review of mapping studies
WODC Europe November 2018	Organisation of half-day workshop: “Managed Access ... Are they the holy grail?”
HTAi June 2019	Organisation of full day workshop “Appraising treatments for rare diseases”

MAP BioPharma October 2018	Presentation: Overcoming HTA Challenges for Rare Disease Treatments
eMBA Symposium HEC November 2018	Presentation: Health technology assessment and rare diseases: Challenges and ways forward
NextLevel Pharma December 2018:	Presentation: What is special about treatments for rare diseases from an HTA perspective?
EURORDIS Symposium February 2019	Panel discussion about pricing and reimbursement of treatments for rare diseases
Closed Policy/HTA Meetings	
Canadian Organisation for Rare Diseases June 2021	Presentation of Appraisal Framework to inform Canadian development of rare disease policy
OECD Expert Group on Pharmaceuticals and Medical Devices, May 2021 and 2019	Presentation on OBMEA tools and links to OECD work
CADTH scientific team May 2021	Discussion of OBMEA tools and granting of permission to use in new RWE processes
SMC Leaders May 2021	Confidential feedback on ethnographic observations
Scottish Government April 2021	Presentation on OBMEA tools
RWE4Decisions discussion with DG Santé March 2021	Sharing of OBMEA findings
Association of British Pharmaceutical Industries, Scotland December 2020	Presentation and discussion about RWE and OBMEA – opportunities for Scotland
NICE Methods Review March 2020	Presentation of emerging results to NICE Executive team
Northwind 12 th Annual Life Sciences Invitational Forum Health and Bio/Life Sciences Toronto, May 2019	Keynote: Appraisal of Rare Disease Treatments – What can EU Research Tell Us?

Appendix IX. Country Vignette - Lithuania

Scope of vignette:

- authorised products (with marketing authorisation)
- decision process about routine use (and not individual requests for reimbursement)
- submissions for P&R made by manufacturers

Green = related to/any special considerations for rare disease and ultra-rare disease treatments

Orange = latest changes (September 2020)

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
<p>Overview of health system and P&R/HTA process</p>	<p>Tax based system [1]</p> <p>HTA exist only at national level: The SMCA (state medicine control agency), the Ministry of Health and the NHIF (payer) are the main parties in P&R/HTA process</p> <p>Formally, the final decision is made by the Minister of Health based on the recommendations from the Reimbursement Committee and NHIF</p> <p>The Reimbursement Committee (representatives from the Ministry of Health, NHIF, University hospitals, PAG, NGO of GP's, Academy) advises the Minister of Health on reimbursement decisions. Advice is issued within an assessment report</p> <p>The SMCA is responsible for the assessment of new medicine submissions and issuing the assessment report to the decision-makers, which then becomes public. It includes assessment of the key domain (see key domains in assessment section)</p> <p>Responsibilities of NHIF in common process:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -assessment of the budget impact of each new medicine submission; 	<p>This special process has been recently updated, and updates are effective since September 29, 2020 [4].</p> <p>The special process has its own regulation, but the actors (SMCA, NHIF) are the same. Decision bodies and budgets are different. It was developed about 10 years ago when the common process together with evidence “requirements” was introduced and rare diseases had emerged as “different”. The update in September 2020 included a “mandatory added benefit assessment based on comparative trial non-surrogate endpoint outcomes”.</p> <p>A special process applies to Very Rare health Conditions (VRC), which is the focus of this special process (not a medicine)</p> <p>An OMP (or any other medicinal product) will be routed through this special process only if it is intended to treat a VRC (see details in section “Appraisal framework”)</p> <p>The reimbursement of medicines to treat a VRC is regulated by a special order of the Ministry of Health</p>

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
	<p>-assessment of the company’s OB-MEA in case it is a part of submission;</p> <p>-contracting whatever risk sharing agreement (PVA, „capping“, OB-MEA)</p> <p>-paying for medicines</p> <p>-procuring high-cost pharmaceuticals via public tenders</p> <p>The MoH issued order No. 159 regulates the inclusion process for placing medicines on a reimbursable (positive) list [3]</p>	<p>The decision-making body in this special process is the Very Rare Conditions Committee (VRCC)</p>
<p>Differentiation of rare disease treatments in the P&R system</p>	<p>A very rare (<1/200,000 newly diagnosed cases of the Lithuanian population per year) human health condition (referred to as “very rare condition” - VRC) is defined as a health disorder, which is life-threatening and/or causing significant permanent disability, and may be subject to an effective etiological (a factor affecting the onset of the disease) or a pathogenic (the factor responsible for the clinical course of the disease) treatment, when the treatment costs of this very rare condition are not reimbursed, and when the treatment can increase the patient's survival and (or) reduce disability (or prevent the increase in disability).</p> <p>Eligibility to the special process (individualised-VRC and generalised VRC) is based on whether the medicine is considered rare according to the criteria stated in the previous paragraph. The number of patients living with a rare condition relies on the orpha.net statistics. The submission will include the precise definition of health condition and is assigned an ORPHA code. Other approaches to define the rarity of a condition accepted within the VRC process includes, e.g. good quality year by year statistics from a recognised center, etc.</p>	
<p>Eligible medicines</p>	<p>The submission drives both the special process and CDR process. If there is no submission, neither the special nor the common-reimbursement process starts. This is the only route through which products would be selected for the special (very rare condition) process. Without an application and consequent appraisal, the product is not reimbursed and can only be accessed commercially</p>	
<p>Process</p>	<p>The MoH issued an order, No. 159, that outlines the guidelines for assessment (for the entity preparing the submission), and the appraisal framework (see appraisal framework section [3])</p>	<p>The MoH’s order regulates the special process that is in place</p> <p>The special process starts with the submission to the VRCC</p>

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - The standard process starts with the submission (comparative efficacy and effectiveness, cost-effectiveness, budget impact, etc.) from industry to the SMCA directly - The four key domains (see section “Key domains in assessment”) are assessed and the SMCA makes its conclusions on the added health benefit and cost-effectiveness, and the NHIF on the budget impact - The assessments’ conclusions are approved/rejected/corrected during deliberation process by Reimbursement Committee (RC), who then issues a final recommendation to the Minister of Health on whether to include or not onto the positive-waiting list - After each review by NHIF of the budget, medicines from the positive-waiting list are included into the positive-actual list (effective reimbursement) 	<p>Two types of submission are intended:</p> <p>Individual-VRC-case are based on hospital submissions (hospital acts as applicant) to the VRCC for the treatment of an individual patient.</p> <p>Generalised-VRC-case are based on university hospital or physicians society submissions to the VRCC requesting for the medicinal product to be included into the special positive list for a VRC treatment</p> <p>The main differences of this special process (for very rare conditions) with the CDR process are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - cost-effectiveness is not assessed - no waiting list in case of positive (to reimburse medicine for a very rare condition) decision
<p>Disease specific expert input (e.g. clinicians or patients in any stage of the process)</p>	<p>Specialty medical societies and patient organizations are proactively asked to provide their structured opinion about submission related topics (positioning, current treatment problems, unmet needs, etc.)</p>	<p>University hospitals representing physicians (Concilium) act as submitters of individual patient applications</p>
<p>Key domains in assessment</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Comparative efficacy - Comparative effectiveness - Cost-effectiveness (based on cost-effectiveness analysis; part of submission) - Budget impact 	<p>For a positive decision, it is mandatory that the conclusions from the SMCA involve a positive added benefit assessment, based on proof that the medicine prolongs survival and/or reduces disability (or prevents it come increasing) in comparison to Lithuanian’s current standard of care. The proof should be based on the assessment of trial direct (non-surrogate) endpoints</p>

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
Evidentiary requirements	Systemic literature review of published RCTs are prioritised; other systemic reviews of peer-reviewed evidence are accepted; indirect treatment comparisons are accepted	Peer reviewed publications
PROMs	None	
Appraisal framework	<p>The appraisal of comparative efficacy may result in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) a positive recommendation if comparative efficacy is superior or non- inferior⁵; 2) a negative recommendation if superiority or non-inferiority are not proven, or if the quality of evidence presented is not acceptable <p>The appraisal of comparative effectiveness may result in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) a positive recommendation if comparative effectiveness is deemed to add benefit (or non-inferior) to patient health 2) a negative recommendation if added or non-inferior benefit to patient health is not proven <p>The appraisal of cost-effectiveness may result in:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) a positive recommendation if the intervention proves to be cost-effective 2) a negative recommendation if the intervention does NOT prove to be cost-effective 	<p>The appraisal process aims to determine compliance (or not) to ALL of the following criteria:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) The medicine should have one of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • OMP designation; • the registered indication should specify treatment of a VRC-in-Lithuania; • proof from a peer-reviewed publication that the medicine has potential to treat a VRC by its mode of action; • proof from a peer-reviewed publication and/or guidance that the medicine could be used to treat a VRC, <p>AND</p> 2) There should be a proof of a therapeutic benefit (see section – “Key domains in assessment”), <p>AND</p>

⁵ Also referred to as “levelled difference”, which doesn’t limit the added benefit assessment to clinical efficacy but in broader terms would also be applicable to (demonstrating a levelled difference in terms of) effectiveness and cost-effectiveness

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
	<p>Summarizing conclusion (one of the following):</p> <p>1) superior comparative efficacy, added patient health benefit (clinical effectiveness), cost-effective (based on cost-utility analysis) compared to 3 different thresholds based on relative (proportional) magnitude of quality-adjusted-life-expectancy (QALE) shortfall, compared to the current available treatment. The QALE shortfall ranges of [0-0,49], [0,5-0,74], [0,75-1] correspond to 1, 3, 5 times the national GDP/per capita; with or without a patient-access-scheme (PAS)</p> <p>2) non-inferior comparative efficacy, with similar patient health benefit (clinical effectiveness) and cost-minimization; with or without PAS.</p> <p>3) superior comparative efficacy with equivalence (the exact wording – “levelled difference in patient health benefit”) in clinical effectiveness, and being cost-effective (based on cost-utility analysis) if there is an outcomes-based risk-sharing-agreement arranged or cost-minimization presented (based on non-inferiority¹ or levelled difference in added benefit)</p>	<p>3) Funding is available</p>
Reimbursement decision	<p>Decision is made by the reimbursement committee based on the summarizing conclusion (see section “Appraisal framework”) after deliberation. They approve/reject/remake the summarizing conclusion. If Committee members vote against the recommendation, they would have to make a strong case as to their reasons.</p>	<p>The reimbursement decision is made by the VRCC and is positive, only if all criteria (see section “Appraisal framework”) are met</p>
Pricing process	<p>Price negotiation informed by cost-effectiveness</p>	<p>If the cost per patient is more than EUR 29,000/per year, but less than EUR 100,000/per year, the price should be negotiated (special regulation; country expert’s remark: based on referencing to international prices of the medicine (i.e. not more than the average of the three cheapest within a grouping of reference countries similar to Lithuania from an economic development perspective)</p>

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
		<p>If the cost per patient is more EUR 100,000/per year, an OB-MEA should be implemented</p>
<p>Managed entry agreements</p>	<p>The order of the MoH regulates the risk-sharing agreements that are in place</p> <p>The actual schemes include discounts, capping of patient numbers, price-volume, or OBMEAs</p> <p>In 2020, changes were made including discounted treatment initiation for individual patients, capping of individual patient costs, capping of individual patient medicine utilization, specifying money-back guarantee, conditional treatment continuation agreements</p>	<p>The same order of the MoH regulating risk-sharing agreements than in the common process is applicable to VRC</p>
<p>Main challenges in appraising medicines for rare diseases</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -The primary focus of the VRC concept and process in Lithuania is not related to appraising medicines for rare diseases - Lack of well-organised real-world data - Lack of data collection and analysing system in case OBMEAs are introduced. 	
<p>Impact of special processes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Currently, 9 medicines are included in the special (very rare condition treatment) reimbursement list - Altogether 136 applications for the treatment of individual patients were submitted since 2016, with 44% of them being oncology treatments 	
<p>Proposed policy change</p>	<p>The current changes made in the VRC process (“mandatory added benefit assessment based on comparative trial non-surrogate end points outcomes”) have resulted in some confusion around the application of specific criteria around the added benefit evidentiary requirements.</p>	
<p>Joint initiatives</p>	<p>Are not known by author in the field of appraising medicines for rare diseases</p>	
<p>SOURCES</p>		

Lithuania	Standard process (non-orphan drugs) - Common Reimbursement Process (CDR)	Special processes (orphan and ultra-orphan drugs)
1	http://www.vlk.lt/sites/en/health-insurance-in-Lithuania/health-insurance-system	
2	http://www.who.int/health-laws/countries/ltu-en.pdf	
3	https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/7d7024009a9411eaa51db668f0092944?ifwid=5ob7msq1q	
4	https://e-seimas.lrs.lt/portal/legalAct/lt/TAD/652656b0b00311e59010bea026bdb259/asr	

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This vignette was compiled based on information provided by country experts and desk research. The information provided may be incomplete or contain inaccuracies. If you have any comments or updates, please email us at the following email addresses:

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Appendix X. Description of the choice tasks and frequency of choices

Choice task	Scenario 1			Scenario 2			Choice statistics	
	Health loss	Reversibility	Savings	Health loss	Reversibility	Savings	choices (N)	Scenario 1 chosen*
1	Small	Possible, anytime	10%	Very small	Hardly possible	10%	170	77%
2	Very small	Hardly possible	5%	Significant	Possible, anytime	15%	156	56%
3	Significant	Possible, anytime	5%	Very small	Possible, delays	10%	157	5%
4	Small	Possible, delays	10%	Very small	Possible, anytime	10%	161	7%
5	Significant	Possible, delays	15%	Small	Possible, anytime	5%	157	15%
6	Small	Hardly possible	15%	Significant	Possible, anytime	5%	160	82%
7	Very small	Possible, delays	5%	Very small	Hardly possible	15%	157	68%
8	Significant	Hardly possible	10%	Small	Possible, delays	15%	130	3%

Appendix XI. Ethical/Political Checklist

Questions and main recommendations	Yes	No
1 - Mainstreaming /exhaustivity		
<i>Q1 - Are all types of d-CEIs systematically identified in the literature and documented, with their respective level of evidence?</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
2 - Inclusion of patients or prescribers' perspectives in the evaluation process		
<i>Q2: Are the patients concerned by the d-CEI clearly identified?</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
➤ Q2bis: if so, can they document the consequences of the d-CEI on their experience of living with the disease?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Q3: Are the prescribers treating those patients clearly identified?</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
➤ Q3.bis: if so, can they identify the consequences of the d-CEI in clinical experience when treating patients living with the disease?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
3 - Transparency		
<i>Q4: Can patients or prescribers identify patients or other populations who will benefit of the reallocation and do they understand why?</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
<i>Q5: Are their contributions explicitly included in the evaluation process as a source of information?</i>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
➤ Q5bis: If so, are they associated more formally (vote, MCDA, ...)?	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
4 - Social justice and ethics		

Q6: Are the objective(s) of considering a d-CEI explicitly defined?

- | | | |
|--|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| 1. Improving overall population health | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 2. Prioritising health needs of vulnerable populations | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| 3. Improving the sustainability of the healthcare system | | |
| a. In routine care (reducing inefficient use of resources) | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| b. In case of shortages (drugs, vaccines) | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Q7 - ex ante (behind the 'veil of ignorance',) is it possible for those involved in the assessment to agree that it can be fair to consider and possibly to adopt, based on pairwise comparisons of:

- | | | |
|---|--------------------------|--------------------------|
| ➤ One patient receiving the d-CEI with another patient with the same condition receiving the i-CEI; | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |
| ➤ One patient receiving the d-CEI and a patient (or one individual) benefiting of the reallocation | <input type="checkbox"/> | <input type="checkbox"/> |

Q8: - ex post, in case the patient has received the d-CEI, will this patient have access to the i-DCEI if experiencing unacceptable side-effects, or disease progression.

	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	--------------------------	--------------------------

Q9: Are the social justice principles governing the reallocation of savings explicitly defined (Maximin principle, proportionate universalism)?

	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
--	--------------------------	--------------------------